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Optimal choice of spatially adaptive parameters in total generalized variation via bilevel optimization with applications to Fourier inpainting

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Chapter 1

Introduction

This work is essentially concerned with the reconstruction of clean images from noisy or otherwise corrupted measurements. In our understanding, a grey scale image is a mapping

$$u : \Omega \rightarrow \mathbb{R} \tag{1.1}$$

where $\Omega \subset \mathbb{R}^n$ denotes a bounded Lipschitz domain. If not stated differently every statement in this thesis is valid at least for $n = 2$. However, most of the theorems do not require this restriction and it is possible to choose general $n \in \mathbb{N}$. Although we only deal with grey scale images in this work, an extension to RGB images is in principle possible by looking at functions $u : \Omega \rightarrow \mathbb{R}^3$.

In contrast to our continuous interpretation of images, there is also a large part of the existing literature that directly considers pictures as discrete objects $u^h : \Omega^h \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ where $\Omega^h = \{1, \dots, N\} \times \{1, \dots, M\}$ is a regular quadratic grid and $N \cdot M$ denotes the number of pixels. The advantage of our continuous viewpoint is twofold.

On the one hand we have the whole toolbox of functional analysis and PDE theory at our disposal and on the other hand we can assume that once we have shown the proper functionality of our method in the infinite dimensional function space, the algorithm will probably also work well in every possible discretization, regardless of the resolution. For a nice account and further information on this so called *first optimize then discretize* approach we refer to the textbook [HPUU08].

The model problem of image processing, which we will consider in this thesis falls into the category of so-called inverse problems. However it is not the aim of this work to give a complete introduction to the field of mathematical inverse problems and therefore we only recall the basic notation and highlight some of the difficulties. For further reading, there are a lot of references, ranging from pure mathematical texts like [EHN00] to more applied books, as for instance [Vog02] or [BB18]. Heuristically speaking, solving an inverse problem is the task of estimating an unknown quantity from given, possibly noisy measurement data. In this setting, the true image $u_{true} \in X$ has undergone some transformation $K : X \rightarrow Y$ and is usually corrupted by (additive) noise $\eta \in Y$, where X and Y denote function spaces. The whole process of corruption can then be described by the formula

$$K u_{true} + \eta = f \tag{1.2}$$

The operator $K : X \rightarrow Y$ is called *forward operator* and is in our case at least linear and continuous, often even compact, since many imaging problems involve integral operators. The aim is now, to

Figure 1.1: Clean image of a parrot, which is widely used in papers on image processing

recover the unknown image $u_{true} \in X$ from the measured incorrect data $f \in Y$. The framework above covers many existing imaging problems, e.g. image denoising, where $K = Id : L^2(\Omega) \rightarrow L^2(\Omega)$ and image deblurring, where the operator K is given by

$$K : L^2(\Omega) \rightarrow L^2(\Omega) \quad Ku(x) = \int_{\Omega} k(x, y) u(y) dy$$

with a suitable kernel $k(\cdot, \cdot) \in L^\infty(\Omega \times \Omega)$. The example of deblurring is visualized in Figure 1.3, alongside with different reconstruction methods.

Although the theoretical model that is developed in the present thesis works for general operators $K \in \mathcal{L}(X, Y)$, in the numerical tests at the end we will only focus on the inverse problem of Fourier inpainting. This problem is widely used as a model for MRI reconstruction and we refer to chapter 7 for details on this.

In general the operator equation $Ku = f$ will be *ill-posed* in the sense of Hadamard, which is exactly if one of the following three conditions is violated

1. Existence : There is an $u \in X$ such that $Ku = f$.
2. Uniqueness: The solution is unique.
3. Stability : For any sequence $(u_n)_{n \in \mathbb{N}} \subset X$ the condition $Ku_n = f_n \rightarrow f = Ku$ implies Y implies $u_n \rightarrow u$ in Y .

If ill-posedness is given, the task of inverting K is difficult and often leads to serious artifacts, when simply applying least squares approximation. This is visualized for example in Figure 1.3 for the inverse problem of deblurring.

Nevertheless, in order to deal with equations of this kind, scientists from different fields developed a variety of methods. The interested reader will find an overview over the different classical approaches in the textbook [Tar05]. Very recently the classical methods were complemented by deep learning methods that entered the field of inverse problems and immediately achieved state of the art results in many applications, [JMFU17], [AÖ17]. However a major drawback of these techniques is that there is still no way of interpreting their outcomes (black box behavior). Moreover, one can construct inputs, so called adversarial examples where these methods totally fail and introduce new artifacts which classical methods would not. This behavior makes it difficult to use deep learning in safety critical areas such as in medical imaging reconstruction tasks, cf. [LL19]. For this reason, the main focus in the present thesis is on *variational regularization methods*, where we try to estimate $u_{true} \approx S_\alpha(f)$ by solving the minimization-problem

Figure 1.2: TV denoising, illustration of the staircasing effect.

$$S_\alpha(f) \in \underset{u \in X}{\operatorname{argmin}} D(Ku, f) + R_\alpha(u) \quad (1.3)$$

for some parameter $\alpha \in \mathbb{V}$ in a normed space \mathbb{V} . In this setting $D : Y \times Y \rightarrow [0, \infty)$ denotes a suitable distance function and $R_\alpha : X \rightarrow [0, \infty]$ is a *regularization term*, penalizing some undesired behavior of the reconstruction and incorporating prior knowledge about the solution $u_{true} \in X$. The parameter $\alpha \in \mathbb{V}$ controls the trade-off between being close to the measured data $f \in Y$ and following a certain behavior enforced by the regularization term. In practice, the discrepancy term and the regularization term are motivated by statistical considerations in finite dimensions, where each pixel is modeled as

a random variable with a certain distribution. The distribution of the noise then determines, which distance $D(\cdot, \cdot)$ to choose. For additive gaussian noise it is widely accepted that $D(v, u) = \|u - v\|_{L^2(\Omega)}^2$ is the suitable choice, see [BL19] for details. For the time being we will stick to that discrepancy term, but keep in mind that also other distances are possible.

The journey of modern variational image reconstruction methods starts then at 1992 with the publication of the work [ROF92] by Rudin, Osher and Fatemi. These authors proposed a method which was able to significantly reduce noise in images, while still preserving sharp edges. The minimization problem which was solved in the latter work reads

$$\min_{u \in L^2(\Omega)} \frac{1}{2} \|Ku - f\|_{L^2(\Omega)}^2 + \alpha \int_{\Omega} d|Du| \quad (1.4)$$

where $\alpha > 0$ is a positive scalar parameter. Despite its success in image processing applications, so called *TV reconstruction* suffers from the well known *staircasing artifacts*. These artifacts emerge in areas of the reconstructed image which are not piecewise constant and lead to blocky structures in actual smooth regions of the image, see Figure 1.2.

To reduce the staircasing effect of TV regularization, the authors in [BKP10] introduced the so called *Total Generalized Variation* regularizer, which reads for order two

$$TGV_{\alpha}^2(u) = \min_{w \in BD(\Omega)} \alpha_1 \int_{\Omega} d|Du - w| + \alpha_0 \int_{\Omega} d|\mathcal{E} w| \quad (1.5)$$

Analogously, this leads to the minimization problem

$$\min_{u \in L^2(\Omega)} \frac{1}{2} \|Ku - f\|_{L^2(\Omega)}^2 + TGV_{\alpha}^2(u) \quad (1.6)$$

For rigorous definitions of the above mathematical expressions, we refer to chapter 2 and chapter 3 of this thesis. It was shown in many empirical studies that solving (1.6) also significantly removes the noise while keeping sharp edges. However instead of preferring piecewise constant images as in TV reconstruction, TGV promotes piecewise affine images, cf. also the last image in Figure 1.3. This mostly ends up in more natural reconstructions. However, this improvement is not for free - while we only had to adjust one scalar parameter for the TV reconstruction, the proper application of the TGV functional requires the correct configuration of two parameters, which can become a time consuming and difficult task. For this reason automatic parameter choice strategies are of great demand. We will focus in this thesis on so called *a priori-choice-strategies*, which means that the noise-level $\|\eta\|_Y$ is known in advance.

Very recently there has been some attempts to tackle this problem by Hintermüller et al. via the concept of bilevel optimization. The authors first developed a theoretic framework for the automatic parameter choice strategy for TV, see [HR17] and tested their results on different inverse problems in [HRWL17]. The above mentioned theoretical framework was then recently extended to TGV regularization in [HPRS20] and tested on the denoising problem. Additionally, in the preceding works, the regularization parameters are no longer considered as scalar parameters but as continuous functions. For obvious reasons, this provides a further improvement in quality. However the manual adjustment of these spatially adaptive parameters is hardly possible anymore.

The goal of this thesis is now to first develop the theory for Total Generalized Variation with spatially distributed regularization parameters as it was done briefly in [HPRS20]. From the mathematical viewpoint, the proofs are very similar to those ones in [BKP10] and [BV11], except for some simple technical details. We then introduce the bilevel optimization framework, which was originally developed in [HPRS20] to chose the spatially adaptive parameters for TGV. In chapter 3 we give a basic existence proof of that bilevel problem via the notion of Γ -convergence. As the derivation of stationary conditions for the original bilevel problem turns out to be hard, in chapter 4 we will substitute the lower level problem by a smoothed version of it, which results in an

Figure 1.3: Deblurring with different reconstruction methods. Here the blurred image was generated by convolving the clean parrot with a gaussian kernel function and adding some gaussian noise.

equivalent PDE constrained optimization problem. This PDE control problem is eventually analyzed theoretically and a rigorous derivation of an adjoint based descent algorithm is provided. In the final part of the thesis we explain how this algorithm can be discretized and solved numerically on a computer. The last chapter contains some tests on the inverse problem of Fourier inpainting.

Figure 1.4: TGV denoising. Almost no more staircasing effect.

Contribution We would like to point out briefly which parts of this thesis represent a contribution by the author and which passages can be regarded as given. First of all, to the best knowledge of the author there is as yet no self-contained treatment of TGV with spatially adaptive parameters in the literature that is also accessible to beginning graduate students. However, there are of course many works which are very close to the present one and from which many proof ideas could be adopted one to one. Here we must mention the works [BKP10], [BH14], [BV11], [BH15] and [BH19] in which the theoretical foundation for the treatment of inverse problems with scalar TGV is discussed in detail. The same is true for the description of the bilevel framework, which was originally developed in [HR17] and [HRWL17]

for spatially adaptive TV. In this part of the thesis we largely follow the treatise in [HPRS20] in which the procedure that is analysed here has already been examined for the case of image denoising. Although the structure of our work is very similar to that one in [HPRS20], in several passages we have added things and provided additional information which make the proofs more accessible to a graduate student and which are usually omitted in published papers in large journals. We have also added some proofs which, in the author's opinion, complement [HPRS20] in a useful way. In particular the proof of existence for the non-smooth bilevel problem, as well as the analysis of the differentiability properties of the solution operator in chapter 5 are to be mentioned here. Never the less, also for these parts of the thesis, there are some papers who have strongly inspired this work. Especially for the section dealing with the differentiability of the solution operator we were strongly influenced by the work in [RHM16], [RSV17] and in [RSV16].

In the numerical part we build largely on the results from [HPRS20]. Most of the parts from the implementation in the latter work, which was originally developed for the case of image denoising, could be transferred to this thesis. ¹

¹The author thanks K. Papafitsoros, who provided his Matlab implementation for the denoising case.

Chapter 2

Mathematical Preliminaries

As this is a mathematical thesis we should first gather some results that are needed for the rigorous analysis in the forthcoming chapters. However we will not explain everything from the very beginning and assume that the reader has a basic knowledge on functional analysis, integration, topology and convex programming as it is typically taught at the beginning graduate level. Many things which are written here and many more, can also be found in the textbook [BL19] or the recent overview article [BH19]. We will loosely follow those two works and cite some additional references if necessary. Since it is not possible to give a thorough introduction to every mathematical topic, which is touched here, we encourage the reader to take a look into the above mentioned works and the references therein, if something is unclear in our presentation.

2.1 Topology and Functional Analysis

As we already said, the reader is assumed to be familiar with basic functional analysis. Therefore we only explain our notation, and refer to some standard work, for instance the classical books [Rud91] by W. Rudin and [Bre10] by H. Brezis for a detailed account and rigorous proofs.

Notation. During the thesis, we will frequently use the following terminology and notation

1. For a topological space X , the closure is denoted by \overline{X} and the interior by X° or $\text{int}(X)$.
2. For two normed spaces X, Y the space of continuous linear operators, mapping from X to Y is denoted by $\mathcal{L}(X, Y)$. The usual operator norm on that space is denoted by $\|\cdot\|_{\mathcal{L}(X, Y)}$ but sometimes we will just write $\|\cdot\|_{\mathcal{L}}$ if the spaces are clear.
3. The space of compact operators between two normed spaces X, Y will be called $\mathcal{K}(X, Y)$.
4. For two normed spaces X, Y and a linear operator $K \in \mathcal{L}(X, Y)$ we denote the kernel or the nullspace of K by $\mathcal{N}(K)$, the range of K by $\mathcal{R}(K)$ and the adjoint of K by $K^* \in \mathcal{L}(Y^*, X^*)$. If X, Y are Hilbert spaces, we often identify $X^* \simeq X$ and take $K^* \in \mathcal{L}(Y, X)$.
5. The dual space of a normed space X is denoted by $X^* = \mathcal{L}(X, \mathbb{R})$. For the bidual space we write $X^{**} := (X^*)^*$. The dual brackets are defined by $\langle x^*, x \rangle_{X^*, X} = x^*(x)$ for $x^* \in X^*$ and $x \in X$. Sometimes, if the spaces are clear, we will also write $\langle x^*, x \rangle := \langle x^*, x \rangle_{X^*, X}$. If X is a Hilbert space we use the notation $\langle x, y \rangle = \langle x, y \rangle_X$ for the inner product and for the dual brackets respectively.
6. If there is a linear homeomorphism between two normed spaces X, Y we sometimes write $X \simeq Y$. For instance, if X is reflexive, we have $X \simeq X^{**}$ and if X is a Hilbert space, we know that $X^* \simeq X$ and the homeomorphisms in these cases are even isometries.

7. If a normed space X is continuously embedded into another normed space Y , we write $X \hookrightarrow Y$. If this embedding is even compact, we denote this by $X \hookrightarrow\hookrightarrow Y$.
8. For the different modes of convergence in a normed space X and its dual X^* we use the notation:

$x_n \rightarrow x$ for the strong convergence in X , i.e. $\|x_n - x\|_X \rightarrow 0$.

$x_n \rightharpoonup x$ for the weak convergence in X , i.e. $\langle x^*, x_n \rangle \rightarrow \langle x^*, x \rangle$ for every $x^* \in X^*$.

$x_n^* \overset{*}{\rightharpoonup} x^*$ for the weak* convergence in X^* , i.e. $\langle x_n^*, x \rangle \rightarrow \langle x^*, x \rangle$ for every $x \in X$.

2.2 Spaces of Functions and Measures

We will now introduce some important function spaces. For the present and the future sections, we deal with spaces of functions $u : \Omega \rightarrow X$, defined on an open, bounded Lipschitz domain $\Omega \subset \mathbb{R}^n$ and mapping into some finite dimensional Hilbert space X . Mostly we consider one of the spaces $X \in \{\mathbb{R}, \mathbb{R}^n, \mathbb{R}^{n \times n}, \mathbb{R}_{sym}^{n \times n}\}$. The inner products in these spaces are defined by

$$x \cdot y = \sum_{i=1}^n x_i y_i \quad \text{for } x, y \in \mathbb{R}^n$$

$$A \cdot B = \sum_{i,j=1}^n A_{ij} B_{ij} \quad \text{for } A, B \in \mathbb{R}^{n \times n}$$

2.2.1 Spaces of Continuous and Differentiable Functions

For fixed $k \in \mathbb{N}$ the vector spaces of differentiable functions are defined by

$$C^k(\Omega; X) := \{u : \Omega \rightarrow X \mid \partial^\alpha u \text{ exists and is continuous for every } |\alpha| \leq k\}$$

$$C^k(\overline{\Omega}; X) := \{u \in C^k(\Omega; X) \mid \partial^\alpha u \text{ admits a continuous extension on } \overline{\Omega} \text{ for every } |\alpha| \leq k\}$$

$$C_b^k(\Omega; X) := \{u \in C^k(\Omega; X) \mid \partial^\alpha u \text{ is bounded for every } |\alpha| \leq k\}$$

For $k = 0$ we set $C(\Omega; X) := C^0(\Omega; X)$, $C(\overline{\Omega}; X) := C^0(\overline{\Omega}; X)$ and $C_b(\Omega; X) := C_b^0(\Omega; X)$ respectively. The space of continuous functions with compact support in Ω and values in X is denoted by $C_c(\Omega; X)$. Further we define

$$C_c^k(\Omega; X) := C^k(\Omega; X) \cap C_c(\Omega; X)$$

and introduce the spaces of infinitely-times differentiable functions:

$$C^\infty(\Omega; X) := \bigcap_{k \in \mathbb{N}} C^k(\Omega; X) \quad C^\infty(\overline{\Omega}; X) := \bigcap_{k \in \mathbb{N}} C^k(\overline{\Omega}; X) \quad C_c^\infty(\Omega; X) := \bigcap_{k \in \mathbb{N}} C_c^k(\Omega; X)$$

In order to define norms on these spaces we consider the functions

$$\|\cdot\|_{C^k(\Omega; X)} : C_b^k(\Omega; X) \rightarrow [0, \infty), \quad \|u\|_{C^k(\Omega; X)} := \max_{|\alpha| \leq k} \|\partial^\alpha u\|_{C(\Omega; X)}$$

where $\|\cdot\|_{C(\Omega; X)}$ denotes the usual maximum norm on $C_b(\Omega; X)$. One can show, that the spaces $(C_b^k(\Omega; X), \|\cdot\|_{C^k(\Omega; X)})$ and $(C^k(\overline{\Omega}; X), \|\cdot\|_{C^k(\Omega; X)})$ are Banach spaces for every $k \in \mathbb{N}$.

The spaces $(C_c^k(\Omega; X), \|\cdot\|_{C^k(\Omega; X)})$ are not complete, but its closure

$$C_0^k(\Omega; X) := \overline{C_c^k(\Omega; X)}^{\|\cdot\|_{C^k(\Omega; X)}} \quad (2.1)$$

in $C_b^k(\Omega; X)$ is again a Banach space.

2.2.2 Spaces of Integrable Functions

For a σ -finite measure space $(\Omega, \mathcal{A}, \mu)$ and again a finite dimensional Hilbert space X , the term

$$\int_{\Omega} (\cdot) \, d\mu : \{f : \Omega \rightarrow X \mid f \text{ is } \mathcal{A} \text{ measurable}\} \rightarrow X \quad f \mapsto \int_{\Omega} f \, d\mu$$

always denotes the integral in the sense of Bochner. For a thorough treatise of this subject and the measure theoretic foundations, we refer to the excellent books by Rao [Rao04] and Yosida [Yos13]. The Bochner integral coincides with the Lebesgue integral, if $X = \mathbb{R}$ and one can show, that if $X = \mathbb{R}^n$ or $X = \mathbb{R}^{n \times n}$ the integral can be evaluated component wise. For instance if $X = \mathbb{R}^{n \times n}$ we obtain

$$\left(\int_{\Omega} f \, d\mu \right)_{ij} = \int_{\Omega} (f(x))_{ij} \, d\mu \quad \text{for every } 1 \leq i, j \leq n.$$

and the right hand side of the above equation can again be interpreted in the sense of Lebesgue. We then define the spaces of (equivalence classes of) integrable functions by

$$\begin{aligned} L^p(\mu, \Omega; X) &:= \left\{ f : \Omega \rightarrow X \mid f \text{ is } \mathcal{A} \text{ measurable and } \int_{\Omega} \|f\|_X^p \, d\mu < \infty \right\} \\ L^\infty(\mu, \Omega; X) &:= \left\{ f : \Omega \rightarrow X \mid f \text{ is } \mathcal{A} \text{ measurable and } \text{esssup}(f) < \infty \right\} \end{aligned}$$

where we set

$$\text{esssup}(f) := \inf \left\{ \sup_{x \in \Omega} \|g(x)\|_X \mid g(x) = f(x) \text{ for } \mu\text{-almost every } x \in \Omega. \right\}$$

On these spaces, we introduce the norms

$$\begin{aligned} \|\cdot\|_{L^p(\mu, \Omega; X)} : L^p(\mu, \Omega; X) &\rightarrow \mathbb{R} & \|f\|_{L^p(\mu, \Omega; X)}^p &:= \int_{\Omega} \|f\|_X^p \, d\mu \\ \|\cdot\|_{L^\infty(\mu, \Omega; X)} : L^\infty(\mu, \Omega; X) &\rightarrow \mathbb{R} & \|f\|_{L^\infty(\mu, \Omega; X)} &:= \text{esssup}(f) \end{aligned}$$

One can show, that the above defined spaces are Banach spaces for $p \in [1, \infty]$. They are even reflexive, if $p \in (1, \infty)$ but non reflexive for $p \in \{1, \infty\}$.

For the case where $p = 2$ we obtain the Hilbert space $L^2(\mu, \Omega; X)$, endowed with the inner product

$$\langle f, g \rangle_{L^2(\mu, \Omega; X)} := \int_{\Omega} f \cdot g \, d\mu$$

Moreover, if $(\Omega, \mathcal{A}, \mu) = (\Omega, \overline{\mathcal{B}(\Omega)}, \mathcal{L}^n)$, i.e. if $\mu : \overline{\mathcal{B}(\Omega)} \rightarrow [0, \infty]$ is the Lebesgue measure \mathcal{L}^n on the measure theoretic completion $\overline{\mathcal{B}(\Omega)}$ with respect to \mathcal{L}^n , we simply set

$$L^p(\Omega; X) := L^p(\mu, \Omega; X)$$

Note, that in the lines above, we were a little vague, as of course the space $L^p(\mu, \Omega; X)$ consists in fact of equivalence classes

$$[f] := \{g : \Omega \rightarrow X \mid g \text{ is } \mathcal{A} \text{ measurable and } f(x) = g(x) \text{ for almost every } x \in \Omega\}$$

and the integral, as well as the norms defined above do not depend on the specific choice of one of the elements in the respective equivalence class. Therefore it is okay to write $f \in L^p(\mu, \Omega; X)$ instead of $[f] \in L^p(\mu, \Omega; X)$. However, the latter would be more precise. For a rigorous exposition of the construction of the integral and all the subtle, technical details we again refer to [Rao04].

2.2.3 Spaces of Distributions

Since the usual definition of differentiability is too restrictive in many cases, the concept of distributions has developed over the past century. As the subject is quite extensive, we only introduce the notation, explain some concepts and refer to [Bre10] for more information. We follow here the lines in [BMA06]. Due to historical reasons, we define the space of test functions as

$$\mathcal{D}(\Omega; X) := C_c^\infty(\Omega; X)$$

for $X = \mathbb{R}$, write $\mathcal{D}(\Omega) := \mathcal{D}(\Omega; \mathbb{R})$. We then come to the definition

Definition 1 (Distributions). *A (vector valued) distribution $T \in \mathcal{D}'(\Omega; X)$ is a linear mapping $T : \mathcal{D}(\Omega; X) \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ such that the following holds true:*

For every compact $K \subset \Omega$, there is a $k \in \mathbb{N}$ and a $C = C(K) \geq 0$, such that for every $v \in \mathcal{D}(\Omega; X)$ with $\text{supp}(v) \subset K$ it holds $|T(v)| \leq C \|v\|_{C^k(\Omega; X)}$

As for the dual spaces we usually write

$$\langle T, v \rangle_{\mathcal{D}', \mathcal{D}} := T(v) \quad \text{for } T \in \mathcal{D}'(\Omega)$$

We then directly infer from the definition that $f \in L^1(\Omega; X)$ and also $y^* \in C_b^k(\Omega; X)^*$ induce distributions $T_f, T_{y^*} \in \mathcal{D}'(\Omega; X)$ via

$$\langle T_f, v \rangle_{\mathcal{D}', \mathcal{D}} := \int_{\Omega} f v \, dx \quad \text{and} \quad \langle T_{y^*}, v \rangle_{\mathcal{D}', \mathcal{D}} := \langle y^*, v \rangle_{C_b^k(\Omega)^*, C_b^k(\Omega)}$$

for $v \in \mathcal{D}(\Omega; X)$. Therefore it makes sense for a distribution $u \in \mathcal{D}'(\Omega; X)$ to write $u \in L^1(\Omega; X)$ and $u \in C_b^k(\Omega; X)^*$ respectively, if there is an element $f \in L^1(\Omega)$ or an $y^* \in C_b^k(\Omega)^*$ with $T_f = u$ or $T_{y^*} = u$. We will use that notation frequently during the following chapters.

Definition 2 (Derivative of a distribution). *If $u \in \mathcal{D}'(\Omega; X)$, then we define its distributional derivative $\partial^\alpha u \in \mathcal{D}'(\Omega; X)$ via*

$$\langle \partial^\alpha u, v \rangle_{\mathcal{D}', \mathcal{D}} := (-1)^{|\alpha|} \langle u, \partial^\alpha v \rangle_{\mathcal{D}', \mathcal{D}} \quad \text{for } v \in \mathcal{D}(\Omega; X)$$

In the same spirit we define the following distributional differential operators

$$\text{div} : \mathcal{D}'(\Omega; \mathbb{R}^n) \rightarrow \mathcal{D}'(\Omega; \mathbb{R}) \quad \langle \text{div } u, v \rangle_{\mathcal{D}', \mathcal{D}} := - \langle u, D v \rangle_{\mathcal{D}', \mathcal{D}} \quad \text{for } v \in C_c^\infty(\Omega)$$

$$\text{div} : \mathcal{D}'(\Omega; \mathbb{R}^{n \times n}) \rightarrow \mathcal{D}'(\Omega; \mathbb{R}^n) \quad \langle \text{div } u, v \rangle_{\mathcal{D}', \mathcal{D}} := - \langle u, D v \rangle_{\mathcal{D}', \mathcal{D}} \quad \text{for } v \in C_c^\infty(\Omega, \mathbb{R}^n)$$

$$\mathcal{E} : \mathcal{D}'(\Omega; \mathbb{R}^n) \rightarrow \mathcal{D}'(\Omega; \mathbb{R}^{n \times n}_{sym}) \quad \langle \mathcal{E} u, v \rangle_{\mathcal{D}', \mathcal{D}} := - \langle u, \text{div } v \rangle_{\mathcal{D}', \mathcal{D}} \quad \text{for } v \in C_c^\infty(\Omega; \mathbb{R}^{n \times n}_{sym})$$

$$D : \mathcal{D}'(\Omega) \rightarrow \mathcal{D}'(\Omega; \mathbb{R}^n) \quad \langle D u, v \rangle_{\mathcal{D}', \mathcal{D}} := - \langle u, \text{div } v \rangle_{\mathcal{D}', \mathcal{D}} \quad \text{for } v \in C_c^\infty(\Omega; \mathbb{R}^n)$$

where the div-operator for continuously differentiable functions is given by

$$\begin{aligned} \text{div } u &= \sum_{i=1}^n \partial^i u_i(x) \quad \text{for } u \in C^1(\Omega; \mathbb{R}^n) \\ (\text{div } u)_i &= \sum_{j=1}^n \partial^j u_{ij}(x) \quad \text{for } u \in C^1(\Omega; \mathbb{R}^{n \times n}) \end{aligned}$$

Moreover if $u \in C^1(\Omega; \mathbb{R}^n)$, then $\mathcal{E} u \in C(\Omega; \mathbb{R}^{n \times n}_{sym})$ and it holds

$$(\mathcal{E} u)_{ij} = \frac{\partial^i u_j + \partial^j u_i}{2}$$

2.2.4 Spaces of Functions whose Derivatives are Integrable

We now briefly define Sobolev spaces with values in \mathbb{R}^m for $m \in \mathbb{N}$ and some related concepts. For a rigorous treatment of Sobolev spaces, the reader may consult [BMA06] and [AF03]. For a detailed account on $LD(\Omega)$, we refer to [TO18]. We first define the Sobolev spaces for the exponent $p \in [1, +\infty]$

$$W^{1,p}(\Omega; \mathbb{R}^m) := \left\{ f \in L^p(\Omega; \mathbb{R}^m) \mid \partial^i f_j \in L^p(\Omega) \text{ for every } 1 \leq i \leq n \text{ and } 1 \leq j \leq m. \right\}$$

alongside the much less known space

$$LD(\Omega) := \left\{ f \in L^1(\Omega; \mathbb{R}^n) \mid \mathcal{E}f \in L^1(\Omega; \mathbb{R}^{n \times n}_{sym}) \right\}$$

The spaces are equipped with norms, defined by

$$\begin{aligned} \|f\|_{W^{1,p}(\Omega; \mathbb{R}^m)}^p &:= \|f\|_{L^p(\Omega; \mathbb{R}^m)}^p + \|Df\|_{L^p(\Omega; \mathbb{R}^{m \times n})}^p \\ \|f\|_{LD(\Omega)} &:= \|f\|_{L^1(\Omega; \mathbb{R}^n)} + \|\mathcal{E}f\|_{L^1(\Omega; \mathbb{R}^{n \times n})} \end{aligned}$$

We then have the following properties

Theorem 1 (Properties of $W^{1,p}(\Omega; \mathbb{R}^m)$ and $LD(\Omega)$). *Consider the spaces $W^{1,p}(\Omega; \mathbb{R}^m)$ and $LD(\Omega)$ as defined above, then the following statements hold true:*

1. $W^{1,p}(\Omega; \mathbb{R}^m)$ and $LD(\Omega)$ are always Banach spaces.
2. For $1 < p < \infty$, the space $W^{1,p}(\Omega; \mathbb{R}^m)$ is reflexive.
3. The space $C_c^\infty(\overline{\Omega}; \mathbb{R}^m)$ is dense in $W^{1,p}(\Omega; \mathbb{R}^m)$.
4. The space $C_c^\infty(\overline{\Omega}; \mathbb{R}^n)$ is dense in $LD(\Omega)$.
5. We have the following embeddings for $p^* := pn/(p-n)$.

$$\begin{aligned} \text{If } 1 \leq p < n: \quad & W^{1,p}(\Omega; \mathbb{R}^m) \hookrightarrow L^q(\Omega; \mathbb{R}^m) \quad \text{For every } 1 \leq q \leq p^* \\ & W^{1,p}(\Omega; \mathbb{R}^m) \hookrightarrow\hookrightarrow L^q(\Omega; \mathbb{R}^m) \quad \text{For every } 1 \leq q < p^* \end{aligned}$$

$$\text{If } p = n: \quad W^{1,p}(\Omega; \mathbb{R}^m) \hookrightarrow\hookrightarrow L^q(\Omega; \mathbb{R}^m) \quad \text{For every } 1 \leq q < \infty$$

$$\text{If } p > n: \quad W^{1,p}(\Omega; \mathbb{R}^m) \hookrightarrow\hookrightarrow C(\overline{\Omega}; \mathbb{R}^m)$$

2.2.5 Basic Theory on Finite Radon Measures

We will now introduce the notion of vector measures, which we will need in the following subsection for the definition of the spaces $BV(\Omega)$ and $BD(\Omega)$. Classical references in the field are [AFP00], [Rud91] and [Fed14], where all statements, which are presented here and much more can be found. We follow again loosely the recent textbook of [BL19] by K. Bredies, which provides a nice and short overview on the topic.

Definition 3. (Finite vector valued Radon measure) *A function $\mu : \mathcal{B}(\Omega) \rightarrow X$ is called a finite Radon measure with values in X , if*

1. $\mu(\emptyset) = 0$ and
2. For pairwise disjoint sets $\{A_n\}_{n \in \mathbb{N}} \subset \mathcal{B}(\Omega)$ and $A := \bigcup_{n \in \mathbb{N}} A_n$ it holds $\sum_{n \in \mathbb{N}} \mu(A_n) = \mu(A)$

The vector space of finite Radon measures with values in X is denoted by $\mathcal{M}(\Omega; X)$. If $X = \mathbb{R}$, we obtain the space $\mathcal{M}(\Omega) := \mathcal{M}(\Omega; X)$ of signed measures.

Each finite vector valued Radon measure $\mu \in \mathcal{M}(\Omega; X)$ can be assigned a positive, finite measure $|\mu| : \mathcal{B}(\Omega) \rightarrow [0, \infty)$, namely the so called total variation measure, which is defined as follows:

Definition 4 (Total variation measure). *Let $\mu \in \mathcal{M}(\Omega; X)$ be a finite vector valued Radon measure. The total variation measure $|\mu| : \mathcal{B}(\Omega) \rightarrow \mathbb{R} \cup \{+\infty\}$ is defined by*

$$|\mu|(A) := \sup \left\{ \sum_{n \in \mathbb{N}} \|\mu(A_n)\|_X \mid A \subset \bigcup_{n \in \mathbb{N}} A_n \text{ and } A_n \in \mathcal{B}(\Omega) \text{ pairwise disjoint.} \right\}$$

With the help of the next theorem, we can then introduce a norm on the space $\mathcal{M}(\Omega; X)$:

Theorem 2. *Let $\mu \in \mathcal{M}(\Omega; X)$, then the function $|\mu| : \mathcal{B}(\Omega) \rightarrow \mathbb{R} \cup \{+\infty\}$ is actually a finite, positive measure. Setting*

$$\|\mu\|_{\mathcal{M}(\Omega; X)} := |\mu|(\Omega)$$

the space $(\mathcal{M}(\Omega; X), \|\cdot\|_{\mathcal{M}(\Omega; X)})$ becomes a Banach space.

An important tool is the so called polar decomposition:

Theorem 3. (Polar decomposition) *Let $\mu \in \mathcal{M}(\Omega; X)$, then there is a unique function $\sigma_\mu \in L^\infty(|\mu|; \Omega; X)$, such that $\|\sigma_\mu(x)\|_X = 1$ for $|\mu|$ -almost every $x \in \Omega$ and with*

$$\mu(A) = \int_A \sigma_\mu(x) d|\mu| \quad \text{for every } A \in \mathcal{B}(\Omega).$$

More generally, given a function $f \in L^1(\lambda; \Omega; X)$ and a positive finite measure $\lambda : \mathcal{B}(\Omega) \rightarrow [0, \infty)$, we can construct finite Radon measure with values in X by

$$\lambda_f : \mathcal{B}(\Omega) \rightarrow X \quad \lambda_f(A) := \int_A f(x) d\lambda$$

And it is possible, to calculate its total variation by the following theorem

Theorem 4. *Let $\lambda : \mathcal{B}(\Omega) \rightarrow [0, \infty)$ a positive finite measure and $f \in L^1(\lambda; \Omega; X)$. Then $\lambda_f \in \mathcal{M}(\Omega; X)$ and the following equation holds true:*

$$|\lambda_f|(A) = \int_A \|f(x)\|_X d\lambda$$

Consequently, we obtain $\|\lambda_f\|_{\mathcal{M}(\Omega; X)} = \|f\|_{L^1(\lambda; \Omega; X)}$. Therefore $L^1(\lambda; \Omega; X) \hookrightarrow \mathcal{M}(\Omega; X)$ isometrically. That is why we often simply write $f \in \mathcal{M}(\Omega; X)$ instead of $\lambda_f \in \mathcal{M}(\Omega; X)$.

For a measure $\mu \in \mathcal{M}(\Omega; X)$ and a function $f \in L^1(|\mu|; \Omega; X)$ also an integral can be defined via the polar decomposition $(\sigma_\mu, |\mu|)$ of the measure $\mu \in \mathcal{M}(\Omega; X)$:

$$\int_\Omega f d\mu := \int_\Omega f(x) \cdot \sigma_\mu(x) d|\mu|$$

The following theorem eventually reveals an important link between the theory of measures and functional analysis.

Theorem 5. (Riesz) *For every $F \in C_0(\Omega; X)^*$ there is exactly one element $\mu_F \in \mathcal{M}(\Omega; X)$, such that*

$$\langle F, f \rangle_{C_0(\Omega; X)^*} = \int_\Omega f d\mu_F$$

Moreover it holds $\|F\|_{C_0(\Omega; X)^} = \|\mu_F\|_{\mathcal{M}(\Omega; X)}$.*

Hence, $C_0(\Omega; X)^* \simeq \mathcal{M}(\Omega; X)$ isometrically and we may also write $\langle \mu, f \rangle_{C_0(\Omega; X)^*}$ for measures $\mu \in \mathcal{M}(\Omega; X)$. The Riesz representation theorem also motivates the following definition, which is of importance, when it comes to regularization with spatially distributed parameters: For a function $\alpha \in C_b(\Omega)$ and a measure $\mu \in \mathcal{M}(\Omega; X)$ we set

$$\langle \alpha \cdot \mu, f \rangle_{C_0(\Omega; X)^*} := \langle \mu, \alpha f \rangle_{C_0(\Omega; X)^*} = \int_{\Omega} \alpha f \, d\mu$$

and as a straightforward consequence of the foregoing discussion one can show

Theorem 6. *Let $\alpha \in C_b(\Omega)$ and $\mu \in \mathcal{M}(\Omega; X)$. Then $\alpha \cdot \mu$ defined as above is an element of $\mathcal{M}(\Omega; X)$ and it holds*

$$\|\alpha \cdot \mu\|_{\mathcal{M}(\Omega; X)} = \int_{\Omega} |\alpha(x)| \, d|\mu|$$

The last theorem will be frequently used in the forthcoming sections without explicitly mentioning. As we have characterized the space $\mathcal{M}(\Omega; X)$ as a dual space of continuous functions, it makes sense to define a weak star convergence in that space.

Definition 5 (Weak* convergence). *A sequence $(\mu_n)_{n \in \mathbb{N}} \subset \mathcal{M}(\Omega; X)$ is said to converge weak* to an element $\mu \in \mathcal{M}(\Omega; X)$ if and only if*

$$\langle \mu_n, f \rangle_{C_0(\Omega; X)^*} \rightarrow \langle \mu, f \rangle_{C_0(\Omega; X)^*} \quad \text{for every } f \in C_0(\Omega; X)$$

If the last line holds true, we usually write

$$\mu_n \xrightarrow{*} \mu \quad \text{in } \mathcal{M}(\Omega; X)$$

2.2.6 Spaces of Functions whose Derivatives are Measures

Now we introduce the spaces, in which clean images are typically assumed to exist. Again we refer to the classical references [BMA06], [AFP00] and the modern treatment in [BH19], where the proofs of our assertions and much more material can be found. We directly introduce the main objects, namely the spaces

$$\begin{aligned} BV(\Omega) &:= \{ u \in L^1(\Omega) \mid Du \in \mathcal{M}(\Omega; \mathbb{R}^n) \} \\ BD(\Omega) &:= \{ w \in L^1(\Omega; \mathbb{R}^n) \mid \mathcal{E}w \in \mathcal{M}(\Omega; \mathbb{R}_{sym}^{n \times n}) \} \end{aligned}$$

which can be turned into a normed space via the norms

$$\begin{aligned} \|u\|_{BV(\Omega)} &:= \|u\|_{L^1(\Omega)} + \|Du\|_{\mathcal{M}(\Omega; \mathbb{R}^n)} \\ \|w\|_{BD(\Omega)} &:= \|w\|_{L^1(\Omega; \mathbb{R}^n)} + \|\mathcal{E}w\|_{\mathcal{M}(\Omega; \mathbb{R}_{sym}^{n \times n})} \end{aligned}$$

Then it is possible to verify following properties

Theorem 7 (Properties of BV and BD). *For the spaces $BV(\Omega)$ and $BD(\Omega)$ the following properties hold true:*

1. *The spaces $BV(\Omega)$ and $BD(\Omega)$ are Banach spaces, which are not reflexive.*
2. *If $u \in \mathcal{D}'(\Omega)$ and $Du \in \mathcal{M}(\Omega; \mathbb{R}^n)$, then it has to hold $u \in BV(\Omega)$.*
3. *If $w \in \mathcal{D}'(\Omega, \mathbb{R}^n)$ and $\mathcal{E}w \in \mathcal{M}(\Omega; \mathbb{R}_{sym}^{n \times n})$, then it has to hold $w \in BD(\Omega)$.*
4. *For every $u \in BV(\Omega)$ there is a sequence $(u_k)_k \subset BV(\Omega) \cap C^\infty(\Omega)$ such that*

$$\|u_k - u\|_{L^1(\Omega)} \rightarrow 0 \quad \text{and} \quad \|Du_k\|_{\mathcal{M}(\Omega; \mathbb{R}^n)} \rightarrow \|Du\|_{\mathcal{M}(\Omega; \mathbb{R}^n)}$$

5. For every $w \in BD(\Omega)$ there is a sequence $(w_k)_k \subset BD(\Omega) \cap C^\infty(\Omega; \mathbb{R}^n)$ such that

$$\|w_k - w\|_{L^1(\Omega; \mathbb{R}^n)} \rightarrow 0 \quad \text{and} \quad \|\mathcal{E}w_k\|_{\mathcal{M}(\Omega; \mathbb{R}_{sym}^{n \times n})} \rightarrow \|\mathcal{E}w\|_{\mathcal{M}(\Omega; \mathbb{R}_{sym}^{n \times n})}$$

6. Moreover we have the following embeddings

$$\begin{aligned} BV(\Omega) &\hookrightarrow L^q(\Omega) && \text{for } 1 \leq q \leq n/(n-1) \\ BV(\Omega) &\hookrightarrow\hookrightarrow L^q(\Omega) && \text{for } 1 \leq q < n/(n-1) \\ \\ BD(\Omega) &\hookrightarrow L^q(\Omega; \mathbb{R}^n) && \text{for } 1 \leq q \leq n/(n-1) \\ BD(\Omega) &\hookrightarrow\hookrightarrow L^q(\Omega; \mathbb{R}^n) && \text{for } 1 \leq q < n/(n-1) \end{aligned}$$

In addition, we need some sort of sequential compactness in these spaces. Therefore define:

Definition 6 (Modes of convergence).

1. We say, that a sequence $(u_n)_n$ converges *weak** to $u \in BV(\Omega)$, denoted by $u_n \xrightarrow{*} u$, if the following limits hold

$$u_n \rightarrow u \quad \text{in } L^1(\Omega) \quad Du_n \xrightarrow{*} Du \quad \text{in } \mathcal{M}(\Omega; \mathbb{R}^n)$$

2. Similarly, a sequence $(w_n)_n$ converges *weak** to $w \in BD(\Omega)$, denoted by $w_n \xrightarrow{*} w$, if

$$w_n \rightarrow w \quad \text{in } L^1(\Omega; \mathbb{R}^n) \quad \mathcal{E}w_n \xrightarrow{*} \mathcal{E}w \quad \text{in } \mathcal{M}(\Omega; \mathbb{R}_{sym}^{n \times n})$$

We eventually have the following compactness results:

Theorem 8 (Compactness in $BV(\Omega)$). Let $(u_n)_n \subset BV(\Omega)$ be bounded with respect to the norm of $BV(\Omega)$. Then there is a subsequence (denoted the same) and an element $u \in BV(\Omega)$, such that

$$u_n \xrightarrow{*} u \quad \text{in } BV(\Omega)$$

Theorem 9 (Compactness in $BD(\Omega)$). Let $(w_n)_n \subset BD(\Omega)$ be bounded with respect to the norm of $BD(\Omega)$. Then there is a subsequence (denoted the same) and an element $w \in BD(\Omega)$, such that

$$w_n \xrightarrow{*} w \quad \text{in } BD(\Omega)$$

2.3 Convex Analysis

As most image reconstruction problems are convex, we need several tools from the field of convex analysis and the related concept of monotone operators. Again the reader is assumed to be familiar with the foundations and is able to consult the classical references [ET99], [BMA06] and [BC11]. For an extensive account on monotone operators, we recommend to consult [ZB89].

Throughout this section we denote by $\overline{\mathbb{R}} := \mathbb{R} \cup \{+\infty\}$ the extended real line and for a function $F : X \rightarrow \overline{\mathbb{R}}$ we set

$$Dom(F) := \{x \in X \mid F(x) < \infty\}$$

which is called *the domain* of the function F . A mapping F is then called proper, if $Dom(F) \neq \emptyset$. A useful example of a convex function is the *indicator function* of a convex set $C \subset X$ defined by

$$\mathcal{I}_C(x) := \begin{cases} 0 & \text{if } x \in C \\ +\infty & \text{if } x \notin C \end{cases}$$

Note that this definition is fundamentally different from that one, which is usually used in stochastics and which is defined as

$$\mathbf{1}_A(x) := \begin{cases} 1 & \text{if } x \in A \\ 0 & \text{if } x \notin A \end{cases}$$

For an arbitrary set $A \subset X$. The next theorem shows some nice continuity properties of convex functions.

Theorem 10 (Continuity of convex functions). *Let $F : X \rightarrow \overline{\mathbb{R}}$ be a proper, convex function. Then*

1. $F(\cdot)$ is continuous at $x_0 \in X$ if and only if $F(\cdot)$ is bounded in a neighborhood of x_0 .
2. If $F : X \rightarrow \overline{\mathbb{R}}$ is lower semicontinuous and X is a Banach space, then $F(\cdot)$ is continuous on $\text{int}(\text{Dom}(F))$.

Especially for the argumentation in chapter 4, we will need the so called Fenchel conjugate of a convex function.

Definition 7 (Fenchel conjugate). *Let $F : X \rightarrow \overline{\mathbb{R}}$ be proper. Then we define the Fenchel conjugate F^* and the biconjugate F^{**} via*

$$\begin{aligned} F^* : X^* \rightarrow \overline{\mathbb{R}} & \quad F^*(x^*) := \sup_{x \in X} \langle x^*, x \rangle_{X^*, X} - F(x) \\ F^{**} : X \rightarrow \overline{\mathbb{R}} & \quad F^{**}(x) := \sup_{x^* \in X^*} \langle x^*, x \rangle_{X^*, X} - F^*(x^*) \end{aligned}$$

If X is reflexive, then we have $F^{**} = (F^*)^*$. Moreover, one can show

Theorem 11 (Biconjugate). *Let $F : X \rightarrow \overline{\mathbb{R}}$ be proper and convex. Then it holds*

$$F : X \rightarrow \overline{\mathbb{R}} \text{ is lower semicontinuous if and only if } F^{**}(x) = F(x) \text{ for every } x \in X.$$

In order to treat also non differentiable functions we introduce the **subdifferential** of a convex and proper function as the set valued operator

$$\partial F : X \rightarrow \mathcal{P}(X^*) \quad \partial F(x) := \begin{cases} \{x^* \in X^* \mid F(x) + \langle x^*, y - x \rangle_{X^*, X} \leq F(y) \quad \forall y \in X\} & \text{for } x \in \text{Dom}(F) \\ \emptyset & \text{else} \end{cases}$$

for which we have the following properties

Theorem 12 (Properties of the subdifferential). *Let X, Y Banach spaces and let $F : X \rightarrow \overline{\mathbb{R}}$ be a proper and convex function. Then it holds*

1. If $F(\cdot)$ is continuous at $x_0 \in X$, then $\partial F(x_0)$ is non-empty, bounded and weak* closed.
2. If $F(\cdot)$ is Gateaux differentiable at $x_0 \in X$, then $\partial F(x_0) = \{\nabla F(x_0)\}$.
3. Vice versa, if $F(\cdot)$ is continuous at $x_0 \in X$ and $\partial F(x_0) = \{x^*\}$. Then $F(\cdot)$ is Gateaux differentiable at $x_0 \in X$ and $\nabla F(x_0) = x^*$.
4. Let $\Lambda \in \mathcal{L}(X, Y)$ and $F : Y \rightarrow \overline{\mathbb{R}}$ be proper, convex and lower semicontinuous on Y . Moreover let $F(\cdot)$ be continuous at one point $y_0 \in \mathcal{R}(\Lambda)$. Then it holds $\partial F \circ \Lambda(x) = \Lambda^* \partial F(\Lambda x)$ for every $x \in X$.
5. Let $F, G : X \rightarrow \overline{\mathbb{R}}$ convex, proper and lower semicontinuous. Moreover assume that there is a point $x_0 \in \text{Dom}(G)$, such that $F(\cdot)$ is continuous at $x_0 \in X$. Then the following equation is valid for every $x \in X$

$$\partial(F + G)(x) = \partial F(x) + G(x)$$

6. In addition, we have the first order characterization of minima:

$$0 \in \partial F(x_0) \text{ if and only if } x_0 \in \operatorname{argmin}_{x \in X} F(x)$$

7. A nice link between Fenchel conjugates and subdifferentials is given by:

$$x^* \in \partial F(x) \text{ if and only if } F(x) + F^*(x^*) = \langle x^*, x \rangle_{X^*, X}$$

In the subsequent part of the thesis we will mostly deal with problems of a specific kind. For two normed spaces X, Y and functions $F : X \rightarrow \overline{\mathbb{R}}, G : Y \rightarrow \overline{\mathbb{R}}$ and a linear operator $\Lambda \in \mathcal{L}(X, Y)$ we will consider

$$\inf_{x \in X} F(x) + G(\Lambda x) \quad (P_{\text{primal}})$$

and introduce the so called dual problem of (P_{primal})

$$\sup_{y^* \in Y^*} -F^*(-\Lambda^* y^*) - G^*(y^*) \quad (P_{\text{dual}})$$

The definition of the Fenchel conjugates directly leads to the inequality

$$\inf_{x \in X} F(x) + G(\Lambda x) \geq \sup_{y^* \in Y^*} -F^*(-\Lambda^* y^*) - G^*(y^*)$$

Now it is natural to ask, under which conditions there is equality and if there is a solution of (P_{dual}) . For that purpose, we introduce the so called Slater condition

$$\text{There is a } x_0 \in \operatorname{Dom}(F) \text{ such that } \Lambda x_0 \in \operatorname{Dom}(G) \text{ and } G(\cdot) \text{ is continuous at } \Lambda x_0. \quad (\text{Slater})$$

and obtain the following theorem

Theorem 13. *Let X, Y be Banach spaces and $\Lambda \in \mathcal{L}(X, Y)$ a linear continuous operator. Moreover let $F : X \rightarrow \overline{\mathbb{R}}, G : Y \rightarrow \overline{\mathbb{R}}$ denote proper, lower semicontinuous and convex functions, such that (Slater) holds true. If moreover*

$$\inf_{x \in X} F(x) + G(\Lambda x) > -\infty$$

then the dual problem (P_{dual}) has a solution, and there is no duality gap, i.e. we have

$$\inf_{x \in X} F(x) + G(\Lambda x) = \max_{y^* \in Y^*} -F^*(-\Lambda^* y^*) - G^*(y^*)$$

Proof. For a proof, consult [BMA06], theorem 9.8.1 and 9.7.2. □

In order to investigate existence of certain minimization problems and nonlinear operator equations, we briefly introduce the notion of monotone operators

Definition 8 (Monotone operators). *An operator $A : X \rightarrow X^*$ on a Banach space X is called*

1. *monotone, if $\langle Ax - Ay, x - y \rangle_{X^*, X} \geq 0$ for every $x, y \in X$.*
2. *strictly monotone, if $\langle Ax - Ay, x - y \rangle_{X^*, X} > 0$ for every $x, y \in X$.*
3. *(κ) -strongly monotone, if $\langle Ax - Ay, x - y \rangle_{X^*, X} \geq \kappa \|x - y\|^2$ for every $x, y \in X$.*

Together with monotonicity, the different notions of coercivity are of importance :

Definition 9 (Coercivity).

1. *A function $F : X \rightarrow \overline{\mathbb{R}}$ is called coercive, if $\|x\|_X \rightarrow \infty$ implies $F(x) \rightarrow \infty$.*

2. An operator $A : X \rightarrow X^*$ is called *coercive*, if $\|x\|_X \rightarrow \infty$ implies $\langle Ax, x \rangle_{X^*, X} / \|x\|_X \rightarrow \infty$

Moreover we have the following important theorem, see [ZB89].

Theorem 14 (Browder, Minty). *Let X be a Banach space and $A : X \rightarrow X^*$ a monotone, continuous and coercive operator, then the operator equation*

$$Ax = b$$

has a solution for every $b \in X^$. If A is even strictly monotone, then the solution is unique.*

As a consequence one can immediately show

Theorem 15 (Lax Milgram). *Let X be a Hilbert space and $A : X \rightarrow X^*$ be a continuous, linear and strongly monotone operator, then*

$$Ax = b$$

has a unique solution for every $b \in X^$. Moreover, the linear inverse operator $A^{-1} : X^* \rightarrow X$ is continuous.*

Chapter 3

Total Generalized Variation with Spatially Varying Parameters

In the subsequent chapter we will give a self contained introduction to the Total Generalized Variation (TGV) regularizer, which was proposed in 2009 by Bredies, Kunisch and Pock in order to reduce the staircasing artifacts obtained by TV-Regularization, while still preserving sharp edges. This is achieved by involving higher order differential operators in the regularization process. In their celebrated paper, the authors develop the theory for TGV of arbitrary order. For reasons of simplicity and legibility we'll only consider second order TGV in this thesis. In addition, in most practical applications only second order TGV is used, as the improvements, resulting from going to third or even higher order TGV are hardly perceptible to the human eye. However we emphasize the fact that the theory given here, can be expanded to higher orders as well. In contrast to the original work [BKP10], we go one step further and allow the regularization parameters not only to be positive constants, but positive functions in $C(\overline{\Omega})$, uniformly bounded away from zero. The purpose of this extension is to better adapt to the different regions in the image, as illustrated for instance in the recent publication [HPRS20]. Our investigation starts in the first section with the basic functional analytic properties, which are then used in the second section to prove a minimum characterization of the TGV regularizer. This characterization enables a better understanding of the underlying regularization process and also marks the starting point for the study of a smoothed TGV functional in chapter 4 and 5. In the last section we use this regularizer as a penalty term in a least squares reconstruction problem and prove existence under rather weak assumptions.

From a theoretical perspective the proofs are mostly the same as in the original papers [BKP10], [BV11] and [BH14], but for the sake of completeness we write them down here properly. However, whenever it is possible, we will make a shortcut to the original papers and use the statements from there in order not to proof everything again. To the best knowledge of the author a rigorous treatise for TGV with spatially varying parameters has not been done yet in the literature. One exception is the recent work [HPRS20], where similar results are provided, but some proofs are omitted or only sketched.

Before presenting the theory, let us fix some notation and assumptions, which will hold during the forthcoming sections. For a function $\alpha \in C(\overline{\Omega})$ we will write

$$\underline{\alpha} := \inf_{x \in \overline{\Omega}} \alpha(x) \quad \overline{\alpha} := \sup_{x \in \overline{\Omega}} \alpha(x)$$

and similarly for $\boldsymbol{\alpha} \in C(\overline{\Omega}) \times C(\overline{\Omega})$ we set $\underline{\boldsymbol{\alpha}} = (\underline{\alpha}_0, \underline{\alpha}_1) \in \mathbb{R}^2$ and $\overline{\boldsymbol{\alpha}} = (\overline{\alpha}_0, \overline{\alpha}_1) \in \mathbb{R}^2$. In order to transfer the results from the original papers to our setting we must make some assumptions:

Assumption 1. (On the chapter)

1. The image domain $\Omega \subset \mathbb{R}^n$ is open, bounded and has a Lipschitz boundary.
2. The distributed parameters are denoted by $\alpha = (\alpha_0, \alpha_1) \in C(\overline{\Omega}) \times C(\overline{\Omega})$ and we always assume, that $\underline{\alpha} > 0$, i.e. the parameters are uniformly bounded away from zero.

Additionally, the following sets will play an important role in the definition of the TGV functional.

$$K_{\alpha,r}^2(X) := \{ \varphi \in X \mid |\varphi(x)|_r \leq \alpha_0(x) \text{ and } |\operatorname{div} \varphi(x)|_r \leq \alpha_1(x) \text{ for (almost) every } x \in \Omega \}$$

$$K_{\alpha,r}^1(X) := \{ \varphi \in X \mid |\varphi(x)|_r \leq \alpha(x) \text{ for (almost) every } x \in \Omega \}$$

where X is a function space of functions $\varphi : \Omega \rightarrow H$, for which the expressions above are well defined. In this thesis we will consider the cases $H \in \{\mathbb{R}^n, \mathbb{R}^{n \times n}, \mathbb{R}_{sym}^{n \times n}\}$, which are endowed with the finite dimensional r -norms. These are defined for $r \in [1, +\infty)$ by

$$|y|_r^r = \begin{cases} \sum_{i=1}^n |y_i|^r & \text{if } H = \mathbb{R}^n. \\ \sum_{i,j=1}^n |y_{ij}|^r & \text{if } H \in \{\mathbb{R}^{n \times n}, \mathbb{R}_{sym}^{n \times n}\}. \end{cases}$$

and for $r = +\infty$ by

$$|y|_\infty = \begin{cases} \max_{i=1,\dots,n} |y_i| & \text{if } H = \mathbb{R}^n. \\ \max_{i,j=1,\dots,n} |y_{ij}| & \text{if } H \in \{\mathbb{R}^{n \times n}, \mathbb{R}_{sym}^{n \times n}\}. \end{cases}$$

If $r = 2$ we will just write $K_\alpha^2(X) := K_{\alpha,2}^2(X)$ and $K_\alpha^1(X) := K_{\alpha,2}^1(X)$.

3.1 Basic Properties of TGV

We will now define the total generalized variation functional for spatially varying parameters $\alpha \in C(\overline{\Omega}) \times C(\overline{\Omega})$ and briefly study some of its fundamental attributes

Definition 10 (Total Generalized Variation functional). *Let $u \in L^1(\Omega)$ and $\alpha \in C(\overline{\Omega}) \times C(\overline{\Omega})$, such that Assumption 1 is satisfied. Then the Total Generalized Variation functional of second order with parameters $\alpha \in C(\overline{\Omega}) \times C(\overline{\Omega})$ is defined as*

$$TGV_{\alpha,r}^2(u) := \sup \left\{ \int_{\Omega} u \operatorname{div}^2 \varphi \, dx \mid \varphi \in K_{\alpha,r}^2(C_c^2(\Omega; \mathbb{R}_{sym}^{n \times n})) \right\} \quad (3.1)$$

If $r = 2$ we set $TGV_{\alpha}^2(u) = TGV_{\alpha,2}^2(u)$.

Remark 1. Notice that the Total Generalized Variation regularizer depends on the choice of the norm in the finite dimensional spaces $\mathbb{R}_{sym}^{n \times n}$ and \mathbb{R}^n . In this work we will focus only on the case $r=2$, which is sometimes also called *isotropic TGV*. However many theorems that are proven here, can be easily generalized to arbitrary $r \in [1, \infty]$. This has been done in [HPRS20]. For a general account on isotropic and anisotropic Total Variation we refer to the recent textbook [BL19].

The following statement investigates basic functional and variational properties of the TGV functional and has been first proven in [BKP10] for constant positive regularization parameters. We will adopt the proof here for the case of distributed weights $\alpha \in C(\overline{\Omega}) \times C(\overline{\Omega})$.

Lemma 1 (Basic properties of TGV). *Let $\alpha \in C(\overline{\Omega}) \times C(\overline{\Omega})$ such that the Assumption 1 hold true. Then the TGV functional in (3.1) satisfies the following properties*

1. TGV_{α}^2 is proper, convex and lower semi-continuous on $L^p(\Omega)$ for every $p \in [1, \infty)$.
2. TGV_{α}^2 is sub-additive, absolutely homogeneous and greater or equal zero, i.e. TGV_{α}^2 is a semi-norm on $L^1(\Omega)$.
3. $TGV_{\alpha}^2(u) = 0$ if and only if $u \in \mathcal{P}^1(\Omega)$ is a polynomial of degree less or equal than one.

Proof. We start proving 1.

Fix $p \in [1, \infty)$. By the definition (3.1), $TGV_{\alpha}^2 : L^p(\Omega) \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ is the pointwise supremum of a family of continuous, linear functions of the form

$$u \mapsto \int_{\Omega} u \operatorname{div}^2 \varphi \, dx \quad \text{indexed by } \varphi \in K_{\alpha}^2(C_c^2(\Omega; \mathbb{R}^{n \times n}))$$

Hence, by a standard result in convex analysis (cf. [ET99], section 2), also the pointwise supremum $TGV_{\alpha}^2 : L^p(\Omega) \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ is convex and lower semi-continuous.

Now we come to point 2.

We show, that $TGV_{\alpha}^2 : L^1(\Omega) \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ satisfies the properties of a semi-norm. For that purpose, fix $\lambda \in \mathbb{R}$ and notice the symmetry of $K_{\alpha}^2(C_c^2(\Omega; \mathbb{R}^{n \times n}))$:

$$\varphi \in K_{\alpha}^2(C_c^2(\Omega; \mathbb{R}^{n \times n})) \quad \text{if and only if} \quad -\varphi \in K_{\alpha}^2(C_c^2(\Omega; \mathbb{R}^{n \times n}))$$

Therefore we may also write

$$\begin{aligned} TGV_{\alpha}^2(\lambda u) &= \sup_{\varphi \in K_{\alpha}^2(C_c^2(\Omega; \mathbb{R}^{n \times n}))} \begin{cases} \lambda \int_{\Omega} u \operatorname{div}^2 \varphi \, dx & \text{if } \lambda \geq 0 \\ -\lambda \int_{\Omega} u \operatorname{div}^2 \varphi \, dx & \text{else} \end{cases} \\ &= |\lambda| TGV_{\alpha}^2(u) \end{aligned}$$

Hence TGV_{α}^2 is positive homogeneous, which also proves the triangle inequality: given $u, v \in L^1(\Omega)$ we see by exploiting the lines above and the convexity

$$TGV_{\alpha}^2(u + v) = 2 TGV_{\alpha}^2\left(\frac{u}{2} + \frac{v}{2}\right) \leq TGV_{\alpha}^2(u) + TGV_{\alpha}^2(v)$$

Since $0 \in K_{\alpha}^2(C_c^2(\Omega; \mathbb{R}^{n \times n}))$, we get $TGV_{\alpha}^2(\cdot) \geq 0$.

For the last claim 3., we use theorem 3 from [BKP10], which already states the assertion for constant regularization weights. Using that information as a prerequisite, the proof of the continuous case $\alpha \in C(\overline{\Omega}) \times C(\overline{\Omega})$ becomes obvious: If $u \in \mathcal{P}^1(\Omega)$, we obtain

$$0 \leq TGV_{\alpha}^2(u) \leq TGV_{\alpha}^2(u) = 0$$

and therefore $TGV_{\alpha}^2(u) = 0$. For the opposite direction, assume that $TGV_{\alpha}^2(u) = 0$ and use again

$$0 \leq TGV_{\alpha}^2(u) \leq TGV_{\alpha}^2(u) = 0$$

as before, by theorem 3 in [BKP10] this gives $u \in \mathcal{P}^1(\Omega)$. □

As $u \mapsto TGV_{\alpha}^2(u)$ is a semi-norm on $L^1(\Omega)$ it is natural to introduce the normed vectorspace:

$$BGV_{\alpha}^2(\Omega) := \{u \in L^1(\Omega) \mid TGV_{\alpha}^2(u) < \infty\} \quad \text{with} \quad \|u\|_{BGV_{\alpha}^2(\Omega)} := \|u\|_{L^1(\Omega)} + TGV_{\alpha}^2(u) \quad (3.2)$$

In [BKP10] it was shown for scalar parameters, that $BGV_{\alpha}^2(\Omega)$ is a Banach space, whose topology does not depend on the specific choice of the regularization weights. Exploiting again the estimate

$$TGV_{\alpha}^2(u) \leq TGV_{\alpha}^2(u) \leq TGV_{\alpha}^2(u) \quad \text{for every } u \in L^1(\Omega)$$

this result can be directly extended to the case of spatially varying regularization-parameters $\alpha \in C(\overline{\Omega}) \times C(\overline{\Omega})$. For that reason we will skip the α in the definition (3.2) and only write $BGV^2(\Omega)$ for the space of functions with bounded total generalized variation.

3.2 Equivalent Minimum Characterization of TGV

As the original definition (3.1) does not provide sufficient interpretability, the authors in [BKP10] and [BH14] also gave the following equivalent characterization of TGV

$$TGV_{\alpha}^2(u) = \min_{w \in BD(\Omega)} \alpha_1 \int_{\Omega} d|Du - w| + \alpha_0 \int_{\Omega} d|\mathcal{E} w| \quad \text{for } u \in BGV^2(\Omega) \quad (3.3)$$

Where $\alpha \in \mathbb{R}^2$ are constant, strictly positive regularization parameters. The latter is often called *minimum characterization of TGV*. Besides its theoretical advantages, this characterization also enables a better understanding of the functional and gives more insight into the regularization process: Therefore consider formally the decomposition

$$\nabla u = (\nabla u - w) + w \quad \text{and} \quad \nabla^2 u = \mathcal{E}(\nabla u - w) + \mathcal{E}(w)$$

Here, we do not care about any regularity of u and w and simply assume sufficiently high differentiability, such that the last line makes sense. We then distinguish two cases:

If $\alpha_1 \gg \alpha_0$, a possible minimizer \bar{w} of the problem on the righthand side of (3.3) might look like $\bar{w} \approx \nabla u$, which results in $TGV_{\alpha}^2(u) \approx \alpha_0 \|\nabla^2 u\|$ by looking at the decomposition above. Hence $TGV_{\alpha}^2(\cdot)$ behaves more like a second order penalizer in that case.

If on the other hand $\alpha_1 \ll \alpha_0$, then choosing $\bar{w} \approx 0$ already should make the objective of the right side of (3.3) fairly small. In that case we see, that $TGV_{\alpha}^2(u) \approx \alpha_1 TV(u)$. To summarize these heuristic observations, we conclude that TGV_{α}^2 is able to balance between a first order and a second order penalty and the balancing is controlled by the parameters $\alpha \in \mathbb{R}^2$. Of course, the discussion above is just an informal one, but the intuition behind these lines can be turned into a rigorous proof like it was done in [PV15]. In fact those authors investigated the limit behavior of the regularization parameters and found the following interesting result:

Theorem 16. (*Asymptotic behavior for TGV with scalar parameters*) *Let $\Omega \subset \mathbb{R}^n$ open, bounded with Lipschitz boundary. Then there is a constant $C > 0$, such that the following statement holds true.*

$$\text{If } \alpha_0/\alpha_1 \geq C, \text{ then for every } u \in BV(\Omega): \quad TGV_{\alpha}^2(u) = \alpha_1 \|Du - m_{\mathcal{E}}(u)\|_{\mathcal{M}(\Omega; \mathbb{R}^n)}$$

where

$$m_{\mathcal{E}}(u) = \operatorname{argmin}_{w \in \mathcal{N}(\mathcal{E})} \|\nabla u - w\|_{L^1(\Omega; \mathbb{R}^n)}$$

and $\nabla u \in L^1(\Omega; \mathbb{R}^n)$ denotes the density of the absolute continuous part $(Du)^a \ll \mathcal{L}^n$ with respect to the Lebesgue measure \mathcal{L}^n .

Hence in the case of $\alpha_1 \gg \alpha_0$, $TGV_{\alpha}^2(\cdot)$ is in fact a first order regularizer. For the proof of that result and further information on the limit behavior of the parameters, consult [PV15].

Our goal is now, to extend the characterization (3.3) to the case of spatially varying regularization parameters. The main tool will be the calculus of Fenchel conjugates, which requires to work in Banach spaces, cf. chapter 2. As the C_c^k -spaces are not complete, we first argue that TGV_{α}^2 can also be written as the supremum over a suitable family of C_0^2 -functions, namely

$$TGV_{\alpha}^2 = \sup \left\{ \int_{\Omega} u \operatorname{div}^2 \varphi \, dx \mid \varphi \in K_{\alpha}^2(C_0^2(\Omega; \mathbb{R}_{sym}^{n \times n})) \right\} \quad (3.4)$$

By standard results on functional analysis, the last line is immediately clear if the following density lemma is satisfied.

Lemma 2 (Density results in spaces of differentiable functions). *Let $\alpha \in C(\overline{\Omega})$, $\alpha \in C(\overline{\Omega}) \times \overline{\Omega}$ such that Assumption 1 holds true. Then the following density results are satisfied*

$$\begin{aligned} \overline{K_{\alpha}^2(C_c^{\infty}(\Omega, \mathbb{R}^{n \times n}))}^{\|\cdot\|_{C^k(\Omega, \mathbb{R}^{n \times n})}} &= K_{\alpha}^2(C_0^k(\Omega, \mathbb{R}^{n \times n})) && \text{for } k \in \mathbb{N} \text{ s.t. } k \geq 1. \\ \overline{K_{\alpha}^1(C_c^{\infty}(\Omega, \mathbb{R}^n))}^{\|\cdot\|_{C^k(\Omega, \mathbb{R}^n)}} &= K_{\alpha}^1(C_0^k(\Omega, \mathbb{R}^n)) && \text{for } k \in \mathbb{N}. \end{aligned}$$

Proof. We only prove the first equation. As the proof of the second one works quite identical, we skip it here. Therefore fix $k \in \mathbb{N}$, $k \geq 1$ and observe, that $K_{\alpha}^2(C_0^k(\Omega, \mathbb{R}^{n \times n}))$ is closed with respect to the $\|\cdot\|_{C^k(\Omega, \mathbb{R}^{n \times n})}$ -norm. Hence „ \subseteq “ is immediately clear and we will focus on showing the opposite inclusion „ \supseteq “.

For that purpose take an arbitrary $u \in K_{\alpha}^2(C_0^k(\Omega, \mathbb{R}^{n \times n}))$, $\varepsilon > 0$ and introduce the scaled version

$$u_{\lambda} := \lambda u \in C_0^k(\Omega, \mathbb{R}^{n \times n})$$

for some parameter $\lambda \in (0, 1)$, which will be adjusted later in dependence of $\varepsilon > 0$. Then we observe for every $x \in \Omega$:

$$\begin{aligned} |u_{\lambda}(x)| &= \lambda |u(x)| \leq \lambda \alpha_0(x) \leq \alpha_0(x) - c_{\lambda,0} \\ |\operatorname{div} u_{\lambda}(x)| &= \lambda |\operatorname{div} u(x)| \leq \lambda \alpha_1(x) \leq \alpha_1(x) - c_{\lambda,1} \end{aligned}$$

with constants $c_{\lambda,i} > 0$, that can be chosen independently of $x \in \Omega$ and such that still $\alpha_i(x) - c_{\lambda,i} > 0$ for every $x \in \Omega$ and $i = 0, 1$. For example one could take

$$c_{\lambda,i} = (1 - \lambda) \underline{\alpha}_i$$

Consequently it holds $u_{\lambda} \in K_{\alpha - c_{\lambda}}^2(C_0^k(\Omega, \mathbb{R}^{n \times n}))$. By exploiting the density of $C_c^{\infty}(\Omega, \mathbb{R}^{n \times n})$ in $C_0^k(\Omega, \mathbb{R}^{n \times n})$ with respect to $\|\cdot\|_{C^k(\Omega, \mathbb{R}^{n \times n})}$ we find for any $0 < \delta$ an $u_{\lambda, \delta} \in C_c^{\infty}(\Omega, \mathbb{R}^{n \times n})$ such that

$$\|u_{\lambda, \delta} - u_{\lambda}\|_{C^k(\Omega, \mathbb{R}^{n \times n})} < \delta$$

Again we will set $\delta = \delta(\varepsilon) > 0$ later. Now we obtain for any $x \in \Omega$:

$$\begin{aligned} |u_{\lambda, \delta}(x)| &\leq \|u_{\lambda, \delta} - u_{\lambda}\|_{C^k(\Omega, \mathbb{R}^{n \times n})} + |u_{\lambda}(x)| < \delta + \lambda \alpha_0(x) \leq \delta + \alpha_0(x) - c_{\lambda,0} \\ |\operatorname{div} u_{\lambda, \delta}(x)| &= \|\operatorname{div} u_{\lambda, \delta} - \operatorname{div} u_{\lambda}\|_{C^0(\mathbb{R}^n)} + |\operatorname{div} u_{\lambda}(x)| \\ &\leq \|\operatorname{div}\|_{\mathcal{L}} \|u_{\lambda, \delta} - u_{\lambda}\|_{C^k(\mathbb{R}^{n \times n})} + \alpha_1(x) - c_{\lambda,1} \\ &\leq \|\operatorname{div}\|_{\mathcal{L}} \delta + \alpha_1(x) - c_{\lambda,1} \end{aligned} \tag{3.5}$$

where we used the fact, that $\operatorname{div}: C^1(\Omega; \mathbb{R}^{n \times n}) \rightarrow C^0(\Omega; \mathbb{R}^n)$ is a linear and continuous operator. Now we choose $\lambda > 0$ such that

$$(1 - \lambda) \|u\|_{C^k(\Omega, \mathbb{R}^{n \times n})} < \frac{\varepsilon}{2} \tag{3.6}$$

and afterwards $\delta > 0$ such that the following three conditions hold

$$\begin{aligned} \delta - c_{\lambda,0} &\leq 0 \\ \|\operatorname{div}\|_{\mathcal{L}} \delta - c_{\lambda,1} &\leq 0 \\ \delta &< \frac{\varepsilon}{2} \end{aligned} \tag{3.7}$$

From (3.5), (3.6) and (3.7) we finally obtain the claim of the statement:

$$\begin{aligned} u_{\lambda, \delta} &\in K_{\alpha}^2(C_c^{\infty}(\Omega, \mathbb{R}^{n \times n})) \\ \|u_{\lambda, \delta} - u\|_{C^k(\Omega, \mathbb{R}^{n \times n})} &\leq \|u_{\lambda, \delta} - u_{\lambda}\|_{C^k(\Omega, \mathbb{R}^{n \times n})} + \|u_{\lambda} - u\|_{C^k(\Omega, \mathbb{R}^{n \times n})} \\ &\leq \delta + (1 - \lambda) \|u\|_{C^k(\Omega, \mathbb{R}^{n \times n})} \\ &< \varepsilon \end{aligned}$$

□

Having shown this technical lemma we can now turn to the main point of this section, which is the proof of the minimum characterization of TGV. The latter is provided in two steps. The first and the more difficult part will be treated in the following theorem. In our argumentation we will closely follow the work [BV11], where the argumentation is only sketched.

Theorem 17. *Let $u \in L^1(\Omega)$, $\alpha \in C(\overline{\Omega})$, such that $\underline{\alpha} > 0$ and choose the Banach spaces $X = C_0^2(\Omega, \mathbb{R}_{sym}^{n \times n})$ and $Y = C_0^1(\Omega, \mathbb{R}^n)$. Then the following two equations hold true for any $w \in Y^*$.*

$$\sup_{v \in K_\alpha^1(C_0^2(\Omega, \mathbb{R}_{sym}^{n \times n}))} \langle w, -\operatorname{div} v \rangle_{Y^*, Y} = \begin{cases} \int_\Omega \alpha \, d|\mathcal{E} w| & \text{if } w \in BD(\Omega) \\ +\infty & \text{else} \end{cases} \quad (3.8)$$

and

$$\sup_{v \in K_\alpha^1(C_0^1(\Omega, \mathbb{R}^n))} \langle w, v \rangle_{Y^*, Y} + \int_\Omega u \operatorname{div} v \, dx = \begin{cases} \int_\Omega \alpha \, d|Du - w| & \text{if } Du - w \in \mathcal{M}(\Omega; \mathbb{R}_{sym}^{n \times n}) \\ +\infty & \text{else} \end{cases} \quad (3.9)$$

Proof. We start proving (3.8).

First assume, that $w \in Y^*$, $w \notin BD(\Omega)$ but

$$\sup_{v \in K_\alpha^1(C_0^2(\Omega; \mathbb{R}_{sym}^{n \times n}))} \langle w, -\operatorname{div} v \rangle_{Y^*, Y} < \infty$$

Then we observe the inequalities

$$\begin{aligned} \sup_{v \in K_\alpha^1(C_0^2(\Omega; \mathbb{R}_{sym}^{n \times n}))} \langle w, -\operatorname{div} v \rangle_{Y^*, Y} &\geq \sup_{v \in K_\alpha^1(C_0^2(\Omega; \mathbb{R}_{sym}^{n \times n}))} \langle w, -\operatorname{div} v \rangle_{Y^*, Y} \\ &\geq \underline{\alpha} \sup_{v \in K_1^1(C_c^\infty(\Omega; \mathbb{R}_{sym}^{n \times n}))} \langle w, -\operatorname{div} v \rangle_{\mathcal{D}', \mathcal{D}} \end{aligned} \quad (3.10)$$

By the definition of the distributional symmetric derivative of $w \in \mathcal{D}'(\Omega; \mathbb{R}^n)$, it holds

$$\sup_{v \in K_1^1(C_c^\infty(\Omega; \mathbb{R}_{sym}^{n \times n}))} \langle w, -\operatorname{div} v \rangle_{\mathcal{D}', \mathcal{D}} = \sup_{v \in K_1^1(C_c^\infty(\Omega; \mathbb{R}_{sym}^{n \times n}))} \langle \mathcal{E} w, v \rangle_{\mathcal{D}', \mathcal{D}} \quad (3.11)$$

and if the term on the right hand side is finite, we may, due to the density results in Lemma 2, extend $\mathcal{E} w \in \mathcal{D}'(\Omega; \mathbb{R}_{sym}^{n \times n})$ to a unique element of $C_0(\Omega; \mathbb{R}_{sym}^{n \times n})^* \simeq \mathcal{M}(\Omega; \mathbb{R}_{sym}^{n \times n})$. By Theorem 7, this already implies, that even $w \in BD(\Omega)$, which contradicts our assumption. Hence, a combination of (3.10) and (3.11) yields

$$\sup_{v \in K_\alpha^1(C_0^2(\Omega; \mathbb{R}_{sym}^{n \times n}))} \langle w, -\operatorname{div} v \rangle_{Y^*, Y} = +\infty$$

which was to show.

Now assume, that instead $w \in BD(\Omega)$. Then, as before we use the density result from Lemma 2 to obtain

$$\begin{aligned} \sup_{v \in K_\alpha^1(C_0^2(\Omega; \mathbb{R}_{sym}^{n \times n}))} \langle w, -\operatorname{div} v \rangle_{Y^*, Y} &= \sup_{v \in K_\alpha^1(C_0^2(\Omega; \mathbb{R}_{sym}^{n \times n}))} \int_\Omega -\operatorname{div} v \cdot w \, dx \\ &= \sup_{v \in K_\alpha^1(C_c^\infty(\Omega; \mathbb{R}_{sym}^{n \times n}))} \int_\Omega -\operatorname{div} v \cdot w \, dx \end{aligned}$$

As $\mathcal{E}w \in \mathcal{M}(\Omega; \mathbb{R}_{sym}^{n \times n})$ by assumption, we deduce

$$\begin{aligned}
\sup_{v \in K_\alpha^1(C_c^\infty(\Omega; \mathbb{R}_{sym}^{n \times n}))} \langle w, -\operatorname{div} v \rangle_{Y^*, Y} &= \sup_{v \in K_\alpha^1(C_c^\infty(\Omega; \mathbb{R}_{sym}^{n \times n}))} \int_\Omega v \, d\mathcal{E}w \\
&= \sup_{v \in K_\alpha^1(C_0(\Omega; \mathbb{R}_{sym}^{n \times n}))} \int_\Omega v \, d\mathcal{E}w \\
&= \sup_{v \in K_1^1(C_0(\Omega; \mathbb{R}_{sym}^{n \times n}))} \int_\Omega (\alpha v) \, d\mathcal{E}w \\
&= \sup_{v \in K_1^1(C_c^\infty(\Omega; \mathbb{R}_{sym}^{n \times n}))} \int_\Omega (\alpha v) \, d\mathcal{E}w
\end{aligned} \tag{3.12}$$

Note, that in the second and the fourth equation of the above lines, we used again the density result from Lemma 2. Employing the above equation, some simple manipulations, which were justified in the measure theory part of this thesis yield

$$\begin{aligned}
\sup_{v \in K_\alpha^1(C_c^\infty(\Omega; \mathbb{R}_{sym}^{n \times n}))} \langle w, -\operatorname{div} v \rangle_{Y^*, Y} &= \sup_{v \in K_1^1(C_c^\infty(\Omega; \mathbb{R}_{sym}^{n \times n}))} \int_\Omega (\alpha v) \, d\mathcal{E}w \\
&= \sup_{v \in K_1^1(C_c^\infty(\Omega; \mathbb{R}_{sym}^{n \times n}))} \int_\Omega v \, d(\alpha \cdot \mathcal{E}w) \\
&= \sup_{v \in K_1^1(C_0(\Omega; \mathbb{R}_{sym}^{n \times n}))} \int_\Omega v \, d(\alpha \cdot \mathcal{E}w) \\
&= \|\alpha \cdot \mathcal{E}w\|_{\mathcal{M}(\Omega; \mathbb{R}_{sym}^{n \times n})}
\end{aligned}$$

where the last two equations result from the density in Lemma 2 under usage of Theorem 5 and the assumption, that $w \in BD(\Omega)$. Consequently, we obtain by exploiting Theorem 6 the final result

$$\sup_{v \in K_\alpha^1(C_0^2(\Omega; \mathbb{R}_{sym}^{n \times n}))} \langle w, -\operatorname{div} v \rangle_{Y^*, Y} = \int_\Omega \alpha \, d|\mathcal{E}w| \tag{3.13}$$

We continue by proving (3.9).

Since the argumentation is almost the same as above, we only show the main steps and skip the details. Again take the distributional gradient $Du \in \mathcal{D}'(\Omega; \mathbb{R}^n)$ and assume, that it holds

$$Du - w \notin \mathcal{M}(\Omega; \mathbb{R}^n)$$

but also

$$\sup_{v \in K_\alpha^1(C_0^1(\Omega; \mathbb{R}^n))} \langle w, v \rangle_{Y^*, Y} + \int_\Omega u \operatorname{div} v \, dx < \infty$$

We will show again a contradiction:

Completely analogous to the first lines of this proof we obtain

$$\begin{aligned}
\sup_{v \in K_\alpha^1(C_0^1(\Omega; \mathbb{R}^n))} \langle w, v \rangle_{Y^*, Y} + \int_\Omega u \operatorname{div} v \, dx &= \sup_{v \in K_\alpha^1(C_c^\infty(\Omega; \mathbb{R}^n))} \langle Du - w, v \rangle_{\mathcal{D}', \mathcal{D}} \\
&\geq \underline{\alpha} \sup_{v \in K_1^1(C_c^\infty(\Omega; \mathbb{R}^n))} \langle Du - w, v \rangle_{\mathcal{D}', \mathcal{D}}
\end{aligned} \tag{3.14}$$

If the last term is finite, namely

$$\sup_{v \in K_1^1(C_c^\infty(\Omega; \mathbb{R}^n))} \langle Du - w, v \rangle_{\mathcal{D}', \mathcal{D}} < +\infty$$

we may, with the help of the density arguments in Lemma 2, extend $Du - w \in \mathcal{D}'(\Omega; \mathbb{R}^n)$ uniquely to an element of $C_0(\Omega, \mathbb{R}^n)^* \simeq \mathcal{M}(\Omega; \mathbb{R}^n)$, which is a contradiction to our starting assumptions. Hence it must hold

$$\sup_{v \in K_1^1(C_c^\infty(\Omega; \mathbb{R}^n))} \langle Du - w, v \rangle_{\mathcal{D}', \mathcal{D}} = +\infty$$

In combination with (3.14) we conclude

$$\sup_{v \in K_\alpha^1(C_0^1(\Omega; \mathbb{R}^n))} \langle w, v \rangle_{Y^*, Y} + \int_\Omega u \operatorname{div} v \, dx = +\infty$$

Now we suppose, that $Du - w \in \mathcal{M}(\Omega; \mathbb{R}^n)$. With a similar argumentation as in the derivation of (3.13), we infer

$$\begin{aligned} \sup_{v \in K_\alpha^1(C_0^1(\Omega; \mathbb{R}^n))} \langle w, v \rangle_{Y^*, Y} + \int_\Omega u \operatorname{div} v \, dx &= \sup_{v \in K_\alpha^1(C_c^\infty(\Omega; \mathbb{R}^n))} \langle w, v \rangle_{Y^*, Y} + \int_\Omega u \operatorname{div} v \, dx \\ &= \sup_{v \in K_\alpha^1(C_c^\infty(\Omega; \mathbb{R}^n))} \langle w - Du, v \rangle_{\mathcal{D}', \mathcal{D}} \\ &= \sup_{v \in K_1^1(C_c^\infty(\Omega; \mathbb{R}^n))} \int_\Omega (\alpha v) \, d(Du - w) \\ &= \sup_{v \in K_1^1(C_c^\infty(\Omega; \mathbb{R}^n))} \int_\Omega v \, d\alpha \cdot (Du - w) \end{aligned}$$

where we again used the calculus from chapter 2 for the finite Radon measure $Du - w \in \mathcal{M}(\Omega; \mathbb{R}^n)$ and the density in Lemma 2. In particular for the third equation above, we used the same argumentation as in (3.12). A further usage of the density in Lemma 2 and an application of the measure theoretic arguments from the first part of this thesis lead to

$$\begin{aligned} \sup_{v \in K_\alpha^1(C_0^1(\Omega; \mathbb{R}^n))} \langle w, v \rangle_{Y^*, Y} + \int_\Omega u \operatorname{div} v \, dx &= \|\alpha \cdot (Du - w)\|_{\mathcal{M}(\Omega; \mathbb{R}^n)} \\ &= \int_\Omega \alpha \, d|Du - w| \end{aligned}$$

□

Note that in the last proof, we used the notation

$$K_1^1(X) := \{ \varphi \in X \mid |\varphi(x)|_2 \leq 1 \text{ for (almost) every } x \in \Omega \}$$

Now, the remaining part in the proof of the minimum characterization consists only on applying the Fenchel duality theory in a correct way.

Theorem 18 (Minimum characterization of TGV). *Let $\Omega \subset \mathbb{R}^n$ and $\alpha \in C(\overline{\Omega}) \times C(\overline{\Omega})$, such that Assumption 1 holds. Then for every $u \in L^1(\Omega)$ the following equivalent characterization of TGV_α^2 is satisfied:*

$$TGV_\alpha^2(u) = \begin{cases} \min_{w \in BD(\Omega)} \int_\Omega \alpha_1 \, d|Du - w| + \int_\Omega \alpha_0 \, d|\mathcal{E}w| & \text{if } u \in BV(\Omega) \\ +\infty & \text{else} \end{cases} \quad (3.15)$$

In particular this implies, that $TGV_\alpha^2(u)$ is finite if and only if $u \in BV(\Omega)$.

Proof. The strategy is, to express $TGV_\alpha^2(\cdot)$ as a suitable minimization problem and to apply the Fenchel duality theory from chapter 2.

For that purpose, we fix $u \in L^1(\Omega)$ and define again the Banach spaces $X := C_0^2(\Omega, \mathbb{R}_{sym}^{n \times n})$ and $Y := C_0^1(\Omega, \mathbb{R}^n)$, both equipped with their standard topologies. Now consider the functions

$$\begin{aligned} F: X &\rightarrow \overline{\mathbb{R}} & v &\mapsto \mathcal{I}_{K_{\alpha_0}^1(X)}(v) \\ G: Y &\rightarrow \overline{\mathbb{R}} & w &\mapsto \mathcal{I}_{K_{\alpha_1}^1(Y)}(w) - \int_{\Omega} u \operatorname{div} w \, dx \\ \Lambda: X &\rightarrow Y & v &\mapsto \operatorname{div} v \end{aligned}$$

Obviously $\Lambda \in \mathcal{L}(X, Y)$ and we obtain, by exploiting the density result Lemma 2

$$TGV_{\alpha}^2(u) = - \inf_{v \in X} F(v) + G(\Lambda v) \quad (3.16)$$

Using the Fenchel conjugates $F^*: X^* \rightarrow \overline{\mathbb{R}}$ and $G^*: Y^* \rightarrow \overline{\mathbb{R}}$ we immediately find

$$TGV_{\alpha}^2(u) \leq \inf_{w \in Y^*} F^*(-\Lambda^* w) + G^*(w) \quad (3.17)$$

Note, that the righthandside of (3.17) is the Fenchel dual problem of (3.16) for which it is a priori unclear, whether there is a solution at all.

Minding Theorem 17, the concrete expressions for the Fenchel conjugates read

$$F^*(-\Lambda^* w) = \begin{cases} \int_{\Omega} \alpha_0 \, d|\mathcal{E} w| & \text{if } w \in BD(\Omega) \\ +\infty & \text{else} \end{cases} \quad (3.18)$$

$$G^*(w) = \begin{cases} \int_{\Omega} \alpha_1 \, d|Du - w| & \text{if } Du - w \in \mathcal{M}(\Omega; \mathbb{R}^n) \\ +\infty & \text{else} \end{cases} \quad (3.19)$$

After presenting the general framework, we turn to the proof of equation (3.15):

Therefore take $u \in L^1(\Omega)$, but $u \notin BV(\Omega)$ and proceed by contradiction, i.e. assume

$$TGV_{\alpha}^2(u) < +\infty \quad (3.20)$$

Then we find $u_0 \in X$ such that $u_0 \in \operatorname{Dom}(F)$, $\Lambda u_0 \in \operatorname{Dom}(G)$ and $G(\cdot)$ being continuous at Λu_0 : For instance, take $u_0 = 0$ and notice the fact, that the indicator

$$\mathcal{I}_{K_{\alpha_1}^1(Y)}: Y \rightarrow \overline{\mathbb{R}} \quad (3.21)$$

is convex and bounded in a small neighborhood of $0 \in Y$, which already implies the continuity of $G(\cdot)$ at zero, by Theorem 10. Hence the (Slater) condition is satisfied, Theorem 13 applies and we conclude

$$TGV_{\alpha}^2(u) = \min_{w \in Y^*} F^*(-\Lambda^* w) + G^*(w)$$

where now the minimum is attained! As $TGV_{\alpha}^2(u)$ is assumed finite, we infer from the equations (3.18) and (3.19), that actually $w \in BD(\Omega)$ and $Du - w \in \mathcal{M}(\Omega; \mathbb{R}^n)$. This directly implies $Du \in \mathcal{M}(\Omega; \mathbb{R}^n)$ and consequently $u \in BV(\Omega)$, which is a contradiction, i.e. it has to hold

$$TGV_{\alpha}^2(u) = +\infty$$

Now assume instead $u \in BV(\Omega)$. Again recalling inequality (3.17), we obtain

$$TGV_{\alpha}^2(u) \leq F^*(-\Lambda^* 0) + G^*(0) = \int_{\Omega} \alpha_1 \, d|Du| < +\infty$$

and we are again in the regime of (3.20). Moreover the same argumentation as above shows, that Slaters constraint qualification holds, which results in

$$TGV_{\alpha}^2(u) = \min_{w \in Y^*} F^*(-\Lambda^* w) + G^*(w) \quad (3.22)$$

by Theorem 13. Employing the concrete formulas for both Fenchel conjugates, (3.18) and (3.19), we conclude, that the minimizer of the righthandside of (3.22) has to lie in the space $BD(\Omega)$ and the following equation holds true:

$$TGV_{\alpha}^2(u) = \min_{w \in BD(\Omega)} \int_{\Omega} \alpha_1 d|Du - w| + \int_{\Omega} \alpha_0 d|\mathcal{E}w|$$

This finishes the proof. \square

3.3 Topological Equivalence with BV

A rigorous analysis of inverse problems with TGV regularization in infinite dimensions is only possible if the main functional analytical properties of the underlying function space are known. However this is not the case for the space $BGV^2(\Omega)$, introduced in (3.2). The following theorem bridges this gap by showing topological equivalence between $BGV^2(\Omega)$ and $BV(\Omega)$.

Theorem 19. *Let $\alpha \in C(\overline{\Omega}) \times C(\overline{\Omega})$, such that Assumption 1 holds true. Then there exist positive constants $c_{\alpha}, C_{\alpha} > 0$, such that the following inequality is valid:*

$$c_{\alpha} \|u\|_{BV(\Omega)} \leq \|u\|_{L^1(\Omega)} + TGV_{\alpha}^2(u) \leq C_{\alpha} \|u\|_{BV(\Omega)} \quad (3.23)$$

i.e. in a topological sense, we have $BV(\Omega) = BGV^2(\Omega)$.

Proof. The theorem has been proven for constant parameters in [BV11]. Using again the estimate

$$TGV_{\underline{\alpha}}^2(u) \leq TGV_{\alpha}^2(u) \leq TGV_{\overline{\alpha}}^2(u) \quad \text{for every } u \in L^1(\Omega)$$

this result can be immediately extended to spatially varying parameters $\alpha \in C(\overline{\Omega}) \times C(\overline{\Omega})$. \square

The previous statement sets the basis for our investigations in the following sections, since it allows us to use the topological properties of $BV(\Omega)$ also when it comes to regularization with the TGV_{α}^2 -functional.

3.4 Existence of Solutions for the Reconstruction Problem

As described in the introductory part, we want to recover an unknown image $u_{true} \in L^2(\Omega)$ from degraded measurements

$$f = Ku_{true} + \eta$$

where $\eta \in L^2(\Omega)$ is some highly oscillating error term, which corresponds to gaussian noise, when considering finite dimensional pixels. This is done by the so called variational approach, in which the the clean image u_{true} is estimated by solving the following optimization problem

$$\min_{u \in L^2(\Omega)} J_{\alpha}(u) := \frac{1}{2} \|Ku - f\|_{L^2(\Omega)}^2 + TGV_{\alpha}^2(u) \quad (P)$$

We want to study first, under which conditions (P) has a solution at all, but before coming to the existence proof we need a Poincare Wirtinger inequality for TGV. For the following part note, that the projection

$$P_{\mathcal{P}_1(\Omega)} : L^2(\Omega) \rightarrow \mathcal{P}_1(\Omega)$$

from $L^2(\Omega)$ on the subspace of polynomials of degree less or equal then one, namely $\mathcal{P}_1(\Omega)$ always exists, since the latter is a finite dimensional and therefore closed linear subspace of $L^2(\Omega)$.

Theorem 20 (Poincaré Wirtinger for TGV). *Let $\Omega \subseteq \mathbb{R}^2$ be a bounded Lipschitz domain and let $\alpha \in C(\overline{\Omega}) \times C(\overline{\Omega})$ denote the regularization parameter, which satisfies Assumption 1. Then there is a $C = C(\alpha) > 0$, such that*

$$\|u - P_{\mathcal{P}_1(\Omega)} u\|_{L^2(\Omega)} \leq C \text{TGV}_{\alpha}^2(u) \quad \text{for every } u \in L^2(\Omega)$$

Proof. The proof of the assertion is presented in [BV11] for scalar regularization parameters. Using again the estimate

$$\text{TGV}_{\underline{\alpha}}^2(u) \leq \text{TGV}_{\alpha}^2(u) \quad \text{for every } u \in L^2(\Omega)$$

the statement can directly be extended to the case of continuous weights. \square

We continue with the existence theorem for the TGV reconstruction problem (P). The proof technique we use is very similar to that one in [BH14] and [BV11]. We emphasize the fact, that the following theorem does not rely on further assumptions on the operator $K \in \mathcal{L}(L^2(\Omega))$, like injectivity on $\mathcal{P}_1(\Omega)$, which is typically demanded in the literature on TV regularization, cf. for instance [Vog02].

Theorem 21 (Existence of solutions). *Let again $\Omega \subset \mathbb{R}^2$ denote a bounded Lipschitz domain and $K \in \mathcal{L}(L^2(\Omega))$ a continuous operator with given noisy data $f \in L^2(\Omega)$ and regularization parameters $\alpha \in C(\overline{\Omega}) \times C(\overline{\Omega})$ such that Assumption 1 holds true. Then the following problem admits at least one solution*

$$\min_{u \in L^2(\Omega)} J_{\alpha}(u) = \frac{1}{2} \|Ku - f\|_{L^2(\Omega)}^2 + \text{TGV}_{\alpha}^2(u) \quad (\text{P})$$

Moreover the solution is unique, if K is injective.

Remark 2. The statement above cannot be verified by simply applying the direct method, see e.g. [BMA06] on the whole $L^2(\Omega)$ and for general K , since there is no coercivity on the whole space. To see this, consider $K = 0 \in \mathcal{L}(L^2(\Omega))$ and a sequence $(p_n)_{n \in \mathbb{N}} \subset \mathcal{P}^1(\Omega)$ with

$$\|p_n\|_{L^2(\Omega)} \rightarrow +\infty \quad \text{as } n \rightarrow \infty$$

Then clearly

$$J_{\alpha}(p_n) = \frac{1}{2} \|f\|_{L^2(\Omega)}^2 \quad \text{for every } n \in \mathbb{N}$$

Hence the objective $J_{\alpha}(\cdot)$ is not coercive on $L^2(\Omega)$.

Proof. (Of Theorem 21)

First, notice two obvious properties of TGV: For every $u \in L^1(\Omega)$ and $p \in \mathcal{P}_1(\Omega)$ it holds

$$\text{TGV}_{\alpha}^2(u) \geq 0 \quad (3.24)$$

$$\text{TGV}_{\alpha}^2(u + p) = \text{TGV}_{\alpha}^2(u) \quad (3.25)$$

The preceding remark shows, that we cannot expect coercivity of $J_{\alpha}(\cdot)$ on the whole $L^2(\Omega)$, hence we will restrict the objective to a smaller subspace, where also $K \in \mathcal{L}(L^2(\Omega))$ is injective. For that purpose define the subspace

$$X := \mathcal{P}_1(\Omega) \cap \mathcal{N}(K) \quad (3.26)$$

which is a finite dimensional, and therefore closed subspace of $L^2(\Omega)$. Next, we uniquely decompose an arbitrary $u \in L^2(\Omega)$ into

$$u = u_1 + u_2 = P_{X^\perp}(u) + P_X(u) \quad \in X^\perp \oplus X = L^2(\Omega)$$

and immediately obtain by using (3.25) and (3.26)

$$\begin{aligned} J_{\alpha}(u) &= \frac{1}{2} \|Ku_1 + Ku_2 - f\|_{L^2(\Omega)}^2 + TGV_{\alpha}^2(u_1 + u_2) \\ &= \frac{1}{2} \|Ku_1 - f\|_{L^2(\Omega)}^2 + TGV_{\alpha}^2(u_1) \\ &= J_{\alpha}(u_1) \end{aligned}$$

consequently we conclude the equivalence of the following minimization problems:

$$\min_{u \in L^2(\Omega)} J_{\alpha}(u) = \min_{u \in X^{\perp}} J_{\alpha}(u) \quad (3.27)$$

Therefore, it is sufficient to restrict the further search for minimizers of $J_{\alpha}(\cdot)$ to the Hilbert space $X^{\perp} \subset L^2(\Omega)$. Since $J_{\alpha}(u) \geq 0$ for every $u \in X^{\perp}$ we may now take an infimizing sequence $(u_n)_{n \in \mathbb{N}} \subset X^{\perp}$ with

$$J_{\alpha}(u_n) \rightarrow \inf_{u \in X^{\perp}} J_{\alpha}(u) \quad \text{as } n \rightarrow \infty$$

from the definition of $J_{\alpha}(\cdot)$, we directly infer that

$$\{\|Ku_n - f\|_{L^2(\Omega)}^2\}_{n \in \mathbb{N}} \quad \text{and} \quad \{TGV_{\alpha}^2(u_n)\}_{n \in \mathbb{N}} \quad \text{are bounded} \quad (3.28)$$

Using Poincaré-Wirtinger inequality, Theorem 20 it follows

$$\|u_n - P_{\mathcal{P}_1(\Omega)} u_n\|_{L^2(\Omega)} \leq TGV_{\alpha}^2(u_n) \quad (3.29)$$

Since $P_{\mathcal{P}_1(\Omega)} u_n = u_n - P_{\mathcal{P}_1(\Omega)^{\perp}} u_n$, $u_n \in X^{\perp}$ and $\mathcal{P}_1(\Omega)^{\perp} \subset X^{\perp}$ by definition of X , we see that

$$P_{\mathcal{P}_1(\Omega)} u_n \in X^{\perp} \cap \mathcal{P}_1(\Omega) \quad \text{for every } n \in \mathbb{N} \quad (3.30)$$

In addition the restriction $K|_{X^{\perp} \cap \mathcal{P}_1(\Omega)}$ is injective, as

$$\mathcal{N}(K|_{X^{\perp} \cap \mathcal{P}_1(\Omega)}) = X^{\perp} \cap \mathcal{P}_1(\Omega) \cap \mathcal{N}(K) = X^{\perp} \cap X = \{0\}$$

In summary, we get that the operator

$$K|_{X^{\perp} \cap \mathcal{P}_1(\Omega)} : X^{\perp} \cap \mathcal{P}_1(\Omega) \longrightarrow \mathcal{R}(K|_{X^{\perp} \cap \mathcal{P}_1(\Omega)})$$

is a continuous, linear bijection between finite dimensional Hilbert spaces. Hence, also its inverse is linear and continuous. From this observation and (3.30), we infer the existence of a constant $C > 0$ with the property

$$\begin{aligned} \|P_{\mathcal{P}_1(\Omega)} u_n\|_{L^2(\Omega)} &= \|(K|_{X^{\perp} \cap \mathcal{P}_1(\Omega)})^{-1} K|_{X^{\perp} \cap \mathcal{P}_1(\Omega)} P_{\mathcal{P}_1(\Omega)} u_n\|_{L^2(\Omega)} \\ &\leq C \|K|_{X^{\perp} \cap \mathcal{P}_1(\Omega)} P_{\mathcal{P}_1(\Omega)} u_n\|_{L^2(\Omega)} \\ &= C \|KP_{\mathcal{P}_1(\Omega)} u_n\|_{L^2(\Omega)} \end{aligned}$$

which yields the estimate

$$\begin{aligned} \|P_{\mathcal{P}_1(\Omega)} u_n\|_{L^2(\Omega)} &\leq C \|KP_{\mathcal{P}_1(\Omega)} u_n\|_{L^2(\Omega)} \\ &\leq C (\|K\|_{\mathcal{L}(L^2(\Omega))} \|u_n - P_{\mathcal{P}_1(\Omega)} u_n\|_{L^2(\Omega)} + \|f\|_{L^2(\Omega)} + \|Ku_n - f\|_{L^2(\Omega)}) \end{aligned} \quad (3.31)$$

Utilizing (3.28), (3.29) and (3.31) the boundedness of $\{\|P_{\mathcal{P}_1(\Omega)} u_n\|_{L^2(\Omega)}\}_{n \in \mathbb{N}}$ is shown. Finally an application of the triangle inequality gives

$$\|u_n\|_{L^2(\Omega)} \leq \|u_n - P_{\mathcal{P}_1(\Omega)} u_n\|_{L^2(\Omega)} + \|P_{\mathcal{P}_1(\Omega)} u_n\|_{L^2(\Omega)}$$

where the right hand side is bounded by the previous discussion and again (3.29). Consequently $\{\|u_n\|_{L^2(\Omega)}\}_{n \in \mathbb{N}}$ is bounded as well. Hence we can extract a weakly convergent subsequence, which will also be denoted as $\{u_n\}_{n \in \mathbb{N}}$ with

$$u_n \rightharpoonup u^* \quad \text{in } L^2(\Omega) \text{ for some } u^* \in L^2(\Omega)$$

Since J_α is weakly lower semicontinuous on $L^2(\Omega)$ and $X^\perp \subset L^2(\Omega)$ is, as a convex and closed set, also weakly closed with respect to the usual $L^2(\Omega)$ -topology, we conclude

$$u^* \in \arg \min_{u \in X^\perp} J_\alpha(u)$$

Because of (3.27), $u^* \in X^\perp$ solves the problem (P) as well. If K is injective, then $J_\alpha(\cdot)$ is a sum of a convex and a strictly convex function. Hence $J_\alpha(\cdot)$ is strictly convex itself, which gives the uniqueness of a solution of (P) in that case. \square

Chapter 4

Choice of Regularization Parameters by Bilevel Optimization

This chapter is devoted to the optimal choice of the spatially varying regularization parameters

$$\boldsymbol{\alpha} \in C(\overline{\Omega}) \times C(\overline{\Omega})$$

in the TGV regularization problem (P). We again point out the fact, that the strategy, which we will propose for this task requires knowledge of the noise level

$$\sigma^2 := \|\eta\|_{L^2(\Omega)} > 0$$

Such parameter choice strategies are usually called *a-priori-choice strategies* in the inverse problems literature. For a detailed and classical account on inverse problems, including also on other parameter choice strategies for scalar weights, even where the noise level is unknown we refer to [EHN00] and [Vog02]. In order to find the distributed optimal parameters, at a first stage we will introduce a loss function, measuring optimality of a given reconstruction. Afterwards, this loss function will serve as an upper level objective in a bilevel minimization problem, where the constraints are given by the problem (P). The subsequent part of the chapter then focuses on existence of solutions for that bilevel problem in the function space, for which the key ingredient will be the Γ -convergence of the lower level problems. As the bilevel problem falls into the realm of mathematical programs with equilibrium constraints, which are notoriously hard to solve directly, we eventually approximate the non-smooth lower level problem by a differentiable problem. Finally, this smoothed problem serves as a starting point for the analysis in the next chapter. On the theoretical side, the last section also provides a proof for the consistency of the approximate smoothing step, i.e. the convergence behavior for vanishing smoothing parameters is investigated. Before starting our exposition, we briefly describe the terminology and assumptions for the current chapter.

Assumption 2. (On the current chapter)

1. The operator $K : L^2(\Omega) \rightarrow L^2(\Omega)$ is again linear and continuous.
2. The set of admissible parameters is denoted by $W_{ad} \subset \mathbb{V}$. The parameter space \mathbb{V} is a Banach space, which is continuously embedded into $L^2(\Omega) \times L^2(\Omega)$. W_{ad} is assumed to be convex and closed in the topology of \mathbb{V} .
3. We also assume, that there exist positive constants $0 < A \leq B$ with

$$\boldsymbol{\alpha}(x) \in [A, B] \times [A, B] \quad \text{for every } \boldsymbol{\alpha} \in W_{ad} \text{ and (almost) every } x \in \Omega$$

4. By $w \in L^\infty(\Omega \times \Omega)$ we denote a normalized, non-negative kernel function, i.e. $w(x, y) \geq 0$ for every pair $x, y \in \Omega$ and $\|w\|_{L^1(\Omega \times \Omega)} = 1$.

In the first part of the chapter we will, unless otherwise stated fix the configuration

$$\mathbb{V} := W^{1,p}(\Omega) \times W^{1,p}(\Omega) \quad \text{for some } p > 2 \text{ and dimension } n = 2.$$

which is due to the fact, that the objective $J_{\alpha}(\cdot)$ in problem (P) is only well defined for $\alpha \in C(\overline{\Omega}) \times C(\overline{\Omega})$ and $W^{1,p}(\Omega) \hookrightarrow C(\overline{\Omega})$ in the above regime.

4.1 The Upper Level Objective

To find optimal parameters in the TGV regularization problem, we simultaneously optimize over the spatially varying regularization parameter and the image itself. A natural approach to do so requires a loss function

$$\mathcal{J} : BV(\Omega) \times \mathbb{V} \rightarrow [0, \infty) \quad (u, \alpha) \mapsto \mathcal{J}(u, \alpha)$$

which indicates, whether a given reconstruction $u = u(\alpha) \in BV(\Omega)$ is sufficiently good, corresponding to small $\mathcal{J}(u, \alpha)$ or unsatisfactory, resulting in large $\mathcal{J}(u, \alpha)$.

A pair $(u(\alpha), \alpha) \in BV(\Omega) \times W_{ad}$ of parameter and reconstruction is then defined to be optimal with respect to the loss function $\mathcal{J}(\cdot, \cdot)$, if it solves the following optimization problem:

$$\begin{aligned} & \min_{(u, \alpha) \in L^2(\Omega) \times W_{ad}} \mathcal{J}(u, \alpha) \\ \text{subject to } & u \in \operatorname{argmin}_{u \in L^2(\Omega)} \frac{1}{2} \|Ku - f\|_{L^2(\Omega)}^2 + TGV_{\alpha}^2(u) \end{aligned}$$

In a series of papers [DHRC11], [HW15], [HR17], [HRWL17] and [HPRS20], the authors developed a bilevel framework including an upper level objective, which does not require knowledge of the true clean image, but is able to still satisfactorily measure the quality of a given reconstruction. In practice it even turns out, that solving this bilevel minimization problem leads to reconstructions, which are often close to optimal with respect to classical quality measures like SSIM and PSNR, see also [HP19] for a nice overview article on this. We will briefly review, how this upper level objective is designed. For that purpose, we introduce the so called *localized residual* $R : L^2(\Omega) \rightarrow L^{\infty}(\Omega)$ defined by

$$R(u)(x) := \int_{\Omega} w(x, y) (Ku(y) - f(y))^2 dy$$

where $w \in L^{\infty}(\Omega \times \Omega)$ is a normalized, non-negative kernel function, i.e. $w(\cdot, \cdot) \geq 0$ and

$$\int_{\Omega \times \Omega} w(x, y) dx dy = 1$$

Indeed we observe, that under these conditions $R(\cdot)$ maps from $L^2(\Omega)$ to $L^{\infty}(\Omega)$ since

$$|R(u)(x)| \leq \|w\|_{L^{\infty}(\Omega \times \Omega)} \|Ku - f\|_{L^2(\Omega)}^2 < \infty \quad \text{independently of } x \in \Omega$$

The value $R(u)(x)$ can be interpreted as a local variance at the point $x \in \Omega$. Consequently, if a given reconstructed image

$$u = u(\alpha) \in BV(\Omega)$$

is close to u_{true} at the point x , we expect that the local residual mainly consists of pure noise, i.e. $R(u)(x) \approx \sigma(x)^2$. Vice versa, if u is far away from u_{true} at x , also $R(u)(x)$ will probably be far away from $\sigma(x)^2$. Due to sake of simplicity we only assume constant variance $\sigma^2(x) = \sigma^2 \in \mathbb{R}$ over the whole image. However, this does not mean any loss of generality in the theory.

The strategy is now, to penalize localized residuals which lie outside a tight variance corridor

$$[\underline{\sigma}^2, \overline{\sigma}^2] := [\sigma^2 - \varepsilon, \sigma^2 + \varepsilon] \subset (0, \infty)$$

around the known variance σ^2 , where the small parameter $\varepsilon > 0$ will be determined later by statistical considerations. The penalty term, which 'punishes' those localized residuals, that are outside this tight variance corridor is then simply given by $F : L^2(\Omega) \rightarrow [0, +\infty)$

$$F(r) := \frac{1}{2} \int_{\Omega} \max(r(x) - \bar{\sigma}^2, 0)^2 dx + \frac{1}{2} \int_{\Omega} \min(r(x) - \underline{\sigma}^2, 0)^2 dx$$

Note that the square inside the integral is due to differentiability purposes. Consequently, the corresponding bilevel optimization problem reads

$$\begin{aligned} \min_{(u, \alpha) \in L^2(\Omega) \times W_{ad}} \mathcal{J}(u, \alpha) &:= F \circ R(u) + \frac{\lambda}{p} \left(\|\alpha_0\|_{W^{1,p}(\Omega)}^p + \|\alpha_1\|_{W^{1,p}(\Omega)}^p \right) & (\mathbb{P}_{\text{orig}}) \\ \text{s.t. } u \in \operatorname{argmin}_{u \in L^2(\Omega)} J_{\alpha}(u) &= \frac{1}{2} \|Ku - f\|_{L^2(\Omega)}^2 + TGV_{\alpha}^2(u) \end{aligned}$$

The regularization term in the upper level objective

$$\alpha \mapsto \frac{\lambda}{p} \left(\|\alpha_0\|_{W^{1,p}(\Omega)}^p + \|\alpha_1\|_{W^{1,p}(\Omega)}^p \right)$$

for $p > 2$ forces the regularization parameters to lie in the space $W^{1,p}(\Omega) \times W^{1,p}(\Omega)$, for which we have the continuous (and even compact) embedding

$$W^{1,p}(\Omega) \times W^{1,p}(\Omega) \hookrightarrow C(\bar{\Omega}) \times C(\bar{\Omega})$$

in dimension $n = 2$. As we already said, this is necessary to make the lower level problem well defined. Later in the chapter, when smoothing the lower level problem, we will relax these assumptions towards $p = 2$, which also gives the advantage of being in a Hilbert space setting. The following theorem investigates differentiability properties of the upperlevel objective. This is essential for deriving existence of solutions for $(\mathbb{P}_{\text{orig}})$ and also for the derivation of a first order optimality system later on.

Theorem 22 (Properties of the upper level objective). *Consider a normalized weight $w \in L^{\infty}(\Omega \times \Omega)$ as in Assumption 2. Then it holds:*

1. *The function $\mathcal{F} := F \circ R : L^2(\Omega) \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$, defined as above is continuously Frechét-differentiable and the derivative is given by*

$$D\mathcal{F}(u)[v] = 2 \int_{\Omega} W^{tr} \left[(R(u) - \bar{\sigma}^2)_+ - (\underline{\sigma}^2 - R(u))_+ \right] (y) (Ku - f)(y) Kv(y) dy$$

where $W^{tr} \in \mathcal{L}(L^1(\Omega), L^{\infty}(\Omega))$ is defined as in (4.3).

2. *The upperlevel objective $\mathcal{J} : L^2(\Omega) \times \mathbb{V} \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ is continuous for $p > 2$ and continuously Frechét-differentiable for $p = 2$.*

Proof. We start proving the first claim of the theorem.

First consider the superposition operator

$$\Phi : L^2(\Omega) \rightarrow L^1(\Omega) \quad \Phi(u)(x) := u(x)^2 \tag{4.1}$$

It easily be seen by the theory of superposition operators, cf. [GKT92] that the operator in (4.1) is continuously differentiable with derivative in each direction $v \in L^2(\Omega)$ given by

$$D\Phi(u)[v](x) := 2u(x)v(x)$$

Moreover define the linear integral operator

$$W : L^1(\Omega) \rightarrow L^\infty(\Omega) \quad Wu(x) := \int_{\Omega} w(x, y) u(y) dy \quad (4.2)$$

which indeed maps all of $L^1(\Omega)$ into $L^\infty(\Omega)$ by the inequality:

$$|Wu(x)| \leq \|w\|_{L^\infty(\Omega \times \Omega)} \|u\|_{L^1(\Omega)}$$

Consequently it holds $\|W\|_{\mathcal{L}} \leq \|w\|_{L^\infty(\Omega \times \Omega)}$. Moreover we have $R(u) = W \circ \Phi(Ku - f)$, which together with the chainrule implies

$$DR(u)[v](x) := W D\Phi(Ku - f)[Kv](x) = 2 \int_{\Omega} w(x, y)(Ku - f)(y) Kv(y) dy$$

With a similar argumentation we see, that the penalty term $F : L^2(\Omega) \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ is also continuously Frechét-differentiable with derivative

$$DF(v)[w] := \int_{\Omega} [(v - \bar{\sigma}^2)_+ - (\underline{\sigma}^2 - v)_+] w dx$$

Eventually, we again use the chainrule to obtain

$$\begin{aligned} D\mathcal{F}(u)[v] &= 2 \int_{\Omega} [(R(u) - \bar{\sigma}^2)_+(x) - (\underline{\sigma}^2 - R(u))_+(x)] \int_{\Omega} w(x, y)(Ku - f)(y) Kv(y) dy dx \\ &= 2 \int_{\Omega} W^{tr} [(R(u) - \bar{\sigma}^2)_+ - (\underline{\sigma}^2 - R(u))_+](y) (Ku - f)(y) Kv(y) dy \end{aligned}$$

where the last line is a consequence of Fubinis theorem. Moreover, we used the linear operator

$$W^{tr} : L^1(\Omega) \rightarrow L^\infty(\Omega) \quad Wu(x) := \int_{\Omega} w(x, y) u(y) dy \quad (4.3)$$

which corresponds to the adjoint of $W \in \mathcal{L}(L^2(\Omega))$, when considering both W, W^{tr} as operators from $L^2(\Omega)$ to $L^2(\Omega)$.

The remaining part of the proof is obvious. \square

Remark 3. It can be easily checked that the function $F(\cdot)$ from above is convex. However, the composition $\mathcal{F} = F \circ R(\cdot)$ is in general non convex and standard arguments to show weak lower semicontinuity of $\mathcal{F}(\cdot)$ can not be applied. Indeed, the following simple example even shows that under the conditions in Assumption 2 neither convexity nor weak lower semicontinuity of $\mathcal{F}(\cdot)$ can in general be expected. Consider therefore $\Omega = [0, 1]$, $f = 0 \in L^2(\Omega)$, $K = Id \in \mathcal{L}(L^2(\Omega))$ and arbitrary $\sigma^2 > 0$ together with fixed positive numbers $0 < \bar{\sigma}^2 < \underline{\sigma}^2$ as described above. Moreover define the most simple kernel function

$$w : L^2([0, 1] \times [0, 1]) \rightarrow [0, 1] \quad w(x, y) = 1$$

To see that $\mathcal{F} : L^2(\Omega) \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ is not convex in this setting, introduce the constant functions $u_i \in L^2(\Omega)$ by

$$u_0(x) = \sigma \quad \text{and} \quad u_1(x) = -\sigma$$

Obviously it holds

$$R(u_i)(x) = \int_{[0, 1]} u_i(x)^2 dx = \sigma^2 \quad \text{for every } x \in \Omega \text{ and } i = 0, 1.$$

and consequently $\mathcal{F}(u_0) = \mathcal{F}(u_1) = 0$, which results in

$$\mathcal{F}\left(\frac{u_0 + u_1}{2}\right) = \mathcal{F}(0) = \frac{1}{2}\sigma^4 > 0 = \frac{1}{2}\mathcal{F}(u_0) + \frac{1}{2}\mathcal{F}(u_1)$$

Hence $\mathcal{F}(\cdot)$ is not convex.

To show, that $\mathcal{F} : L^2(\Omega) \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ is not weakly lower semicontinuous, we consider further a countable orthonormal basis $(v_n)_{n \in \mathbb{N}}$ of $L^2(\Omega)$. This means that the following two conditions are satisfied

$$\langle v_n, v_m \rangle_{L^2(\Omega)} = \begin{cases} 1 & \text{if } n = m \\ 0 & \text{else} \end{cases} \quad (4.4)$$

$$\|u\|_{L^2(\Omega)}^2 = \sum_{n \in \mathbb{N}} |\langle v_n, u \rangle_{L^2(\Omega)}|^2 \quad \text{for every } u \in L^2(\Omega) \quad (4.5)$$

The second equation is also known as Parsevals identity. For countable orthonormal systems in general Hilbert spaces and the theory behind, we refer to [Bre10]. We then set

$$u_n := \sigma v_n$$

From (4.4) and (4.5) we directly obtain the properties

$$u_n \rightharpoonup 0 \quad \text{weakly in } L^2(\Omega) \quad (4.6)$$

$$R(u_n)(x) = \sigma^2 \|v_n\|_{L^2(\Omega)}^2 = \sigma^2 \quad \text{for every } n \in \mathbb{N} \quad (4.7)$$

and therefore also $\mathcal{F}(u_n) = 0$ for every $n \in \mathbb{N}$ and consequently

$$\liminf_{n \rightarrow \infty} \mathcal{F}(u_n) = 0 < \frac{1}{2} \sigma^4 = \mathcal{F}(0) \quad (4.8)$$

As $u_n \rightharpoonup 0$ in $L^2(\Omega)$, the loss function $\mathcal{F}(\cdot)$ cannot be weakly lower semicontinuous.

4.2 Gamma-Convergence of the Lower Level Objectives

Our goal in this section is to prove existence of solutions for $(\mathbb{P}_{\text{orig}})$. When applying the direct method of calculus of variations, we are facing some difficulties, which we want to point out briefly without being too rigorous with the notation:

Consider an infimizing sequence $\{u_n, \alpha_n\}_{n \in \mathbb{N}} \subseteq L^2(\Omega) \times W_{ad}$. Assume further that we can somehow extract a weakly convergent subsequence, denoted the same, with $(u_n, \alpha_n) \rightharpoonup (u^*, \alpha^*)$.

Then two questions immediately come up

1. Is $(u^*, \alpha^*) \in L^2(\Omega) \times W_{ad}$ again a feasible point, i.e. does $u^* \in L^2(\Omega)$ solve (P) for the parameter α^* ?
2. The mapping $u \mapsto F \circ R(u)$ is non-convex, see Remark 3. Therefore classical lower semicontinuity arguments will not apply and we need strong convergence of the infimizing sequence. How can we ensure strong $L^2(\Omega)$ -convergence in the absence of suitable compact embeddings? Recall, that $BV(\Omega)$ does not embed compactly into $L^2(\Omega)$ in dimensions $n \geq 2$, cf. Theorem 7.

The first question is clearly connected to the concept of Γ -convergence of functionals. We briefly recall the definition and the most important property for our purpose. For a detailed account on this extensive subject, we again refer to [BMA06].

Definition 11 (Γ -convergence). *Let (X, τ) be a Hausdorff space and let $F_n, F : X \rightarrow \mathbb{R} \cup \{+\infty\}$ be functions with values in the extended reals. Then we call*

$$F = \Gamma - \lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} F_n$$

the (sequential) Γ -limit of the sequence $\{F_n\}_{n \in \mathbb{N}}$, if the following two conditions are satisfied

1. For every sequence $(u_n)_{n \in \mathbb{N}}$ with $u_n \rightarrow u$, the so called liminf inequality holds true:

$$F(u) \leq \liminf_{n \rightarrow \infty} F_n(u_n)$$

2. For every $u \in X$, there is a so called recovery sequence $(u_n)_{n \in \mathbb{N}}$ with $u_n \rightarrow u$ and

$$F(u) \geq \limsup_{n \rightarrow \infty} F_n(u_n)$$

In cases, where the topology and the spaces are obvious we write

$$F_n \xrightarrow{\Gamma} F \quad \text{as } n \rightarrow \infty$$

The reason, why Γ -convergence is the key tool to address the first question from above is provided by the following theorem

Theorem 23 (Basic properties of Γ -convergence). *Let $F_n, F : X \rightarrow \mathbb{R} \cup \{+\infty\}$ where again (X, τ) denotes a topological Hausdorff space and let $F = \Gamma - \lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} F_n$. Then the following statement holds true:*

If $u_n \in X$, such that $F_n(u_n) = \inf_{u \in X} F_n(u)$, i.e. $u_n \in X$ minimizes $F_n(\cdot)$ and $\{u_n\}_{n \in \mathbb{N}}$ is itself relatively compact. Then every clusterpoint $u^ \in X$ of $\{u_n\}_{n \in \mathbb{N}}$ is a minimizer of $F(\cdot)$ and*

$$\lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} F_n(u_n) = F(u^*)$$

Proof. The proof can be found in [BMA06]. □

The preceding theorem basically states that the limit of a sequence $u_n \in X$ of minimizers of functionals $F_n : X \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ is again a minimizer of their Γ -limit $F : X \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$. This is exactly what we need to answer the question whether a possible limit point of a convergent infimizing sequence is again a solution of (P). In order to use Theorem 23 for our purposes, we will now prove the Γ -convergence of the lower level functionals. This is done in several steps. We begin with a measure theoretic lemma.

Lemma 3. *Fix $X \in \{\mathbb{R}^n, \mathbb{R}_{sym}^{n \times n}\}$. Let $f_n, f \in C(\Omega)$, with $f(x) \geq 0$ for every $x \in \Omega$. Moreover let $\mu, \mu_n \in \mathcal{M}(\Omega; X)$ denote Radon measures, such that*

$$\mu_n \xrightarrow{*} \mu \quad \text{in } \mathcal{M}(\Omega; X) \tag{4.9}$$

$$f_n \rightarrow f \quad \text{in } C(\Omega) \tag{4.10}$$

Then the following inequality is satisfied

$$\liminf_{n \rightarrow \infty} \int_{\Omega} f_n \, d|\mu_n| \geq \int_{\Omega} f \, d|\mu|$$

Proof. The assertion follows from the inequality

$$\liminf_{n \rightarrow \infty} \int_{\Omega} f_n \, d|\mu_n| \geq \liminf_{n \rightarrow \infty} \int_{\Omega} (f_n - f) \, d|\mu_n| + \liminf_{n \rightarrow \infty} \int_{\Omega} f \, d|\mu_n| \tag{4.11}$$

The first term on the righthand side of the last inequality goes to zero as

$$\left| \int_{\Omega} (f_n - f) \, d|\mu_n| \right| \leq \|f_n - f\|_{C(\Omega)} \sup_{n \in \mathbb{N}} \|\mu_n\|_{\mathcal{M}(\Omega; X)} \rightarrow 0 \tag{4.12}$$

Note for (4.12), that

$$\sup_{n \in \mathbb{N}} \|\mu_n\|_{\mathcal{M}(\Omega; X)} < \infty$$

by (4.9) and the uniform boundedness principle. For the second term on the righthand side of (4.11) we use Theorem 6 from chapter 2, which leads to the equation

$$\int_{\Omega} f \, d|\mu_n| = \|f \cdot \mu_n\|_{\mathcal{M}(\Omega; X)}$$

with $f \cdot \mu_n \in \mathcal{M}(\Omega; X)$ denotes the vector measure defined as in chapter 2. By exploiting

$$\langle f \cdot \mu_n, \varphi \rangle_{C_0^*, C_0} = \langle \mu_n, f \varphi \rangle_{C_0^*, C_0} \quad \text{for every } \varphi \in C_0(\Omega; X)$$

it's easy to verify that also $f \cdot \mu_n \xrightarrow{*} f \cdot \mu$. Consequently the weak* sequential lower semi-continuity of $\mu \mapsto \|\mu\|_{\mathcal{M}(\Omega; X)}$ implies

$$\liminf_{n \rightarrow \infty} \int_{\Omega} f \, d|\mu_n| = \liminf_{n \rightarrow \infty} \|f \cdot \mu_n\|_{\mathcal{M}(\Omega; X)} \geq \|f \cdot \mu\|_{\mathcal{M}(\Omega; X)} = \int_{\Omega} f \, d|\mu|$$

which together with (4.12) proves the assertion. \square

The next theorem is the first part for proving the Γ -convergence of the lower level problems, precisely it provides the basis for the existence of a recovery-sequence. Moreover the statement is interesting in its own right, since it shows that $TGV_{\alpha}^2(\cdot)$ is stable with respect to small $C(\bar{\Omega}) \times C(\bar{\Omega})$ -perturbations in α .

Before proving the theorem, we have to fix some assumptions on sequences in $C(\bar{\Omega}) \times C(\bar{\Omega})$.

Assumption 3. (On sequences of continuous functions) For a sequence $\{\alpha_n\}_{n \in \mathbb{N}} \subset C(\bar{\Omega}) \times C(\bar{\Omega})$ we assume, that there exist positive constants $0 < A \leq B$ with

$$\alpha_n(x) \in [A, B] \times [A, B] \quad \text{for every } n \in \mathbb{N} \text{ and every } x \in \Omega$$

Under these assumptions, we can now present the proof for the stability theorem. Note, that similar results have been provided in [BH14] and the recent work [DFL19] in the case of constant regularization weights. Our proof strategy works similar as the one in [DFL19].

Theorem 24 (Stability of TGV with respect to α). *Let $\{\alpha_n\}_{n \in \mathbb{N}} \subset C(\bar{\Omega}) \times C(\bar{\Omega})$, such that Assumption 3 is satisfied and $\alpha_n \rightarrow \alpha$ in $C(\bar{\Omega}) \times C(\bar{\Omega})$. Then for every $u \in BV(\Omega)$*

$$TGV_{\alpha_n}^2(u) \rightarrow TGV_{\alpha}^2(u) \quad \text{as } n \rightarrow \infty$$

Proof. At first, we show the inequality

$$\liminf_{n \rightarrow \infty} TGV_{\alpha_n}^2(u) \geq TGV_{\alpha}^2(u) \quad (4.13)$$

Assume that (4.13) is not true. Then we may suppose, by possibly switching to a subsequence, that

$$\lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} TGV_{\alpha_n}^2(u) < TGV_{\alpha}^2(u) \quad (4.14)$$

Minding Theorem 18, we find elements $w_n \in BD(\Omega)$ with

$$TGV_{\alpha_n}^2(u) = \int_{\Omega} \alpha_{1,n} \, d|Du - w_n| + \int_{\Omega} \alpha_{0,n} \, d|\mathcal{E}w_n| \quad (4.15)$$

The same theorem yields the boundedness of the sequence $(w_n)_{n \in \mathbb{N}}$ in $BD(\Omega)$. To see this, consider

$$\begin{aligned} A \|Du - w_n\|_{\mathcal{M}(\Omega; \mathbb{R}^n)} + A \|\mathcal{E}w_n\|_{\mathcal{M}(\Omega; \mathbb{R}_{sym}^{n \times n})} &\leq \int_{\Omega} \alpha_{1,n} \, d|Du - w_n| + \int_{\Omega} \alpha_{0,n} \, d|\mathcal{E}w_n| \\ &\leq B \int_{\Omega} d|Du| \\ &< +\infty \end{aligned} \quad (4.16)$$

as $u \in BV(\Omega)$. In the last lines we also used the positive constants $0 < A, B$ from Assumption 3. From (4.16), we directly infer the boundedness of $(\mathcal{E}w_n)_n$ in $\mathcal{M}(\Omega; \mathbb{R}_{sym}^{n \times n})$. In addition, by

$$\|w_n\|_{L^1(\Omega; \mathbb{R}^n)} \leq \|Du - w_n\|_{\mathcal{M}(\Omega; \mathbb{R}^n)} + \|Du\|_{\mathcal{M}(\Omega; \mathbb{R}^n)}$$

we deduce the boundedness of $(w_n)_{n \in \mathbb{N}}$ in $BD(\Omega)$.

We now employ the weak*-compactness in $BD(\Omega)$ and (4.16), to find a subsequence, also denoted by $(w_n)_{n \in \mathbb{N}}$ and an element $w \in BD(\Omega)$ with

$$\begin{aligned} w_n &\rightarrow w \quad \text{in } L^1(\Omega; \mathbb{R}^n) \text{ as } n \rightarrow \infty. \\ \mathcal{E}w_n &\overset{*}{\rightharpoonup} \mathcal{E}w \quad \text{in } \mathcal{M}(\Omega; \mathbb{R}_{sym}^{n \times n}) \text{ as } n \rightarrow \infty. \end{aligned}$$

Now the desired estimate follows easily:

$$\begin{aligned} \liminf_{n \rightarrow \infty} TGV_{\alpha_n}^2(u) &\geq \liminf_{n \rightarrow \infty} \int_{\Omega} \alpha_{1,n} \, d|Du - w_n| + \liminf_{n \rightarrow \infty} \int_{\Omega} \alpha_{0,n} \, d|\mathcal{E}w_n| \\ &\geq \int_{\Omega} \alpha_1 \, d|Du - w| + \int_{\Omega} \alpha_0 \, d|\mathcal{E}w| \end{aligned} \quad (4.17)$$

$$\geq TGV_{\alpha}^2(u) \quad (4.18)$$

where (4.17) stems from Lemma 3 and from the fact, that $w_n \rightarrow w$ in $L^1(\Omega, \mathbb{R}^n)$ implies

$$(Du - w_n) \overset{*}{\rightharpoonup} (Du - w) \quad \text{in } \mathcal{M}(\Omega; \mathbb{R}^n)$$

Note that inequality (4.18) is a consequence of the minimum characterization in Theorem 18. This is a contradiction to (4.14) and therefore (4.13) has to hold true.

Now we prove the opposite inequality:

$$\limsup_{n \rightarrow \infty} TGV_{\alpha_n}^2(u) \leq TGV_{\alpha}^2(u) \quad (4.19)$$

For that purpose, we take again the $w \in BD(\Omega)$ from the minimum characterization of $TGV_{\alpha}(u)$ in Theorem 18, i.e.

$$TGV_{\alpha}^2(u) = \int_{\Omega} \alpha_1 \, d|Du - w| + \int_{\Omega} \alpha_0 \, d|\mathcal{E}w|$$

Applying the same theorem then yields

$$\begin{aligned} TGV_{\alpha_n}(u) &= \min_{w \in BD(\Omega)} \int_{\Omega} \alpha_{1,n} \, d|Du - w| + \int_{\Omega} \alpha_{0,n} \, d|\mathcal{E}w| \\ &\leq \int_{\Omega} \alpha_{1,n} \, d|Du - w| + \int_{\Omega} \alpha_{0,n} \, d|\mathcal{E}w| \end{aligned}$$

and by taking the the lim sup on both sides, inequality (4.19) can be shown:

$$\begin{aligned} \limsup_{n \rightarrow \infty} TGV_{\alpha_n}^2(u) &\leq \limsup_{n \rightarrow \infty} \int_{\Omega} \alpha_{1,n} \, d|Du - w| + \limsup_{n \rightarrow \infty} \int_{\Omega} \alpha_{0,n} \, d|\mathcal{E}w| \\ &= \int_{\Omega} \alpha_1 \, d|Du - w| + \int_{\Omega} \alpha_0 \, d|\mathcal{E}w| \\ &= TGV_{\alpha}^2(u) \end{aligned} \quad (4.20)$$

In order to understand the validity of the second equation in (4.20), the following two facts should also be verified. Their proof follows immediately from standard properties of the integral:

$$\begin{aligned} \lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \int_{\Omega} \alpha_{1,n} \, d|Du - w| &= \int_{\Omega} \alpha_1 \, d|Du - w| \\ \lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \int_{\Omega} \alpha_{0,n} \, d|\mathcal{E}w| &= \int_{\Omega} \alpha_0 \, d|\mathcal{E}w| \end{aligned}$$

Finally, by combining (4.13) and (4.19) the assertion of the theorem is proven. \square

The next theorem essentially shows the liminf inequality in the definition of the Γ -convergence.

Theorem 25 (liminf inequality for TGV). *Let again Assumption 3 hold true for a sequence $(\alpha_n)_n$ with $\alpha_n \rightarrow \alpha$ in $C(\overline{\Omega}) \times C(\overline{\Omega})$. Moreover take a sequence $(u_n)_n \subset L^2(\Omega)$ with $u_n \rightharpoonup u$ weakly in $L^2(\Omega)$. Then the following inequality is valid:*

$$\liminf_{n \rightarrow \infty} TGV_{\alpha_n}^2(u_n) \geq TGV_{\alpha}^2(u) \quad (4.21)$$

Proof. We distinguish two cases. Assume first, that $u \notin BV(\Omega)$. As $u \in L^2(\Omega)$, an application of Theorem 19 reveals that necessarily

$$TGV_{\alpha}^2(u) = +\infty \quad (4.22)$$

For inequality (4.21) to hold true, the following line must also be valid

$$\liminf_{n \rightarrow \infty} TGV_{\alpha_n}^2(u_n) = +\infty \quad (4.23)$$

We prove (4.23) by contradiction, i.e we may assume that after selection of a suitable subsequence it holds

$$\lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} TGV_{\alpha_n}^2(u_n) =: M < +\infty \quad (4.24)$$

for some finite value $M \in [0, \infty)$.

We now show, that $(u_n)_{n \in \mathbb{N}}$ is bounded in $BV(\Omega)$:

For that purpose, use the boundedness of the weakly convergent sequence

$$u_n \rightharpoonup u \quad \text{in } L^2(\Omega)$$

and the continuous embedding of $L^2(\Omega) \hookrightarrow L^1(\Omega)$ to see

$$\sup_{n \in \mathbb{N}} \|u_n\|_{L^1(\Omega)} \leq C_1 \sup_{n \in \mathbb{N}} \|u_n\|_{L^2(\Omega)} < +\infty \quad (4.25)$$

for some embedding constant $C_1 > 0$. A further application of the topological equivalence in Theorem 19 provides the desired estimate for $\|u_n\|_{BV(\Omega)}$:

$$\begin{aligned} \|u_n\|_{BV(\Omega)} &\leq C_2 \left(\|u_n\|_{L^1(\Omega)} + TGV_{(A,A)}(u_n) \right) \\ &\leq C_2 \left(\|u_n\|_{L^1(\Omega)} + TGV_{\alpha_n}(u_n) \right) \end{aligned} \quad (4.26)$$

For a constant $C_2 = C_2(A) > 0$ and the lower bound $A > 0$ from Assumption 3. Now the boundedness of the righthand side of (4.26) is clearly a consequence of (4.24) and (4.25). By the weak* compactness in $BV(\Omega)$ we find an $u^* \in BV(\Omega)$, such that (up to a subsequence) $u_n \overset{*}{\rightharpoonup} u^*$ in $BV(\Omega)$, i.e.

$$\begin{aligned} u_n &\rightarrow u^* \quad \text{in } L^1(\Omega) \\ Du_n &\overset{*}{\rightharpoonup} Du^* \quad \text{in } \mathcal{M}(\Omega; \mathbb{R}^n) \end{aligned}$$

Together with the weak convergence $u_n \rightharpoonup u$ in $L^2(\Omega)$ and consequently also $u_n \rightharpoonup u$ in $L^1(\Omega)$, we obtain

$$u = u^* \quad \text{in } BV(\Omega)$$

This is a contradiction to (4.22) by the aforementioned norm equivalence between $BGV^2(\Omega)$ and $BV(\Omega)$.

Consider now the other case $u \in BV(\Omega)$. We proceed again by contradiction and assume, that (4.21) is not satisfied, i.e after switching to a subsequence we have

$$\lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} TGV_{\alpha_n}^2(u_n) =: M < TGV_{\alpha}^2(u) < \infty \quad (4.27)$$

with some positive $M > 0$, which has nothing to do with the one from the first part of the proof. As $u \in BV(\Omega)$, we again infer $TGV_{\alpha}^2(u) < \infty$ from Theorem 19 and exactly like in the first part of this proof, we deduce that $(u_n)_{n \in \mathbb{N}}$ is bounded in $BV(\Omega)$, and that we may extract a subsequence (renamed) with

$$\begin{aligned} u_n &\rightarrow u && \text{in } L^1(\Omega) \\ Du_n &\overset{*}{\rightharpoonup} Du && \text{in } \mathcal{M}(\Omega; \mathbb{R}^n) \end{aligned} \quad (4.28)$$

Moreover, we use Theorem 18 to find elements $w_n \in BD(\Omega)$, such that

$$TGV_{\alpha_n}^2(u_n) = \int_{\Omega} \alpha_{1,n} d|Du_n - w_n| + \int_{\Omega} \alpha_{0,n} d|\mathcal{E}w_n|$$

And again by exploiting the minimum characterization of TGV and the constants $A, B > 0$ from Assumption 3 we deduce the estimate

$$A \|Du_n - w_n\|_{\mathcal{M}(\Omega; \mathbb{R}^n)} + A \|\mathcal{E}w_n\|_{\mathcal{M}(\Omega; \mathbb{R}_{sym}^{n \times n})} \leq \int_{\Omega} \alpha_{1,n} d|Du_n - w_n| + \int_{\Omega} \alpha_{0,n} d|\mathcal{E}w_n| \quad (4.29)$$

$$\leq B \int_{\Omega} d|Du_n| \quad (4.30)$$

$$\leq B \sup_{n \in \mathbb{N}} \|Du_n\|_{\mathcal{M}(\Omega; \mathbb{R}^n)} \quad (4.31)$$

$$< +\infty \quad (4.32)$$

where $\sup_n \|Du_n\|_{\mathcal{M}(\Omega; \mathbb{R}^n)} < \infty$ comes from (4.28) and the uniform boundedness principle. The preceding estimates, together with the inequality

$$\|w_n\|_{L^1(\Omega; \mathbb{R}^n)} \leq \|Du_n - w_n\|_{\mathcal{M}(\Omega; \mathbb{R}^n)} + \|Du_n\|_{\mathcal{M}(\Omega; \mathbb{R}^n)}$$

yield the boundedness of $\{\|w_n\|_{BD(\Omega)}\}_{n \in \mathbb{N}}$, which results in the extraction of a subsequence, also denoted by $(w_n)_{n \in \mathbb{N}}$ and an element $w \in BD(\Omega)$ with the properties

$$\begin{aligned} w_n &\rightarrow w && \text{in } L^1(\Omega; \mathbb{R}^n) \\ \mathcal{E}w_n &\overset{*}{\rightharpoonup} \mathcal{E}w && \text{in } \mathcal{M}(\Omega; \mathbb{R}_{sym}^{n \times n}) \end{aligned}$$

This is a consequence of the weak* compactness in $BD(\Omega)$. Finally the next inequality follows by Lemma 3 from the beginning of this section:

$$\begin{aligned} \liminf_{n \rightarrow \infty} TGV_{\alpha_n}(u_n) &\geq \liminf_{n \rightarrow \infty} \int_{\Omega} \alpha_{1,n} d|Du_n - w_n| + \liminf_{n \rightarrow \infty} \int_{\Omega} \alpha_{0,n} d|\mathcal{E}w_n| \\ &\geq \int_{\Omega} \alpha_1 d|Du - w| + \int_{\Omega} \alpha_0 d|\mathcal{E}w| \\ &\geq TGV_{\alpha}(u) \end{aligned}$$

where we used again the minimum characterization of TGV to infer the inequality in the last line. The above estimate is a contradiction to our assumption (4.27). Hence the assertion of the theorem is true. \square

The above results enable us to prove the Γ -convergence of the lower level functionals from the last chapter:

$$J_{\alpha_n}(u) = \frac{1}{2} \|Ku - f\|_{L^2(\Omega)}^2 + TGV_{\alpha_n}^2(u)$$

Theorem 26 (Γ -convergence of the lower level problems). *Let Assumption 3 hold true for a sequence with $\alpha_n \rightarrow \alpha$ in $C(\bar{\Omega}) \times C(\bar{\Omega})$. Then the following convergence result is valid*

$$J_{\alpha_n} \xrightarrow{\Gamma} J_{\alpha} \quad \text{with respect to the weak and strong } L^2(\Omega)\text{-topology.}$$

Proof. (Only for the weak topology, the other case is identical) The existence of a recovery sequence is clear: For a fixed $u \in L^2(\Omega)$, we take the sequence $(u_n)_{n \in \mathbb{N}}$ in $L^2(\Omega)$ which is constant $u_n := u$ for every $n \in \mathbb{N}$. By Theorem 24, we obtain $TGV_{\alpha_n}^2(u_n) \rightarrow TGV_{\alpha}^2(u)$ as $n \rightarrow \infty$ and directly from that

$$J_{\alpha_n}(u_n) = \frac{1}{2} \|Ku - f\|_{L^2(\Omega)}^2 + TGV_{\alpha_n}^2(u) \rightarrow \frac{1}{2} \|Ku - f\|_{L^2(\Omega)}^2 + TGV_{\alpha}^2(u) = J_{\alpha}(u)$$

Hence $(u_n)_{n \in \mathbb{N}}$ is a recovery sequence.

We go on with the liminf-inequality. Therefore take an arbitrary sequence $(u_n)_{n \in \mathbb{N}}$ in $L^2(\Omega)$, such that $u_n \rightharpoonup u$ weakly in $L^2(\Omega)$ to some $u \in L^2(\Omega)$. By Theorem 25, we immediately get the desired estimate

$$\begin{aligned} \liminf_{n \rightarrow \infty} J_{\alpha_n}(u_n) &\geq \liminf_{n \rightarrow \infty} \frac{1}{2} \|Ku_n - f\|_{L^2(\Omega)}^2 + \liminf_{n \rightarrow \infty} TGV_{\alpha_n}^2(u_n) \\ &\geq \frac{1}{2} \|Ku - f\|_{L^2(\Omega)}^2 + TGV_{\alpha}^2(u) \\ &= J_{\alpha}(u) \end{aligned}$$

where we used the obvious fact, that $u \mapsto \|Ku - f\|_{L^2(\Omega)}^2$ is weakly lower semi-continuous on $L^2(\Omega)$. In summary, we showed the existence of a recovery-sequence and the liminf-inequality. Together this implies the claim of the theorem. \square

Finally we are able to prove the existence of solutions of the original bilevel optimization problem $(\mathbb{P}_{\text{orig}})$.

Theorem 27 (Existence of solutions of the bilevel problem). *Let Assumption 2 be satisfied for $n = 2$ and the parameter space*

$$\mathbb{V} = W^{1,p}(\Omega) \times W^{1,p}(\Omega)$$

where we only allow exponents $p > 2$. In addition assume that the operator $K^*K \in \mathcal{L}(L^2(\Omega))$ is invertible. Then Problem $(\mathbb{P}_{\text{orig}})$ has at least one solution.

Proof. Take an infimizing sequence $(u_n, \alpha_n) \in L^2(\Omega) \times W_{ad}$, which always exists due to Theorem 21. The coercivity of the mapping

$$\alpha = (\alpha_0, \alpha_1) \mapsto \frac{\lambda}{p} \left(\|\alpha_0\|_{W^{1,p}(\Omega)}^p + \|\alpha_1\|_{W^{1,p}(\Omega)}^p \right)$$

on \mathbb{V} then yields the boundedness of $\{\|\alpha_{i,n}\|_{W^{1,p}(\Omega)}\}_{n \in \mathbb{N}}$ for each $i = 0, 1$. Therefore, by also exploiting the compact embedding $W^{1,p}(\Omega) \hookrightarrow C(\bar{\Omega})$ in dimension $n = 2$, we find an element $\alpha \in C(\bar{\Omega}) \times C(\bar{\Omega})$, which satisfies (up to a subsequence)

$$\begin{aligned} \alpha_n &\rightharpoonup \alpha \quad \text{weakly in } W^{1,p}(\Omega) \times W^{1,p}(\Omega) \\ \alpha_n &\rightarrow \alpha \quad \text{strongly in } C(\bar{\Omega}) \times C(\bar{\Omega}) \end{aligned}$$

Moreover, as the set $W_{ad} \subset \mathbb{V}$ is closed and convex in \mathbb{V} by Assumption 2, we deduce $\alpha \in W_{ad}$. We now show, that $(u_n)_n$ is bounded in $L^2(\Omega)$: First notice that Assumption 3 is satisfied for the sequence $\{\alpha_n\}_n$ as $\alpha_n \in W_{ad}$ for every $n \in \mathbb{N}$ and W_{ad} was assumed to satisfy Assumption 2. In addition the pair $(u_n, \alpha_n) \in L^2(\Omega) \times W_{ad}$ is feasible, which means, that $u_n \in L^2(\Omega)$ solves the lower level problem in (\mathbb{P}_{orig}) for every $n \in \mathbb{N}$. Consequently it holds

$$\frac{1}{2} \|Ku_n - f\|_{L^2(\Omega)}^2 + TGV_{\alpha_n}^2(u_n) \leq \frac{1}{2} \|f\|_{L^2(\Omega)}^2 \quad \text{for every } n \in \mathbb{N}$$

and since $K^*K \in \mathcal{L}(L^2(\Omega))$ is invertible, we also observe for arbitrary $u \in L^2(\Omega)$

$$\|u\|_{L^2(\Omega)} = \|(K^*K)^{-1}(K^*K)u\|_{L^2(\Omega)} \leq \|(K^*K)^{-1}\|_{\mathcal{L}(L^2(\Omega))} \|K^*Ku\|_{L^2(\Omega)}$$

Moreover, as $\|K^*Ku\|_{L^2(\Omega)} \leq C\|Ku\|_{L^2(\Omega)}$ for $C := \|K^*\|_{\mathcal{L}(L^2(\Omega))}$ we deduce

$$\|u\|_{L^2(\Omega)} \leq C \|(K^*K)^{-1}\|_{\mathcal{L}(L^2(\Omega))} \|Ku\|_{L^2(\Omega)}$$

and consequently by the triangle inequality

$$\|u\|_{L^2(\Omega)} \leq C \|(K^*K)^{-1}\|_{\mathcal{L}(L^2(\Omega))} (\|Ku - f\|_{L^2(\Omega)} + \|f\|_{L^2(\Omega)})$$

Minding the previous estimate, we directly infer the boundedness of $\{\|u_n\|_{L^2(\Omega)}\}_{n \in \mathbb{N}}$ and extract a subsequence, which satisfies (after renaming)

$$u_n \rightharpoonup u \quad \text{in } L^2(\Omega) \text{ and as } n \rightarrow \infty$$

for some element $u \in L^2(\Omega)$.

By Theorem 23 and Theorem 26, which states the Γ -convergence of the lower level problems, we deduce, that $u \in L^2(\Omega)$ solves the lower level problem

$$u \in \operatorname{argmin}_{v \in L^2(\Omega)} \frac{1}{2} \|Kv - f\|_{L^2(\Omega)}^2 + TGV_{\alpha}^2(v)$$

As discussed in the beginning of this chapter, $u \mapsto F \circ R(u)$ is not convex and also not weakly lower semicontinuous on $L^2(\Omega)$, but instead $L^2(\Omega)$ -continuous, cf. Theorem 22 and the example in Remark 3. To overcome this issue, we show strong convergence $u_n \rightarrow u$ in $L^2(\Omega)$. The latter can be done by looking at the first order optimality conditions of the lower level problems, which read

$$0 \in \partial J_{\alpha_n}(u_n) = K^*Ku_n - K^*f + \partial TGV_{\alpha_n}^2(u_n)$$

For the last line note that $u \mapsto \|Ku - f\|_{L^2(\Omega)}^2$ is convex, continuous and finite valued on $L^2(\Omega)$. Hence the sum-rule for subdifferentials is applicable since also $\operatorname{Dom}(TGV_{\alpha_n}^2) \neq \emptyset$, cf. Theorem 12. The first order condition is equivalent to $K^*f - K^*Ku_n \in \partial TGV_{\alpha_n}^2(u_n)$ for every $n \in \mathbb{N}$.

Setting $v_n := K^*f - K^*Ku_n$ and $v := K^*f - K^*Ku$, the subgradient-inequality yields

$$TGV_{\alpha_n}^2(u_n) + \langle v_n - v, u - u_n \rangle_{L^2(\Omega)} \leq TGV_{\alpha_n}^2(u) - \langle v, u - u_n \rangle_{L^2(\Omega)}$$

plugging in the definition of v and v_n , the last line reads

$$TGV_{\alpha_n}^2(u_n) + \|u - u_n\|_B^2 \leq TGV_{\alpha_n}^2(u) - \langle v, u - u_n \rangle_{L^2(\Omega)}$$

Here we used the norm $v \mapsto \|v\|_B^2 := \langle K^*Kv, v \rangle_{L^2(\Omega)}$, which is equivalent to the usual $L^2(\Omega)$ -norm, since K^*K is invertible. Taking the liminf on both sides of the inequality, we arrive at

$$\liminf_{n \rightarrow \infty} TGV_{\alpha_n}^2(u_n) + \|u - u_n\|_B^2 \leq \liminf_{n \rightarrow \infty} TGV_{\alpha_n}^2(u) - \langle v, u - u_n \rangle_{L^2(\Omega)}$$

which, by Theorem 24 and Theorem 25 results in

$$TGV_{\alpha}^2(u) + \liminf_{n \rightarrow \infty} \|u - u_n\|_B^2 \leq TGV_{\alpha}^2(u)$$

Using the aforementioned norm-equivalence, we eventually obtain the desired strong convergence $u_n \rightarrow u$ in $L^2(\Omega)$. By the continuity of $F \circ R : L^2(\Omega) \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ and the weak lower semicontinuity of

$$(\alpha_0, \alpha_1) \mapsto \frac{\lambda}{p} \left(\|\alpha_0\|_{W^{1,p}(\Omega)}^p + \|\alpha_1\|_{W^{1,p}(\Omega)}^p \right)$$

standard arguments now show, that the pair $(u, \alpha) \in L^2(\Omega) \times \mathbb{V}$ is a solution of $(\mathbb{P}_{\text{orig}})$. \square

4.3 The First Smoothing of the Bilevel Problem

The lower level problem in $(\mathbb{P}_{\text{orig}})$ is not differentiable. We will briefly explain, how this fact can be seen: In [HPRS20] it is shown, that for every $u \in L^2(\Omega)$ in the two dimensional setting $\Omega \subset \mathbb{R}^2$ it holds

$$TGV_{\alpha}^2(u) = \sup \left\{ \int_{\Omega} u \operatorname{div}^2 \varphi \, dx \mid \varphi \in K_{\alpha}^2(H_0^2(\operatorname{div}^2, \Omega)) \right\} \quad (4.33)$$

where the Banach space $H_0^2(\operatorname{div}^2, \Omega)$ is defined as the closure

$$H_0^2(\operatorname{div}^2, \Omega) := \overline{C_c^{\infty}(\Omega; \mathbb{R}_{sym}^{n \times n})}^{\|\cdot\|_{H^2(\operatorname{div}^2, \Omega)}}$$

with respect to the norm $\|\cdot\|_{H^2(\operatorname{div}^2, \Omega)}$, which is given by

$$\|p\|_{H^2(\operatorname{div}^2, \Omega)}^2 := \|p\|_{L^2(\Omega; \mathbb{R}_{sym}^{n \times n})}^2 + \|\operatorname{div} p\|_{L^2(\Omega; \mathbb{R}^n)}^2 + \|\operatorname{div}^2 p\|_{L^2(\Omega)}^2$$

This space $H_0^2(\operatorname{div}^2, \Omega)$ is a generalization of the well known space $H_0(\operatorname{div})$, which is used frequently in the theory of Navier Stokes equation and it can be shown that $H_0^2(\operatorname{div}^2, \Omega)$ consists of exactly those functions $p \in L^2(\Omega; \mathbb{R}_{sym}^{n \times n})$ whose distributional divergences up to order two are square integrable and satisfy some zero boundary conditions. For more information on that space and its properties, consult the recent works [HPRS20] and [BH15], but also the classical textbook [GR12] in which most of the properties on $H_0(\operatorname{div})$ can be generalized to the space $H_0^2(\operatorname{div}^2, \Omega)$.

Equation (4.33) can equivalently be written as the Fenchel-conjugate of an indicator function:

$$TGV_{\alpha}^2(u) = \mathcal{I}_{\operatorname{div}^2 K_{\alpha}^2(H_0^2(\operatorname{div}^2, \Omega))}^*(u) \quad (4.34)$$

and since the set $\operatorname{div}^2 K_{\alpha}^2(H_0^2(\operatorname{div}^2, \Omega))$ is closed in the $L^2(\Omega)$ topology, the indicator in the last equation is lower semicontinuous and we deduce from Theorem 11 in chapter 2, that

$$(TGV_{\alpha}^2)^*(u^*) = \mathcal{I}_{\operatorname{div}^2 K_{\alpha}^2(H_0^2(\operatorname{div}^2, \Omega))}^*(u^*) \quad (4.35)$$

for any $u^* \in L^2(\Omega)$. Once we have characterized the conjugate, we can immediately characterize also the subdifferential of the $TGV_{\alpha}^2(\cdot)$ functional:

Theorem 28. (Subdifferential of TGV) Fix the space dimension $n = 2$. Moreover, let $u \in L^2(\Omega)$ and $\alpha \in C(\overline{\Omega}) \times C(\overline{\Omega})$ satisfy Assumption 1, then

$u^* \in L^2(\Omega)$ is in the subdifferential $u^* \in \partial TGV_{\alpha}^2(u)$ if and only if $u \in BV(\Omega)$ and there is a $g \in K_{\alpha}^2(H_0^2(\operatorname{div}^2, \Omega))$ such that $\operatorname{div}^2 g = u^*$ in $L^2(\Omega)$ with

$$\int_{\Omega} u \operatorname{div}^2 g \, dx = TGV_{\alpha}^2(u)$$

Proof. From Theorem 12, we know that $u^* \in \partial TGV_{\alpha}^2(u)$ if and only if

$$(TGV_{\alpha}^2)^*(u^*) + TGV_{\alpha}^2(u) = \langle u^*, u \rangle_{L^2(\Omega)}$$

The latter equation together with (4.35) implies the assertion of the theorem. \square

With the help of the last theorem we derive the formula

$$\partial TGV_{\alpha}^2(0) = \operatorname{div}^2 K_{\alpha}^2(H_0^2(\operatorname{div}^2, \Omega))$$

where the righthand side is not single valued! Hence $TGV_{\alpha}^2(\cdot)$ is at least not differentiable at $0 \in L^2(\Omega)$. Thus, the constraints in $(\mathbb{P}_{\text{orig}})$, given there in form of the convex minimization problem (P) can be equivalently expressed by a variational inequality or by a subdifferential inclusion, but not by an equation. These kind of problems lead directly to the class of mathematical problems with equilibrium constraints (MPECS) in infinite dimensions, for which the standard KKT theory in [ZK79] is known to fail and other methods need to be consulted to derive first order conditions. We will not go further into detail on MPECS, as especially in infinite dimensions the field of MPECS turns out to be a very delicate subject, which is out of the scope of this thesis. Instead we refer to the recent work [HK09] and the references therein.

To implement a solution algorithm in spite of the difficulties described above, we will replace the lower level Problem in $(\mathbb{P}_{\text{orig}})$ by a smoothed version of it. The methodology we use, combines an elliptic regularization, which lifts the regularity of the minimizer to the Hilbert space $H^1(\Omega)$ with a Huber type smoothing of the related Radon norms. The functional below was recently proposed in [HPRS20], but similar techniques have also been employed in [RSV17], [RSV16], [RS13] and earlier in [HS06] in the context of TV regularization. Following those works, we introduce the regularized lower level problem

$$\min_{(u,w) \in H^1(\Omega) \times H^1(\Omega; \mathbb{R}^n)} J_{\alpha}^{\gamma, \epsilon}(u, w) \quad (P_{\alpha}^{\gamma, \epsilon})$$

where the objective $J_{\alpha}^{\gamma, \epsilon} : H^1(\Omega) \times H^1(\Omega; \mathbb{R}^n) \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ is defined as

$$J_{\alpha}^{\gamma, \epsilon}(u, w) := \frac{1}{2} \|Ku - f\|_{L^2(\Omega)}^2 + \epsilon(u, w) + \int_{\Omega} \alpha_1 \varphi_{\gamma}(\nabla u - w) dx + \int_{\Omega} \alpha_0 \varphi_{\gamma}(\mathcal{E}w) dx$$

and the elliptic regularization $\epsilon : H^1(\Omega) \times H^1(\Omega; \mathbb{R}^n) \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ is given by

$$\epsilon(u, w) := \frac{\mu_K}{2} \|u\|_{L^2(\Omega)}^2 + \frac{\mu}{2} \|\nabla u\|_{L^2(\Omega)}^2 + \frac{\eta}{2} \|w\|_{H^1(\Omega; \mathbb{R}^n)}^2$$

Here we choose the regularization parameter $\mu_K \geq 0$, which will be set later depending on the operator K . The necessity of that additional smoothing parameter will become fully clear in the subsequent part, where we want to differentiate the solution map of the above problem. The other parameters $\gamma, \mu, \eta > 0$ are always positive.

By $\varphi_{\gamma} : X \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ we denote the Moreau-Yosida regularization of the finite dimensional $|\cdot|_2$ -norm on $X \in \{\mathbb{R}^n, \mathbb{R}_{sym}^{n \times n}\}$, sometimes also called Huber function [Hub64].

$$\varphi_{\gamma}(x) := \inf_{y \in \mathbb{R}^n} |y|_2 + \frac{\gamma}{2} |x - y|_2^2 = \begin{cases} |x|_2 - \frac{\gamma}{2} & \text{if } |x|_2 \geq \gamma \\ \frac{1}{2\gamma} |x|_2^2 & \text{if } |x|_2 < \gamma \end{cases} \quad (4.36)$$

The Huber function smoothes the norm-function in a very small area around the origin, see Figure 4.1. Its gradient is continuous and can be calculated from the formula

$$h_{\gamma} := \nabla \varphi_{\gamma} : X \rightarrow X \quad h_{\gamma}(x) = \frac{x}{\max(\gamma, |x|_2)} \quad (4.37)$$

The finite dimensional space $X \in \{\mathbb{R}^n, \mathbb{R}_{sym}^{n \times n}\}$ is again endowed with its usual Hilbert space structure as in chapter 2 and again we do not distinguish in the notation between the two possible cases for the space X . To clarify questions like existence of solutions of the regularized lower level problem and the corresponding bilevel optimization problem later on, we initially need a thorough investigation of the functional analytic properties of the objective $J_{\alpha}^{\gamma, \epsilon}(\cdot)$. In particular the term involving the Huber function needs some studies. For this reason we first define

$$\|\cdot\|_{L^1(\Omega; X), \gamma, \alpha} : L^2(\Omega; X) \rightarrow \overline{\mathbb{R}} \quad u \mapsto \int_{\Omega} \alpha \varphi_{\gamma}(u) dx$$

for some function $\alpha \in L^2(\Omega)$. The operator above can be seen as a smoothed and weighted $L^1(\Omega)$ norm. Exploiting some standard results on the properties of the Moreau-Yosida regularization, which can be found for example in [BC11], we obtain the equivalent characterization

$$\varphi_{\gamma}(x) = \left(|x|_2^* + \frac{\gamma}{2} |x|_2^2 \right)^* (x) = \left(\mathcal{I}_{\{x: |x|_2 \leq 1\}}(\cdot) + \frac{\gamma}{2} |x|_2^2 \right)^* (x)$$

Minding [BMA06], theorem 9.3.3 or [HM70], theorem 2.14 convex conjugation and integration commute and we deduce the equivalent representation

$$\|u\|_{L^1(\Omega), \gamma, \alpha} = \sup_{\substack{v \in L^2(\Omega, X) \\ \|v\|_{L^\infty(\Omega, X)} \leq 1}} \int_{\Omega} \alpha u \cdot v dx - \frac{\gamma}{2} \int_{\Omega} \alpha |v|_2^2 dx \quad (4.38)$$

The expression in (4.38) motivates the following definition, which is a smoothed and weighted Radon norm with weight $\alpha \in C_b(\Omega)$:

$$\|\cdot\|_{\mathcal{M}(\Omega; X), \alpha, \gamma} : \mathcal{M}(\Omega; X) \rightarrow \overline{\mathbb{R}} \quad \|\mu\|_{\mathcal{M}(\Omega; X), \alpha, \gamma} := \sup_{\substack{v \in C_0(\Omega, X) \\ \|v\|_{L^\infty(\Omega, X)} \leq 1}} \int_{\Omega} \alpha v d\mu - \frac{\gamma}{2} \int_{\Omega} \alpha |v|_2^2 dx \quad (4.39)$$

By standard density arguments, we clearly have $\|u\|_{L^1(\Omega), \gamma, \alpha} = \|\mu\|_{\mathcal{M}(\Omega; X), \alpha, \gamma}$ for $u \in L^1(\Omega; X)$ and it can be shown, that

$$\|\mu\|_{\mathcal{M}(\Omega; X), \alpha, \gamma} = \int_{\Omega} \alpha \varphi_{\gamma}(f) dx + \int_{\Omega} \alpha d|\mu^s| \quad (4.40)$$

where $\mu = f\mathcal{L}^n + \mu^s$ is the Lebesgue decomposition of $\mu \in \mathcal{M}(\Omega; X)$ with respect to the lebesgue measure \mathcal{L}^n , $\mu^s \in \mathcal{M}(\Omega; X)$ is the singular part of that decomposition and $f : \Omega \rightarrow X$ is the density of the absolute continuous part. The above statement and much more on the theory of functions of measures can be found in [DT84]. Thanks to the smoothing of the Radon norms, we are now able to provide a simple first order characterization of minimizers of $(P_{\alpha}^{\gamma, \epsilon})$.

Figure 4.1: Graphs of the Huber function and its derivative in dimension one.

Theorem 29. (First order optimality conditions) Choose the parameter space $\mathbb{V} = L^2(\Omega) \times L^2(\Omega)$ and $\alpha \in W_{ad}$ as in Assumption 2. Then the following statement is true:

$x^* = (u^*, w^*) \in H^1(\Omega) \times H^1(\Omega; \mathbb{R}^n)$ is a solution of $(P_\alpha^{\gamma, \epsilon})$ if and only if x^* solves the operator equation $g_\gamma(x^*, \alpha) = 0$ in $H^1(\Omega)^* \times H^1(\Omega; \mathbb{R}^n)^*$.

where the operator $g_\gamma(\cdot, \alpha) : H^1(\Omega) \times H^1(\Omega; \mathbb{R}^n) \rightarrow H^1(\Omega)^* \times H^1(\Omega; \mathbb{R}^n)^*$ is defined by

$$\begin{aligned} g_\gamma(x, \alpha)[v] := & \langle K^*Ku - K^*f, v_1 \rangle_{L^2} + \mu_K \langle u, v_1 \rangle_{L^2} + \mu \langle \nabla u, \nabla v_1 \rangle_{L^2} + \eta \langle w, v_2 \rangle_{H^1} \\ & + \int_{\Omega} \alpha_1 h_\gamma(\nabla u - w) \cdot (\nabla v_1 - v_2) \, dx + \int_{\Omega} \alpha_0 h_\gamma(\mathcal{E}w) \cdot \mathcal{E}v_2 \, dx \end{aligned} \quad (4.41)$$

For $(v_1, v_2) \in H^1(\Omega) \times H^1(\Omega; \mathbb{R}^n)$.

Proof. (Of Theorem 29) Note, that $J_\alpha^{\gamma, \epsilon} : H^1(\Omega) \times H^1(\Omega; \mathbb{R}^n) \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ can be written as

$$J_\alpha^{\gamma, \epsilon}(x) = F(x) + G(\Lambda x)$$

with functions $F : H^1(\Omega) \times H^1(\Omega; \mathbb{R}^n) \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$, $G : L^2(\Omega; \mathbb{R}^n) \times L^2(\Omega; \mathbb{R}_{sym}^{n \times n})$ and the continuous, linear operator $\Lambda \in \mathcal{L}(H^1(\Omega) \times H^1(\Omega; \mathbb{R}^n); L^2(\Omega; \mathbb{R}^n) \times L^2(\Omega; \mathbb{R}_{sym}^{n \times n}))$ and

$$\begin{aligned} F(x) := & \frac{1}{2} \|Ku - f\|_{L^2(\Omega)}^2 + \frac{\mu_1}{2} \|u\|_{L^2(\Omega)}^2 + \frac{\mu}{2} \|\nabla u\|_{L^2(\Omega)}^2 + \frac{\eta}{2} \|w\|_{H^1(\Omega; \mathbb{R}^n)}^2 \\ G(y) := & + \int_{\Omega} \alpha_1 \varphi_\gamma(p) \, dx + \int_{\Omega} \alpha_0 \varphi_\gamma(q) \, dx \\ \Lambda x := & \begin{bmatrix} \nabla & -id \\ 0 & \mathcal{E} \end{bmatrix} \cdot \begin{pmatrix} u \\ w \end{pmatrix} \end{aligned}$$

For the definition of these operators, we again used the notation $x = (u, w) \in H^1(\Omega) \times H^1(\Omega; \mathbb{R}^n)$ and $y = (p, q) \in L^2(\Omega; \mathbb{R}^n) \times L^2(\Omega; \mathbb{R}_{sym}^{n \times n})$. From this representation, we directly deduce the convexity of $J_\alpha^{\gamma, \epsilon}(\cdot)$ as $F(\cdot)$ and $G(\cdot)$ are convex itself and Λ is linear. Exploiting the differentiability of the involved norms, we then get the partial (Frechét-) differentials $D_1F(x) \in H^1(\Omega)^*$ and $D_2F(x) \in H^1(\Omega; \mathbb{R}^n)^*$ by

$$\begin{aligned} \langle D_1F(x), v_1 \rangle_{(H^1)^*, H^1} &= \langle K^*Ku - K^*f, v_1 \rangle_{L^2} + \mu_1 \langle u, v_1 \rangle_{L^2} + \mu \langle \nabla u, \nabla v_1 \rangle_{L^2} && \text{for } v_1 \in H^1(\Omega) \\ \langle D_2F(x), v_2 \rangle_{(H^1)^*, H^1} &= \eta \langle \nabla w, \nabla v_2 \rangle_{L^2} + \eta \langle w, v_2 \rangle_{L^2} && \text{for } v_2 \in H^1(\Omega; \mathbb{R}^n) \end{aligned}$$

Utilizing some standard analysis on the commutation of integration and differentiation, we obtain the partial (Gateaux-) derivatives of $G(\cdot)$ as

$$\begin{aligned} \langle D_1G(y), w_1 \rangle_{(L^2)^*, L^2} &= \int_{\Omega} \alpha_0 h_\gamma(p) \cdot w_1 \, dx \quad \text{for } w_1 \in L^2(\Omega; \mathbb{R}^n) \\ \langle D_2G(y), w_2 \rangle_{(L^2)^*, L^2} &= \int_{\Omega} \alpha_1 h_\gamma(q) \cdot w_2 \, dx \quad \text{for } w_2 \in L^2(\Omega; \mathbb{R}_{sym}^{n \times n}) \end{aligned}$$

Putting everything together, and taking into account the convexity of $J_\alpha^{\gamma, \epsilon}(\cdot)$ along with the properties of the subdifferential in Theorem 12, we obtain eventually the statement

$$\begin{aligned} x \in H^1(\Omega) \times H^1(\Omega; \mathbb{R}^n) \text{ is a solution of } (P_\alpha^{\gamma, \epsilon}) \text{ if and only if} \\ 0 \in \partial J_\alpha^{\gamma, \epsilon}(x) = \{DF(x)\} + \Lambda^* \{DG(\Lambda x)\} \quad \text{in } H^1(\Omega)^* \times H^1(\Omega; \mathbb{R}^n)^* \end{aligned}$$

which is exactly the claim of the theorem. □

We briefly argue, that $(P_\alpha^{\gamma, \epsilon})$ has a solution.

Theorem 30 (Existence). *Choose again the parameter space $\mathbb{V} = L^2(\Omega) \times L^2(\Omega)$ and $\alpha \in W_{ad}$ as in Assumption 2. Moreover assume that $K \in \mathcal{L}(L^2(\Omega))$ is injective on constant functions. Then problem $(P_{\alpha}^{\gamma, \epsilon})$ has a solution, which is unique, if K is injective or $\mu_K > 0$.*

Proof. The proof can be done by the direct method of calculus of variations, pretty similar as the proof for Theorem 21. As this is nothing new, a rigorous proof is omitted. \square

Remark 4. Note that, unlike Theorem 21, the above existence statement works in general space dimension. This is because the Poincaré inequality in $H^1(\Omega)$ is valid in any dimension. As a brief reminder, the Poincaré inequality reads

$$\|u - u_{\Omega}\|_{L^2(\Omega)} \leq C_p \|\nabla u\|_{L^2(\Omega)} \quad \text{for any } u \in H^1(\Omega)$$

where $C_p > 0$ and we used the notation

$$u_{\Omega} := \frac{1}{|\Omega|} \int_{\Omega} u \, dx$$

The convergence of solutions of the smoothed lower level problems $(P_{\alpha}^{\gamma, \epsilon})$ to a solution of the original lower level problem (P) as the parameters $\gamma, \mu, \eta > 0$ vanish is addressed by the next theorem. Notice that a thorough treatise of the convergence behavior for $(\gamma, \mu, \eta) \rightarrow (0, 0, 0)$ and general $\alpha \in L^2(\Omega) \times L^2(\Omega)$ seems exclusive for the time being, since the non smooth lower level objective $J_{\alpha} : BV(\Omega) \times BD(\Omega) \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$

$$J_{\alpha}(u, w) = \int_{\Omega} \alpha_1 \, d|Du - w| + \int_{\Omega} \alpha_0 \, d|\mathcal{E}w|$$

is only well-defined for continuous regularization weights $\alpha \in C(\bar{\Omega}) \times C(\bar{\Omega})$ uniformly bounded away from zero.

Theorem 31 (Consistency of the smoothed lower level problem for continuous parameters). *Consider space dimension $n = 2$, a linear operator $K \in \mathcal{L}(L^2(\Omega))$, which is injective on affine functions and $\mu_K \geq 0$ as in the beginning of the section. Moreover fix continuous distributed weights $\alpha \in C(\bar{\Omega}) \times C(\bar{\Omega})$ as in Assumption 2. If*

$$\begin{aligned} (\gamma_n, \mu_n, \eta_n) &\rightarrow (0, 0, 0) \\ (u_n, w_n) &\in \underset{(u, w) \in H^1(\Omega) \times H^1(\Omega; \mathbb{R}^n)}{\operatorname{argmin}} J_{\alpha}^{\gamma_n, \epsilon}(u, w) \end{aligned}$$

then we find $(u^*, w^*) \in BV(\Omega) \times BD(\Omega)$ such that, up to the choice of a suitable subsequence

$$\begin{aligned} u_n &\overset{*}{\rightharpoonup} u^* \quad \text{in } BV(\Omega) \\ w_n &\overset{*}{\rightharpoonup} w^* \quad \text{in } BD(\Omega) \end{aligned}$$

$$(u^*, w^*) \in \underset{(u, w) \in BV(\Omega) \times BD(\Omega)}{\operatorname{argmin}} \frac{1}{2} \|Ku - f\|_{L^2(\Omega)}^2 + \frac{\mu_K}{2} \|u\|_{L^2(\Omega)}^2 + \int_{\Omega} \alpha_1 \, d|Du - w| + \int_{\Omega} \alpha_0 \, d|\mathcal{E}w|$$

i.e $u^* \in BV(\Omega)$ solves the original lower level Problem, at least for the choice $\mu_K = 0$.

If the solution $u^* \in BV(\Omega)$ of the original non smooth bilevel problem is unique, then the whole sequence converges $u_n \overset{*}{\rightharpoonup} u^*$ in $BV(\Omega)$.

Before any proof of the above statement can be presented, we need some measure theoretic approximation lemma, which was found in [BH14] with the purpose of generalizing the concept of *intermediate convergence* to the TGV case. The term 'intermediate' refers to the fact, that the intermediate convergence is stronger than weak* convergence, but weaker than norm convergence in the spaces $BV(\Omega)$ or $BD(\Omega)$.

Lemma 4. (Smooth approximation) Let $u \in BV(\Omega)$, $w \in BD(\Omega)$ and $1 \leq q \leq n/(n-1)$. Then there are sequences $(u_n)_{n \in \mathbb{N}}$ in $BV(\Omega) \cap C^\infty(\bar{\Omega})$ and $(w_n)_{n \in \mathbb{N}}$ in $BD(\Omega) \cap C^\infty(\bar{\Omega}; \mathbb{R}^n)$ such that

$$\begin{aligned} \|u_n - u\|_{L^q(\Omega)} &\rightarrow 0 & \text{and} & & \|\nabla u_n - w_n\|_{\mathcal{M}(\Omega; \mathbb{R}^n)} &\rightarrow \|\nabla u - w\|_{\mathcal{M}(\Omega; \mathbb{R}^n)} \\ \|w_n - w\|_{L^q(\Omega; \mathbb{R}^n)} &\rightarrow 0 & \text{and} & & \|\mathcal{E} w_n\|_{\mathcal{M}(\Omega; \mathbb{R}^{n \times n}_{sym})} &\rightarrow \|\mathcal{E} w\|_{\mathcal{M}(\Omega; \mathbb{R}^{n \times n}_{sym})} \end{aligned} \quad (4.42)$$

Proof. For $q = 1$, the lengthy proof to obtain sequences

$$(u_n)_{n \in \mathbb{N}} \text{ in } BV(\Omega) \cap C^\infty(\Omega) \quad (w_n)_{n \in \mathbb{N}} \text{ in } BD(\Omega) \cap C^\infty(\Omega; \mathbb{R}^n)$$

such that (4.42) holds, is presented in [Val17] via mollification arguments. These arguments can be straight forward extended to higher integrability exponents $1 \leq q \leq n/(n-1)$, using the continuous embeddings $BV(\Omega) \hookrightarrow L^q(\Omega)$ and $BD(\Omega) \hookrightarrow L^q(\Omega; \mathbb{R}^n)$ as well as standard properties on the convergence of mollifiers.

For the extension up to the boundary, we can argue as in [BMA06], Theorem 10.1.2 that $BV(\Omega) \cap C^\infty(\Omega) = W^{1,1}(\Omega) \cap C^\infty(\Omega)$ and $BD(\Omega) \cap C^\infty(\Omega; \mathbb{R}^n) = LD(\Omega) \cap C^\infty(\Omega; \mathbb{R}^n)$. Now recall, that $C^\infty(\bar{\Omega})$ is dense in $W^{1,1}(\Omega)$ and $C^\infty(\bar{\Omega}; \mathbb{R}^n)$ is dense in $LD(\Omega)$, both with respect to the strong topology, cf. Theorem 1. Taking into account, that the strong convergence is finer than the intermediate convergence in each of the two spaces $W^{1,1}(\Omega)$ and $LD(\Omega)$, the result follows immediately. \square

We are now able to present the proof of the main consistency theorem:

Proof. (Of Theorem 31) For abbreviation we set

$$\begin{aligned} J_n(u, w) &:= \frac{1}{2} \|Ku - f\|_{L^2(\Omega)}^2 + \frac{\mu_K}{2} \|u\|_{L^2(\Omega)}^2 + \frac{\mu_n}{2} \|\nabla u\|_{L^2(\Omega; \mathbb{R}^n)}^2 + \frac{\eta_n}{2} \|w\|_{H^1(\Omega; \mathbb{R}^n)}^2 \\ &\quad + \int_{\Omega} \alpha_1 \varphi_{\gamma_n}(\nabla u - w) dx + \int_{\Omega} \alpha_0 \varphi_{\gamma_n}(\mathcal{E} w) dx \end{aligned}$$

and for the original nonsmooth functional

$$J_0(u, w) := \|Ku - f\|_{L^2(\Omega)}^2 + \frac{\mu_K}{2} \|u\|_{L^2(\Omega)}^2 + \int_{\Omega} \alpha_0 d|Du - w| + \int_{\Omega} \alpha_1 d|\mathcal{E} w|$$

we then proceed in several steps:

Step 1: Show that the sequences $(\|u_n\|_{BV(\Omega)})_{n \in \mathbb{N}}$ and $(\|w_n\|_{BD(\Omega)})_{n \in \mathbb{N}}$ are bounded.

Since $(u_n, w_n) \in H^1(\Omega) \times H^1(\Omega; \mathbb{R}^n)$ is a minimizer of J_n , we observe for every $n \in \mathbb{N}$

$$\int_{\Omega} \alpha_1 \varphi_{\gamma_n}(\nabla u_n - w_n) dx \leq J_n(u_n, w_n) \leq J_n(0, 0) = \frac{1}{2} \|f\|_{L^2(\Omega)}^2 \quad (4.43)$$

The left hand side of the above chain of inequalities can be further estimated from below:

$$\begin{aligned} \int_{\Omega} \alpha_1 \varphi_{\gamma_n}(\nabla u_n - w_n) dx &= \sup_{\substack{v \in C_0(\Omega, X) \\ \|v\|_{L^\infty(\Omega, X)} \leq 1}} \int_{\Omega} \alpha_1 (\nabla u_n - w_n) \cdot v dx - \frac{\gamma_n}{2} \int_{\Omega} \alpha_1 |v|_2^2 dx \\ &\geq \underline{\alpha}_1 \sup_{\substack{v \in C_0(\Omega, X) \\ \|v\|_{L^\infty(\Omega, X)} \leq 1}} \int_{\Omega} (\nabla u_n - w_n) \cdot v dx - \frac{\gamma_n}{2} \bar{\alpha}_1 |\Omega| \\ &\geq (\underline{\alpha}_1/2) \|\nabla u_n - w_n\|_{\mathcal{M}(\Omega; \mathbb{R}^n)} \end{aligned}$$

for $n \in \mathbb{N}$ large enough by $\gamma_n \rightarrow 0$. Thus we obtain with (4.43)

$$\underline{\alpha}_1 \|\nabla u_n - w_n\|_{\mathcal{M}(\Omega; \mathbb{R}^n)} \leq \|f\|_{L^2(\Omega)} \quad (4.44)$$

The same argumentation yields

$$\underline{\alpha}_0 \|\mathcal{E} w_n\|_{\mathcal{M}(\Omega; \mathbb{R}_{sym}^{n \times n})} \leq \|f\|_{L^2(\Omega)} \quad (4.45)$$

where both equations hold again for every $n \in \mathbb{N}$, sufficiently large. By the minimization property of (u_n, w_n) we also see

$$\|K u_n - f\|_{L^2(\Omega)}^2 \leq J_n(0, 0) = \frac{1}{2} \|f\|_{L^2(\Omega)}^2 \quad (4.46)$$

Together with (4.44) and (4.45) we infer

$$TGV_{\underline{\alpha}}^2(u_n) \leq \underline{\alpha}_1 \|\nabla u_n - w_n\|_{\mathcal{M}(\Omega; \mathbb{R}^n)} + \underline{\alpha}_0 \|\mathcal{E} w_n\|_{\mathcal{M}(\Omega; \mathbb{R}_{sym}^{n \times n})} \leq 2\|f\|_{L^2(\Omega)} \quad (4.47)$$

Now arguing exactly as the proof of Theorem 21 via Poincaré-Wirtinger inequality, we obtain the boundedness of $(u_n)_{n \in \mathbb{N}}$ in $BV(\Omega)$ from (4.46) and (4.47). Now observe, that

$$\begin{aligned} \|w_n\|_{L^1(\Omega; \mathbb{R}^n)} &\leq \|\nabla u_n - w_n\|_{\mathcal{M}(\Omega; \mathbb{R}^n)} + \|\nabla u_n\|_{\mathcal{M}(\Omega; \mathbb{R}^n)} \\ &\leq \|\nabla u_n - w_n\|_{\mathcal{M}(\Omega; \mathbb{R}^n)} + \|u_n\|_{BV(\Omega)} \end{aligned}$$

Taking also into account (4.45), the boundedness of $(w_n)_{n \in \mathbb{N}}$ in $BD(\Omega)$ follows from the last estimate. Minding Theorem 7, in particular the compactness in $BV(\Omega)$ and $BD(\Omega)$, the boundedness of $(\|u_n\|_{BV(\Omega)})_{n \in \mathbb{N}}$ and $(\|w_n\|_{BD(\Omega)})_{n \in \mathbb{N}}$ yields subsequences (renamed!) and elements $u^* \in BV(\Omega)$, $w^* \in BD(\Omega)$ with

$$\begin{aligned} u_n &\overset{*}{\rightharpoonup} u^* && \text{weak}^* \text{ in } BV(\Omega) \\ u_n &\rightharpoonup u^* && \text{weakly in } L^2(\Omega) \\ w_n &\overset{*}{\rightharpoonup} w^* && \text{weak}^* \text{ in } BD(\Omega) \end{aligned} \quad (4.48)$$

We will show, that (u^*, w^*) is the desired minimizer of $J_0(\cdot, \cdot)$, but first we continue with

Step 2: Show that

$$\liminf_{n \rightarrow \infty} J_n(u_n, w_n) \geq J_0(u^*, w^*) \quad (4.49)$$

In order to show (4.49), we recall the weak lower semicontinuity of

$$u \mapsto \frac{1}{2} \|K u - f\|_{L^2(\Omega)}^2 + \frac{\lambda_K}{2} \|u\|_{L^2(\Omega)}^2$$

on $L^2(\Omega)$. Additionally, we observe as in the first step

$$\begin{aligned} \int_{\Omega} \alpha_1 \varphi_{\gamma_n}(\nabla u_n - w_n) \, dx &= \sup_{\substack{v \in C_0(\Omega, X) \\ \|v\|_{L^\infty(\Omega, X)} \leq 1}} \int_{\Omega} \alpha_1 (\nabla u_n - w_n) \cdot v \, dx - \frac{\gamma_n}{2} \int_{\Omega} \alpha_1 |v|_2^2 \, dx \\ &\geq \|\alpha_1 \cdot (\nabla u_n - w_n)\|_{\mathcal{M}(\Omega; \mathbb{R}^n)} - \frac{\gamma_n}{2} \bar{\alpha}_1 |\Omega| \end{aligned}$$

Its easy to see that (4.48) yields also $\alpha_1 \cdot (\nabla u_n - w_n) \overset{*}{\rightharpoonup} \alpha_1 \cdot (\nabla u^* - w^*)$ weak* in $\mathcal{M}(\Omega; \mathbb{R}^n)$ and by the weak* lower semi-continuity of $\|\cdot\|_{\mathcal{M}(\Omega; \mathbb{R}^n)}$ we arrive at

$$\begin{aligned} \liminf_{n \rightarrow \infty} \int_{\Omega} \alpha_1 \varphi_{\gamma_n}(\nabla u_n - w_n) \, dx &\geq \liminf_{n \in \infty} \|\alpha_1 \cdot (\nabla u - w)\|_{\mathcal{M}(\Omega; \mathbb{R}^n)} + \liminf_{n \rightarrow \infty} -\frac{\gamma_n}{2} \bar{\alpha}_1 |\Omega| \\ &= \int_{\Omega} \alpha_1 \, d|\nabla u - w| \end{aligned}$$

As $\gamma_n \rightarrow 0$. With the same argumentation we see

$$\liminf_{n \rightarrow \infty} \int_{\Omega} \alpha_0 \varphi_{\gamma_n}(\mathcal{E} w_n) \, dx \geq \int_{\Omega} \alpha_0 \, d|\mathcal{E} w|$$

Gathering everything together, we get

$$\begin{aligned}
\liminf_{n \rightarrow \infty} J_n(u_n, w_n) &\geq \liminf_{n \rightarrow \infty} \frac{1}{2} \|Ku_n - f\|_{L^2(\Omega)}^2 + \frac{\lambda_K}{2} \|u_n\|_{L^2(\Omega)}^2 \\
&\quad + \liminf_{n \rightarrow \infty} \int_{\Omega} \alpha_1 \varphi_{\gamma_n}(\nabla u_n - w_n) \, dx \\
&\quad + \liminf_{n \rightarrow \infty} \int_{\Omega} \alpha_0 \varphi_{\gamma_n}(\mathcal{E} w_n) \, dx \\
&\geq \frac{1}{2} \|Ku - f\|_{L^2(\Omega)}^2 + \frac{\lambda_K}{2} \|u\|_{L^2(\Omega)}^2 + \int_{\Omega} \alpha_1 \, d|\nabla u - w| + \int_{\Omega} \alpha_0 \, d|\mathcal{E} w|
\end{aligned}$$

which is exactly (4.49) in the claim of step 2.

Step 3: Show, that

$$J_0(u^*, w^*) \leq J_0(u, w) \quad \text{for every } (u, w) \in H^1(\Omega) \times H^1(\Omega; \mathbb{R}^n)$$

The claim follows directly from (4.49): Since $(u_n, w_n)_n$ are minimizers of $J_n(\cdot, \cdot)$, we obtain for every $(u, w) \in H^1(\Omega) \times H^1(\Omega; \mathbb{R}^n)$:

$$J_0(u^*, w^*) \leq \liminf_{n \rightarrow \infty} J_n(u_n, w_n) \leq \liminf_{n \rightarrow \infty} J_n(u, w) \leq J_0(u, w)$$

where the last inequality relies on the fact, that for every $n \in \mathbb{N}$:

$$\begin{aligned}
\int_{\Omega} \alpha_1 \varphi_{\gamma_n}(\nabla u - w) \, dx &\leq \int_{\Omega} \alpha_1 \, d|\nabla u - w| \\
\int_{\Omega} \alpha_0 \varphi_{\gamma_n}(\mathcal{E} w) \, dx &\leq \int_{\Omega} \alpha_0 \, d|\mathcal{E} w|
\end{aligned}$$

These inequalities can again be easily deduced from the Fenchel dual characterizations of the huberized Radon norms (4.39).

Step 4: Show, that even

$$J_0(u^*, w^*) \leq J_0(u, w) \quad \text{for every } (u, w) \in BV(\Omega) \times BD(\Omega)$$

Using Lemma 4 with $q = 2$, we approximate $(u, w) \in BV(\Omega) \times BD(\Omega)$ by a sequence $(u_n, w_n) \in H^1(\Omega) \times H^1(\Omega; \mathbb{R}^n)$, such that (4.42) holds. By continuity, we further deduce

$$\|Ku_n - f\|_{L^2(\Omega)}^2 \rightarrow \|Ku - f\|_{L^2(\Omega)}^2 \tag{4.50}$$

Now observe, that

$$|\nabla u_n - w_n|(\Omega) = \|\nabla u_n - w_n\|_{\mathcal{M}(\Omega; \mathbb{R}^n)} \rightarrow \|\nabla u - w\|_{\mathcal{M}(\Omega; \mathbb{R}^n)} = |\nabla u - w|(\Omega) \tag{4.51}$$

and for fixed, open $U \subset \Omega$, we see by the monotonicity of the considered measures

$$\sup_{n \in \mathbb{N}} |\nabla u_n - w_n|(U) \leq \sup_{n \in \mathbb{N}} |\nabla u_n - w_n|(\Omega) < \infty$$

hence also

$$\nabla u_{n_k} - w_{n_k} \xrightarrow{*} \nabla u - w \quad \text{weak}^* \text{ in } \mathcal{M}(U; \mathbb{R}^n)$$

for some subsequence, by compactness in $\mathcal{M}(U; \mathbb{R}^n)$. Minding weak* lower semicontinuity of the TV seminorm on the space $\mathcal{M}(U; \mathbb{R}^n)$, we deduce

$$\liminf_{n \rightarrow \infty} |\nabla u_{n_k} - w_{n_k}|(U) \geq |\nabla u - w|(U)$$

As this argumentation applies to every subsequence and $U \subset \Omega$ was arbitrary, we get

$$\liminf_{n \rightarrow \infty} |\nabla u_n - w_n|(U) \geq |\nabla u - w|(U) \quad \text{for every open } U \subset \Omega \quad (4.52)$$

By [BMA06], proposition 4.2.5, the inequality in (4.52) alongside with the limit in (4.51) are sufficient for $|\nabla u_n - w_n| \in \mathcal{M}(\Omega)_+$ to converge narrowly¹ to $|\nabla u - w| \in \mathcal{M}(\Omega)_+$. Therefore we get

$$\int_{\Omega} \alpha_1 d|\nabla u_n - w_n| \rightarrow \int_{\Omega} \alpha_1 d|\nabla u - w|$$

Exactly the same argumentation also yields

$$\int_{\Omega} \alpha_0 d|\mathcal{E} w_n| \rightarrow \int_{\Omega} \alpha_0 d|\mathcal{E} w| \quad (4.53)$$

The last two inequalities, combined with (4.50) and the statement of step 3. result in

$$J_0(u^*, w^*) \leq J_0(u_n, w_n) \rightarrow J_0(u, w) \quad (4.54)$$

that proves step 4 and with it also the claim of the first part of the theorem.

Assume now that the solution $u^* \in BV(\Omega)$ of the original non smooth bilevel problem is unique (for instance, if $\mu_K > 0$) and that $u_n \xrightarrow{*} u^*$ in $BV(\Omega)$ does not hold. The latter is exactly the case if one of the following conditions is violated

$$u_n \rightarrow u^* \quad \text{in } L^1(\Omega) \quad (4.55)$$

$$Du_n \xrightarrow{*} Du^* \quad \text{in } \mathcal{M}(\Omega; \mathbb{R}^n) \quad (4.56)$$

If (4.55) does not hold true, we find a small $\varepsilon_0 > 0$ and a subsequence $(u_{n_k})_k$ such that

$$\|u_{n_k} - u^*\|_{L^1(\Omega)} \geq \varepsilon_0 \quad \text{for every } k \in \mathbb{N} \quad (4.57)$$

However, if we repeat steps one to four for the sequence $(u_{n_k}, w_{n_k})_k \subset BV(\Omega) \times BD(\Omega)$, we obtain again (up to a subsequence)

$$u_{n_k} \xrightarrow{*} u^* \quad \text{in } BV(\Omega) \quad (4.58)$$

as $u^* \in BV(\Omega)$ is the unique solution. This is clearly a contradiction to (4.57).

If the second condition (4.56) is violated, we find a small number $\varepsilon_1 > 0$, an element $\varphi_1 \in C_0(\Omega; \mathbb{R}^n)$ and a subsequence $(u_{n_k})_k$, which is not necessarily the same as above, such that

$$|\langle Du_{n_k}, \varphi_1 \rangle - \langle Du^*, \varphi_1 \rangle| \geq \varepsilon_1 \quad \text{for every } k \in \mathbb{N} \quad (4.59)$$

Again we may repeat steps one to four for the sequence $(u_{n_k}, w_{n_k})_k \subset BV(\Omega) \times BD(\Omega)$ and get (up to some subsequence)

$$u_{n_k} \xrightarrow{*} u^* \quad \text{in } BV(\Omega) \quad (4.60)$$

since $u^* \in BV(\Omega)$ is the unique solution. This is again a contradiction to (4.59). Hence the whole sequence converges $u_n \xrightarrow{*} u^*$ in $BV(\Omega)$. \square

¹Narrow convergence of a sequence of measures $\mu_n \in \mathcal{M}(\Omega; X)$ to a measure $\mu \in \mathcal{M}(\Omega; X)$ means, that

$$\int_{\Omega} f d\mu_n \rightarrow \int_{\Omega} f d\mu \quad \text{for every } f \in C_b(\Omega; X)$$

Eventually we approximate the problem (\mathbb{P}_{orig}) by replacing the lower level problem by its equivalent first order characterization from Theorem 29:

$$\begin{aligned} \min_{(u, \alpha) \in L^2(\Omega) \times W_{ad}} \mathcal{J}(x, \alpha) &:= F \circ R(u) + \frac{\lambda}{2} \left(\|\alpha_0\|_{H^1(\Omega)}^2 + \|\alpha_1\|_{H^1(\Omega)}^2 \right) \\ \text{s.t. } g_\gamma(x, \alpha) &= 0 \end{aligned} \quad (\mathbb{P}^\gamma)$$

where we again wrote $x = (u, w)$ and chose the configuration

$$W_{ad} \subset \mathbb{V} = H^1(\Omega) \times H^1(\Omega)$$

The function $g_\gamma(\cdot, \cdot)$ is given by (4.41).

Note, that the equation $g_\gamma(x, \alpha) = 0$ can be formally written in a strong form as

$$\begin{bmatrix} K^*Ku - K^*f + \mu_K u - \mu \Delta u \\ \eta w - \eta \Delta w \end{bmatrix} + \begin{bmatrix} -\text{div} & 0 \\ -Id & -\text{div} \end{bmatrix} \circ \begin{bmatrix} \alpha_1 h_\gamma(\nabla u - w) \\ \alpha_0 h_\gamma(\mathcal{E} w) \end{bmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} 0 \\ 0 \end{pmatrix} \quad (4.61)$$

which is (at least for the denoising case) a second order system of quasilinear partial differential equations (PDEs) with Neumann boundary conditions. This motivates the discussion in the following chapter.

Chapter 5

Bilevel Imaging via Optimal Control Theory

In the last chapter we stated a bilevel optimization problem, that was derived from the equivalent first order optimality conditions of the lower level problem. This problem has a structure, which is well known from the theory of optimal control with PDE constraints. For this reason we will analyze problem (\mathbb{P}^γ) from the control theory viewpoint. This approach is inspired by the work [RS13] and the recent papers [RSV17] and [HPRS20]. In the first section the lower level problem (\mathbb{P}^γ) is smoothed again and reformulated in the optimal control theory language. Afterwards, existence of solutions of the state equation is examined and the solution operator is studied regarding continuity and differentiability properties. The results are used to provide a first order optimality system of the control problem and to state a projected gradient descent algorithm in the infinite dimensional function space. The chapter is intended to complement the recent paper [HPRS20], where the analysis of the control problem is carried out in a more formal way. Moreover the results concerning the differentiability of the solution operator slightly extend the existing literature [RSV17] and [VCRS17] to general operators $K \in \mathcal{L}(L^2(\Omega))$ and spatially varying parameters $\alpha \in L^\infty(\Omega) \times L^\infty(\Omega)$. The mathematical challenges, arising from the introduction of these spatially distributed parameters are discussed and possible workarounds are proposed. These could also serve as a starting point for further investigations.

5.1 Setting and Statement of the Optimal Control Problem

This short section is intended to transfer the bilevel imaging problem (\mathbb{P}^γ) to the language of optimal control theory. To this end we shall first introduce the notation, which is typically used in optimal control theory and fix some assumptions needed for our further analysis.

Assumption 4. (On the current chapter)

1. Let $\Omega \subset \mathbb{R}^n$ be a bounded Lipschitz domain. In addition we demand that Ω is convex.
2. For $p \geq 1$, the so called **state space** is given by

$$\mathbb{W}_{1,p} := W^{1,p}(\Omega) \times W^{1,p}(\Omega; \mathbb{R}^n)$$

In the case $p = 2$ we simply write $\mathbb{H}_1 := \mathbb{W}_{1,2}$. Moreover, an element $x \in \mathbb{W}_{1,p}$ is usually denoted componentwise by $x = (u, w) \in W^{1,p}(\Omega) \times W^{1,p}(\Omega; \mathbb{R}^n)$.

3. The **control space** \mathbb{V} is a Banach space, for which we have the continuous embedding

$$\mathbb{V} \hookrightarrow L^2(\Omega) \times L^2(\Omega)$$

4. The **set of admissible controls** $W_{ad} \subset \mathbb{V}$ is a nonempty, closed and convex subset of \mathbb{V} , such that there are positive constants $0 < A \leq B$ with

$$\boldsymbol{\alpha}(x) \in [A, B] \times [A, B] \quad \text{for every } \boldsymbol{\alpha} \in W_{ad} \text{ and (almost) every } x \in \Omega$$

5. The **cost functional** $\mathcal{F} : \mathbb{H}_1 \rightarrow [0, \infty)$ is chosen to be continuously Frechét-differentiable with derivative $D\mathcal{F} : \mathbb{H}_1 \rightarrow \mathbb{H}_1^*$.
6. The operator $K \in \mathcal{L}(L^2(\Omega))$ is continuous, linear and bounded.
7. The parameter $0 \leq \mu_K$ is chosen, such that

$$\mu_K = 0 \quad \text{if } K^*K \text{ is invertible.} \quad (5.1)$$

$$\mu_K > 0 \quad \text{if } K^*K \text{ is not invertible.} \quad (5.2)$$

8. The parameters $0 < \mu, \eta, \lambda, \gamma, \delta$ denote always positive real numbers.

Under these assumptions and with the choice of $\mathbb{V} := H^1(\Omega) \times H^1(\Omega)$ and $x \mapsto \mathcal{F}(x) = F \circ R(u)$ as in the previous chapter, the bilevel problem (\mathbb{P}^γ) reads

$$\begin{aligned} \min_{(x, \boldsymbol{\alpha}) \in \mathbb{H}^1 \times \mathbb{V}} \quad & \mathcal{J}(x, \boldsymbol{\alpha}) := \mathcal{F}(u) + \frac{\lambda}{2} \left(\|\alpha_0\|_{H^1(\Omega)}^2 + \|\alpha_1\|_{H^1(\Omega)}^2 \right) \\ \text{s.t.} \quad & g_\gamma(x, \boldsymbol{\alpha}) = 0 \quad \text{in } \mathbb{H}_1^* \\ & \boldsymbol{\alpha} \in W_{ad} \end{aligned} \quad (5.3)$$

where the so called **state-equation** is given in terms of the PDE operator $g_\gamma : \mathbb{H}_1 \times \mathbb{V} \rightarrow \mathbb{H}_1^*$ of quasilinear type

$$\langle g_\gamma(x, \boldsymbol{\alpha}), v \rangle_{\mathbb{H}_1^*, \mathbb{H}_1} = \langle Ax, v \rangle_{\mathbb{H}_1^*, \mathbb{H}_1} + \langle N_\gamma(\boldsymbol{\alpha})x, v \rangle_{\mathbb{H}_1^*, \mathbb{H}_1}$$

Here, we used the operators $A, N_\gamma(\boldsymbol{\alpha})$, which are defined as

$$\begin{aligned} A, N_\gamma(\boldsymbol{\alpha}) : \mathbb{H}_1 &\rightarrow \mathbb{H}_1^* \\ \langle Ax, v \rangle_{\mathbb{H}_1^*, \mathbb{H}_1} &:= \langle K^*Ku - K^*f, v_1 \rangle_{L^2} + \mu_K \langle u, v_1 \rangle_{L^2} + \mu \langle \nabla u, \nabla v_1 \rangle_{L^2} + \eta \langle w, v_2 \rangle_{H^1} \end{aligned} \quad (5.4)$$

$$\langle N_\gamma(\boldsymbol{\alpha})x, v \rangle_{\mathbb{H}_1^*, \mathbb{H}_1} := \int_{\Omega} \alpha_1 h_\gamma(\nabla u - w) \cdot (\nabla v_1 - v_2) \, dx + \int_{\Omega} \alpha_0 h_\gamma(\mathcal{E}w) \cdot \mathcal{E}v_2 \, dx \quad (5.5)$$

for $v = (v_1, v_2) \in \mathbb{H}_1$. Note, that the parameters $0 \leq \mu_K$ and $0 < \mu, \eta$ are adjusted exactly in such a way, that the operator $A : \mathbb{H}_1 \rightarrow \mathbb{H}_1^*$ is strongly monotone in any case, cf. chapter 2 and [ZB89]. To derive a first order optimality system for (5.3), we need to differentiate $g_\gamma(\cdot, \cdot)$ in a certain sense. However, the function $h_\gamma(\cdot)$, defined in (4.37) is not differentiable, which makes it hard to prove the smoothness of $N_\gamma(\boldsymbol{\alpha}) : \mathbb{H}_1 \rightarrow \mathbb{H}_1^*$. Therefore a second smoothing step of the Huber function is applied as for instance proposed in [RHM16], [RSV17] and also in the recent paper [HPRS20]. For given $\delta \leq 2\gamma$, we therefore introduce the function $h(\cdot) = h_{\gamma, \delta}(\cdot)$ defined as

$$h_{\gamma, \delta} : X \rightarrow X \quad h_{\gamma, \delta}(x) := \frac{x}{m_\delta(|x|, \gamma)} \quad (5.6)$$

but instead of the pointwise max-operator in (4.37), a smoothed approximation of the latter is used:

$$m_\delta(\cdot, \gamma) : [0, \infty) \rightarrow \mathbb{R} \quad m_\delta(r, \gamma) = \begin{cases} \gamma & \text{if } r \leq \gamma - \delta/2 \\ (2\delta)^{-1}(r + \delta/2 - \gamma)^2 + \gamma & \text{if } \gamma - \delta/2 < r < \gamma + \delta/2 \\ r & \text{if } r \geq \gamma + \delta/2 \end{cases} \quad (5.7)$$

which is continuously differentiable and the derivative is given by

$$m'_\delta(\cdot, \gamma) : [0, \infty) \rightarrow \mathbb{R} \quad m'_\delta(r, \gamma) = \begin{cases} 0 & \text{if } r \leq \gamma - \delta/2 \\ \delta^{-1}(r + \delta/2 - \gamma) & \text{if } \gamma - \delta/2 < r < \gamma + \delta/2 \\ 1 & \text{if } r \geq \gamma + \delta/2 \end{cases} \quad (5.8)$$

Recall that, as in the previous chapter, we chose $X \in \{\mathbb{R}^n, \mathbb{R}_{sym}^{n \times n}\}$ and in the notation we do not distinguish between both cases.

Additionally, unless otherwise stated, we will mostly skip the (γ, δ) in the notation of $h_{\gamma, \delta}(\cdot)$ and $m_\delta(\cdot, \gamma)$ and every time we write $h(\cdot)$ or $m(\cdot, \gamma)$ in the subsequent part, it should be clear, that we mean the smoothed version in (5.7) and (5.8).

The next theorem summarizes important properties of $h(\cdot)$, which are used tacitly throughout the entire chapter.

Theorem 32. *Let $X \in \{\mathbb{R}^n, \mathbb{R}_{sym}^{n \times n}\}$ and let the function $h(\cdot)$ be defined as in (5.7). Then the subsequent statements are valid.*

1. $|h(\cdot)| \leq 1$, in particular, h is bounded.
2. h is Lipschitz continuous, i.e. there is a number $L_1 > 0$ such that $|h(x) - h(y)| \leq L_1|x - y|$ for every $x, y \in X$.
3. h is monotone in the sense, that $(h(x) - h(y)) \cdot (x - y) \geq 0$ for every $x, y \in X$.
4. h is continuously differentiable and the derivative is given by

$$h' : X \rightarrow \mathcal{L}(X) \quad h'(x)[v] = \frac{v}{m(|x|, \gamma)} - m'(|x|, \gamma) \frac{x \cdot v}{m(|x|, \gamma)^2} \frac{x}{|x|} \quad (5.9)$$

5. The derivative $h' : X \rightarrow \mathcal{L}(X)$ satisfies

$$\|h'(x)\|_{\mathcal{L}(X)} \leq L_\gamma \quad \text{for a constant } L_\gamma > 0 \text{ and every } x \in X. \quad (5.10)$$

$$h'(x)[v] \cdot v \geq 0 \quad \text{for every } x, v \in X. \quad (5.11)$$

$$h'(x)[v] \cdot w = h'(x)[w] \cdot v \quad \text{for every } v, w \in X. \quad (5.12)$$

Proof. The proof uses only standard finite dimensional analysis and therefore is omitted here. \square

Remark 5. In the above theorem we used the notation $x/|x| \in X$ for the unit-vector in direction x . For $|x| = 0$, this term is defined to be zero. Moreover we point out, that 1., 2. and 3. hold also for the nonsmooth $h_\gamma(\cdot)$, defined in (4.37).

Finally, we can state the control problem by replacing the nonsmooth operator $g_\gamma = A + N_\gamma(\alpha)$ by a smoothed version of it, using the function $h(\cdot)$. For that purpose, we simply substitute the nondifferentiable function $h_\gamma(\cdot)$ in the definition of $N_\gamma(\alpha)$ by $h(\cdot)$, which yields

$$N(\alpha) := N_{\gamma, \delta}(\alpha) : \mathbb{H}_1 \rightarrow \mathbb{H}_1^* \\ \langle N(\alpha)x, v \rangle_{\mathbb{H}_1^*, \mathbb{H}_1} := \int_\Omega \alpha_1 h(\nabla u - w) \cdot (\nabla v_1 - v_2) dx + \int_\Omega \alpha_0 h(\mathcal{E}w) \cdot \mathcal{E}v_2 dx \quad \text{for } v = (v_1, v_2) \in \mathbb{H}_1 \quad (5.13)$$

where now $h(\cdot)$ is the function in the definition of (5.7). Consequently, setting

$$g(x, \alpha) := g_{\gamma, \delta}(x, \alpha) := Ax + N(\alpha)x \quad \text{for every } x \in \mathbb{H}_1$$

the control problem can be rewritten as

$$\begin{aligned} \min_{(u, \alpha) \in \mathbb{H}^1 \times W_{ad}} \mathcal{J}(u, \alpha) &= \mathcal{F}(u) + \frac{\lambda}{2} \left(\|\alpha_0\|_{H^1(\Omega)}^2 + \|\alpha_1\|_{H^1(\Omega)}^2 \right) \\ \text{s.t. } g(x, \alpha) &:= 0 \quad \text{in } \mathbb{H}_1^* \end{aligned} \quad (\mathbb{P}_{\text{control}})$$

The linear operator $A: \mathbb{H}_1 \rightarrow \mathbb{H}_1^*$ remains the same as in (5.4).

A further smoothing step, as we did in the transformation from the non-smooth problem (5.3) to the smooth problem ($\mathbb{P}_{\text{control}}$) requires again a proper justification by some limit analysis for $\delta \rightarrow 0$. This is provided by the next theorem for the easy case, where all other parameters remain constant.

Theorem 33 (Consistency of second smoothing step). *Let Assumption 4 be satisfied for the control space $\mathbb{V} = L^2(\Omega) \times L^2(\Omega)$ and fix $\alpha \in W_{ad}$. If we have*

$$g_\gamma(x_\gamma, \alpha) = 0 \quad \text{and} \quad g_{\gamma, \delta}(x_{\gamma, \delta}, \alpha) = 0 \quad \text{in } \mathbb{H}_1^*.$$

then the subsequent limit holds:

$$\|x_\gamma - x_{\gamma, \delta}\|_{\mathbb{H}_1} \rightarrow 0 \quad \text{as } \delta \rightarrow 0$$

Proof. First note, that under the conditions of the theorem, such solutions $x_\gamma \in \mathbb{H}_1$ and $x_{\gamma, \delta} \in \mathbb{H}_1$ exist and are unique, which follows from Theorem 34 in the next section and Theorem 30 respectively.

By considering the different cases for $r \geq 0$, we then obtain for arbitrary $\gamma > 0$.

$$|\max(r, \gamma) - m_\delta(r, \gamma)| \leq \delta \quad \text{for every } r \geq 0$$

and consequently

$$|h_\gamma(x) - h_{\gamma, \delta}(x)| = \frac{|\max(|x|, \gamma) - m_\delta(|x|, \gamma)|}{\max(|x|, \gamma) m_\delta(|x|, \gamma)} |x| \leq \frac{\delta}{\gamma} \quad \text{for every } x \in X \quad (5.14)$$

Furthermore, by definition of $x_\gamma, x_{\gamma, \delta} \in \mathbb{H}_1$ it holds

$$\langle g_\gamma(x_\gamma, \alpha), v \rangle_{\mathbb{H}_1^*, \mathbb{H}_1} = 0 \quad \text{for every } v \in \mathbb{H}_1 \quad (5.15)$$

$$\langle g_{\gamma, \delta}(x_{\gamma, \delta}, \alpha), v \rangle_{\mathbb{H}_1^*, \mathbb{H}_1} = 0 \quad \text{for every } v \in \mathbb{H}_1 \quad (5.16)$$

For general $x = (u, w) \in \mathbb{H}_1$ and $v = (v_1, v_2) \in \mathbb{H}_1$ we then obtain by definition

$$\begin{aligned} \langle g_\gamma(x, \alpha), v \rangle_{\mathbb{H}_1^*, \mathbb{H}_1} - \langle g_{\gamma, \delta}(x, \alpha), v \rangle_{\mathbb{H}_1^*, \mathbb{H}_1} &= \int_{\Omega} \alpha_1 (h_\gamma(\nabla u - w) - h_{\gamma, \delta}(\nabla u - w)) \cdot (\nabla v_1 - v_2) \, dx \\ &\quad + \int_{\Omega} \alpha_0 (h_\gamma(\mathcal{E}w) - h_{\gamma, \delta}(\mathcal{E}w)) \cdot \mathcal{E}v_2 \, dx \end{aligned} \quad (5.17)$$

Using the equations (5.15), (5.16) and (5.17) we infer the estimate

$$\begin{aligned} \langle g_{\gamma, \delta}(x_{\gamma, \delta}, \alpha) - g_\gamma(x_\gamma, \alpha), v \rangle_{\mathbb{H}_1^*, \mathbb{H}_1} &= \langle g_\gamma(x_\gamma, \alpha) - g_{\gamma, \delta}(x_\gamma, \alpha), v \rangle_{\mathbb{H}_1^*, \mathbb{H}_1} \\ &= \int_{\Omega} \alpha_1 (h_\gamma(\nabla u_\gamma - w_\gamma) - h_{\gamma, \delta}(\nabla u_\gamma - w_\gamma)) \cdot (\nabla v_1 - v_2) \, dx \\ &\quad + \int_{\Omega} \alpha_0 (h_\gamma(\mathcal{E}w_\gamma) - h_{\gamma, \delta}(\mathcal{E}w_\gamma)) \cdot \mathcal{E}v_2 \, dx \\ &\leq \frac{C\delta}{\gamma} (\|\alpha_0\|_{L^2} + \|\alpha_1\|_{L^2}) \|v\|_{\mathbb{H}_1} \quad \text{for every } v \in \mathbb{H}_1 \end{aligned} \quad (5.18)$$

where the inequality in the last line is a consequence of (5.14) and $C > 0$ is a generic positive constant. In the subsequent section, namely in Theorem 34 we will see, that the operator $x \mapsto g_{\gamma,\delta}(x, \boldsymbol{\alpha})$ is strongly monotone on \mathbb{H}_1 for some positive parameter $\kappa > 0$ and any $\boldsymbol{\alpha} \in W_{ad}$. This information, combined with (5.18) implies the estimate:

$$\kappa \|x_{\gamma,\delta} - x_\gamma\|_{\mathbb{H}_1}^2 \leq \langle g_{\gamma,\delta}(x_{\gamma,\delta}, \boldsymbol{\alpha}) - g_{\gamma,\delta}(x_\gamma, \boldsymbol{\alpha}), x_{\gamma,\delta} - x_\gamma \rangle_{\mathbb{H}_1^*, \mathbb{H}_1} \leq \frac{C\delta}{\gamma} \|\boldsymbol{\alpha}\|_{\mathbb{V}} \|x_\delta - x_{\gamma,\delta}\|_{\mathbb{H}_1}$$

Dividing by $\|x_\delta - x_{\gamma,\delta}\|_{\mathbb{H}_1}$, the claim of the theorem eventually follows. \square

5.2 Existence and Continuity of Solutions

This section is devoted to the study of existence of solutions for the smooth control problem $(\mathbb{P}_{\text{control}})$. The first question will be, whether there is at least one feasible point, i.e. whether the equation $g(x, \boldsymbol{\alpha}) = 0$ has at least one solution $x = x(\boldsymbol{\alpha}) \in \mathbb{H}_1$, for a proper choice of $\boldsymbol{\alpha} \in \mathbb{V} \cap W_{ad}$. After proving existence of such feasible points, our interest is directed towards continuity properties of the so called **control-to-state-mapping**, also known as the **solution operator**, which is denoted by

$$S: \mathbb{V} \rightarrow 2^{\mathbb{H}_1} \quad \boldsymbol{\alpha} \mapsto \{x \in \mathbb{H}_1 \mid g(x, \boldsymbol{\alpha}) = 0\} \quad (5.19)$$

In general, the mapping in (5.19) is set-valued, and, as we will see, the non emptiness of such a mapping cannot be ensured for general $\boldsymbol{\alpha}$. However, existence can be shown, if $\boldsymbol{\alpha}$ is positive component wise. In this situation, we obtain also uniqueness and the Lipschitz continuity of $S: W_{ad} \rightarrow \mathbb{H}_1$. Afterwards, we use these properties to show that $(\mathbb{P}_{\text{control}})$ has at least one solution. We start our investigations directly with the main theorem

Theorem 34 (Existence and continuity properties of the solution operator). *Let Assumption 4 hold for the control space*

$$\mathbb{V} := \mathbb{L}^2(\Omega) := L^2(\Omega) \times L^2(\Omega)$$

Then the subsequent statements are valid

1. If $\boldsymbol{\alpha} \in W_{ad}$, then $S(\boldsymbol{\alpha})$ is well-defined and single valued.
2. There is an $L > 0$, such that for every pair of parameters $\boldsymbol{\alpha}^1, \boldsymbol{\alpha}^2 \in W_{ad}$ and the corresponding solutions $(u(\boldsymbol{\alpha}^i), w(\boldsymbol{\alpha}^i)) = S(\boldsymbol{\alpha}^i)$, $i = 1, 2$ the following inequality is satisfied

$$\|u(\boldsymbol{\alpha}^1) - u(\boldsymbol{\alpha}^2)\|_{H^1(\Omega)} + \|w(\boldsymbol{\alpha}^1) - w(\boldsymbol{\alpha}^2)\|_{H^1(\Omega; \mathbb{R}^n)} \leq L \|\boldsymbol{\alpha}^1 - \boldsymbol{\alpha}^2\|_{\mathbb{L}^2(\Omega)} \quad (5.20)$$

Proof. At first, we show that $S(\boldsymbol{\alpha}) \in \mathbb{H}_1$ is well defined and single-valued, provided $S(\boldsymbol{\alpha}) \in W_{ad} \subset \mathbb{V}$. Therefore fix $\boldsymbol{\alpha} \in W_{ad}$ and consider the operators $A, N(\boldsymbol{\alpha})$ from (5.4) and (5.13), again given by

$$\begin{aligned} A, N(\boldsymbol{\alpha}) &: \mathbb{H}_1 \rightarrow \mathbb{H}_1^* \\ \langle Ax, v \rangle_{\mathbb{H}_1^*, \mathbb{H}_1} &:= \langle K^* Ku - K^* f, v_1 \rangle_{L^2} + \mu_K \langle u, v_1 \rangle_{L^2} + \mu \langle \nabla u, \nabla v_1 \rangle_{L^2} + \eta \langle w, v_2 \rangle_H \\ \langle N(\boldsymbol{\alpha})x, v \rangle_{\mathbb{H}_1^*, \mathbb{H}_1} &:= \int_{\Omega} \alpha_1 h(\nabla u - w) \cdot (\nabla v_1 - v_2) dx + \int_{\Omega} \alpha_0 h(\mathcal{E}w) \cdot \mathcal{E}v_2 dx \end{aligned}$$

for $v = (v_1, v_2) \in \mathbb{H}_1$. By definition, $x \in S(\boldsymbol{\alpha})$ if and only if $x \in \mathbb{H}_1$ solves

$$\langle Ax, v \rangle_{\mathbb{H}_1^*, \mathbb{H}_1} + \langle N(\boldsymbol{\alpha})x, v \rangle_{\mathbb{H}_1^*, \mathbb{H}_1} = 0 \quad \text{for every } v = (v_1, v_2) \in \mathbb{H}_1 \quad (5.21)$$

and we will solve (5.21) by monotone operator theory. For this reason, the continuity and monotonicity properties of both operators $A, N(\boldsymbol{\alpha}) : \mathbb{H}_1 \rightarrow \mathbb{H}_1^*$ are examined first.

It can be immediately checked, that the Operator $A : \mathbb{H}_1 \rightarrow \mathbb{H}_1^*$ is continuous and strongly monotone, if $K^*K \in \mathcal{L}(L^2(\Omega))$ is invertible in combination with $\mu_K \geq 0$ and also in the other case, where $K \in \mathcal{L}(L^2(\Omega))$ is arbitrary, possibly non invertible, resulting in $\mu_K > 0$. Consequently, there is a constant $\kappa > 0$, such that

$$\kappa \|x_1 - x_2\|_{\mathbb{H}_1}^2 = \kappa (\|u_1 - u_2\|_{H^1}^2 + \|w_1 - w_2\|_{H^1}^2) \leq \langle Ax_1 - Ax_2, x_1 - x_2 \rangle_{\mathbb{H}_1^*, \mathbb{H}_1} \quad (5.22)$$

for any $x_1 = (u_1, w_1), x_2 = (u_2, w_2) \in \mathbb{H}_1$. Minding the monotonicity properties of $h(\cdot)$ in Theorem 32, and the positivity of $\alpha \in W_{ad}$, we infer the monotonicity of $N(\alpha) : \mathbb{H}_1 \rightarrow \mathbb{H}_1^*$ as well. The continuity of the latter operator can be seen as follows:

Take a sequence $(x_n)_{n \in \mathbb{N}} \subset \mathbb{H}_1$, with $x_n \rightarrow x$ in \mathbb{H}_1 for some element $x \in \mathbb{H}_1$ and observe from the definition (5.13) and Hölders inequality for arbitrary $v \in \mathbb{H}_1$:

$$\begin{aligned} |\langle N(\alpha)x_n - N(\alpha)x, v \rangle_{\mathbb{H}_1^*, \mathbb{H}_1}| &\leq \|\alpha_1 h(\nabla u_n - w_n) - \alpha_0 h(\nabla u - w)\|_{L^2} \|\nabla v_1 - v_2\|_{L^2} \\ &\quad + \|\alpha_0 h(\mathcal{E}w_n) - \alpha_1 h(\mathcal{E}w)\|_{L^2} \|\mathcal{E}v_2\|_{L^2} \\ &\leq \|\alpha_1 h(\nabla u_n - w_n) - \alpha_1 h(\nabla u - w)\|_{L^2} (\|v_1\|_{H^1} + \|v_2\|_{H^1}) \\ &\quad + \|\alpha_0 h(\mathcal{E}w_n) - \alpha_0 h(\mathcal{E}w)\|_{L^2} \|\mathcal{E}\|_{\mathcal{L}} (\|v_1\|_{H^1} + \|v_2\|_{H^1}) \end{aligned}$$

which instantly implies

$$\begin{aligned} \|N(\alpha)x_n - N(\alpha)x\|_{\mathbb{H}_1^*} &\leq C_1 \|\alpha_1 h(\nabla u_n - w_n) - \alpha_1 h(\nabla u - w)\|_{L^2} \\ &\quad + \|\alpha_1 h(\mathcal{E}w_n) - \alpha_1 h(\mathcal{E}w)\|_{L^2} \end{aligned} \quad (5.23)$$

for some constant $C_1 > 0$, which involves embedding constants and norm-equivalence constants, stemming from different equivalent product-norms on \mathbb{V} . Now observe, that the superposition operator $v \mapsto \alpha h(v(\cdot))$ is continuous from $L^2(\Omega; X)$ to $L^2(\Omega; X)$ for any $\alpha \in L^2(\Omega)$. This can be seen similarly to the discussion in Lemma 5 and also by theorem 4 in [GKT92]. Hence we obtain from (5.23)

$$\|N(\alpha)x_n - N(\alpha)x\|_{\mathbb{H}_1^*} \longrightarrow 0 \quad \text{as } n \rightarrow \infty$$

which gives the continuity of $N(\alpha) : \mathbb{H}_1 \rightarrow \mathbb{H}_1^*$. Moreover, we conclude from the monotonicity of $N(\alpha) : \mathbb{H}_1 \rightarrow \mathbb{H}_1^*$ and the strong monotonicity of $A : \mathbb{H}_1 \rightarrow \mathbb{H}_1^*$, that the operator

$$x \mapsto g(x, \alpha) = Ax + N(\alpha)x \quad (5.24)$$

is still κ -strongly monotone as a mapping from \mathbb{H}_1 to \mathbb{H}_1^* . In addition the operator in (5.24) is coercive in the sense of chapter 2, since strong monotonicity implies coercivity. Gathering all that information together, we conclude, that the operator (5.24) is strongly monotone, continuous and coercive. Hence, by Browder Minty theorem, the operator equation $g(\cdot, \alpha) = 0$ in \mathbb{H}_1^* has a unique solution $x = S(\alpha)$.

We will now show the Lipschitz property (5.20).

For that purpose consider $\alpha^1, \alpha^2 \in W_{ad}$ and arbitrary elements in the corresponding solution map $x_i = (u_i, w_i) = S(\alpha^i)$ for $i = 1, 2$. By the definition of the solution operator it again holds

$$\langle g(x_1, \alpha^1), v \rangle_{\mathbb{H}_1^*, \mathbb{H}_1} = \langle Ax_1, v \rangle_{\mathbb{H}_1^*, \mathbb{H}_1} + \langle N(\alpha^1)x_1, v \rangle_{\mathbb{H}_1^*, \mathbb{H}_1} = 0 \quad (5.25)$$

$$\langle g(x_2, \alpha^2), v \rangle_{\mathbb{H}_1^*, \mathbb{H}_1} = \langle Ax_2, v \rangle_{\mathbb{H}_1^*, \mathbb{H}_1} + \langle N(\alpha^2)x_2, v \rangle_{\mathbb{H}_1^*, \mathbb{H}_1} = 0 \quad (5.26)$$

for every $v \in \mathbb{H}_1$. Moreover, by the definition of $g(\cdot, \cdot)$, in particular by the linearity of $\alpha \mapsto N(\alpha)x$, we obtain for every $x, v \in \mathbb{H}_1$

$$\langle g(x, \alpha^1) - g(x, \alpha^2), v \rangle_{\mathbb{H}_1^*, \mathbb{H}_1} = \langle N(\alpha^1 - \alpha^2)x, v \rangle_{\mathbb{H}_1^*, \mathbb{H}_1} \quad \text{for every } v \in \mathbb{H}_1$$

Taking into account the latter equation together with (5.25) from (5.26), we infer

$$\begin{aligned} \langle g(x_2, \boldsymbol{\alpha}^1) - g(x_1, \boldsymbol{\alpha}^1), v \rangle_{\mathbb{H}_1^*, \mathbb{H}_1} &= \langle g(x_2, \boldsymbol{\alpha}^1) - g(x_2, \boldsymbol{\alpha}^2), v \rangle_{\mathbb{H}_1^*, \mathbb{H}_1} \\ &= \langle N(\boldsymbol{\alpha}^1 - \boldsymbol{\alpha}^2) x_2, v \rangle_{\mathbb{H}_1^*, \mathbb{H}_1} \quad \text{for every } v \in \mathbb{H}_1 \end{aligned} \quad (5.27)$$

The right hand side of the last equation can now be estimated via multiple application of Hölders inequality:

$$\begin{aligned} \langle N(\boldsymbol{\alpha}^1 - \boldsymbol{\alpha}^2) x_2, v \rangle_{\mathbb{H}_1^*, \mathbb{H}_1} &= \int_{\Omega} (\alpha_1^1 - \alpha_1^2) h(\nabla u_2 - w_2) \cdot (\nabla v_1 - v_2) \, dx + \int_{\Omega} (\alpha_0^1 - \alpha_0^2) h(\mathcal{E}(w_2)) \cdot \mathcal{E} v_2 \, dx \\ &\leq \int_{\Omega} |\alpha_1^1 - \alpha_1^2| |h(\nabla u_2 - w_2)| |\nabla v_1 - v_2| \, dx + \int_{\Omega} |\alpha_0^1 - \alpha_0^2| |h(\mathcal{E} w_2)| |\mathcal{E} v_2| \, dx \\ &\leq \|\alpha_1^1 - \alpha_1^2\|_{L^2} \|h\|_{L^\infty} (\|v_1\|_{H^1} + \|v_2\|_{H^1}) + \|\alpha_0^1 - \alpha_0^2\|_{L^2} \|h\|_{L^\infty} \|\mathcal{E}\|_{\mathcal{L}} \|v_2\|_{H_1} \\ &\leq C_2 \|\boldsymbol{\alpha}^1 - \boldsymbol{\alpha}^2\|_{\mathbb{L}^2} \|v\|_{\mathbb{H}_1} \end{aligned} \quad (5.28)$$

for every $v \in \mathbb{H}_1$ and a constant $C_2 > 0$. Exploiting the strong monotonicity of $x \mapsto g(x, \boldsymbol{\alpha}^1)$, the assumptions on $\boldsymbol{\alpha}$ and the estimate in (5.28), equation (5.21) eventually implies

$$\kappa \|x_2 - x_1\|_{\mathbb{H}_1}^2 = \langle g(x_2, \boldsymbol{\alpha}^1) - g(x_1, \boldsymbol{\alpha}^1), x_2 - x_1 \rangle_{\mathbb{H}_1^*, \mathbb{H}_1} \leq C_2 \|\boldsymbol{\alpha}^2 - \boldsymbol{\alpha}^1\|_{\mathbb{L}^2} \|x_2 - x_1\|_{\mathbb{H}_1}$$

Dividing by $\kappa > 0$ and $\|x_2 - x_1\|_{\mathbb{H}_1}$, the assertion of the theorem follows by norm equivalence in the productspace $\mathbb{H}_1 = H^1(\Omega) \times H^1(\Omega; \mathbb{R}^n)$. \square

Remark 6. The proof of the previous theorem works also, if $A, B \in \mathbb{R}$ from Assumption 4 are non negative instead of strictly positive.

With the help of Theorem 34, the existence of solutions for $(\mathbb{P}_{\text{control}})$ can now be easily verified for the case, where the parameters are Sobolev functions.

Theorem 35 (Existence of the control problem). *Under Assumption 4 with the control space*

$$\mathbb{V} := \mathbb{H}^1(\Omega) := H^1(\Omega) \times H^1(\Omega) \quad (5.29)$$

the optimal control problem $(\mathbb{P}_{\text{control}})$ has at least one solution.

Proof. Let $(x_n, \boldsymbol{\alpha}_n)_{n \in \mathbb{N}} \subset \mathbb{H}^1(\Omega) \times W_{ad}$ be an infimizing sequence of admissible elements, i.e $x_n = (u_n, w_n) = S(\boldsymbol{\alpha}_n) \in \mathbb{H}_1$ for every $n \in \mathbb{N}$, where $S : W_{ad} \rightarrow \mathbb{H}_1$ is the solution map, defined in (5.19). By Theorem 34, this solution map is well defined and single valued on W_{ad} . In conclusion, such a sequence really exists. Exploiting the $\mathbb{H}^1(\Omega)$ -coercivity of

$$\boldsymbol{\alpha} \mapsto \frac{\lambda}{2} \left(\|\alpha_0\|_{H^1(\Omega)}^2 + \|\alpha_1\|_{H^1(\Omega)}^2 \right)$$

the $\mathbb{H}^1(\Omega)$ boundedness of $\{\boldsymbol{\alpha}_n\}_{n \in \mathbb{N}}$ follows from standard arguments. By the compact embedding $H^1(\Omega) \hookrightarrow L^2(\Omega)$ and the reflexivity of $\mathbb{H}^1(\Omega)$, there is an element $\boldsymbol{\alpha}^* \in \mathbb{H}^1(\Omega)$ such that (after selection of a subsequence)

$$\begin{aligned} \boldsymbol{\alpha}_n &\rightarrow \boldsymbol{\alpha}^* && \text{in } L^2(\Omega) \times L^2(\Omega) \\ \boldsymbol{\alpha}_n &\rightharpoonup \boldsymbol{\alpha}^* && \text{weakly in } H^1(\Omega) \times H^1(\Omega) \end{aligned}$$

Since $W_{ad} \subset \mathbb{V}$ is assumed to be closed and convex in \mathbb{V} it is also closed in the weak topology of \mathbb{V} . Hence $\boldsymbol{\alpha}^* \in W_{ad}$. Moreover, by Theorem 34, there is a unique element $x^* = (u^*, w^*) \in \mathbb{H}_1$ such that

$x^* = (u^*, w^*) = S(\alpha)$ and via the second claim in Theorem 34, namely the Lipschitz continuity of the solution operator we see that

$$\begin{aligned} u_n &\rightarrow u^* && \text{in } H^1(\Omega) \\ w_n &\rightarrow w^* && \text{in } H^1(\Omega; \mathbb{R}^n) \end{aligned}$$

The assertion of the theorem now follows from continuity of $u \mapsto \mathcal{F}(u)$ on $L^2(\Omega)$ and the weak lower semicontinuity of

$$\alpha \mapsto \frac{\lambda}{2} \left(\|\alpha_0\|_{H^1(\Omega)}^2 + \|\alpha_1\|_{H^1(\Omega)}^2 \right)$$

on $\mathbb{H}^1(\Omega)$. □

Remark 7. The above proof does not work, if we replace $\alpha \mapsto \lambda \|\alpha\|_{\mathbb{H}^1}^2$ by a term of lower regularity, for example $\alpha \mapsto \lambda \|\alpha\|_{\mathbb{L}^2(\Omega)}^2$. This is because, in that case we cannot extract a strong $\mathbb{L}^2(\Omega)$ convergent subsequence of the infimizing sequence. However this strong convergence is needed, as the cost functional $\mathcal{F}(\cdot)$ is in general not weakly lower semi-continuous, as indicated by the example in Remark 3.

5.3 Differentiability of the Solution Operator

The focus of this section lies on the derivation of the solution operator (5.19) on $W_{ad} \subset \mathbb{V}$ with respect to an appropriate normed subspace $\mathbb{V} \subset L^2(\Omega) \times L^2(\Omega)$ in order to state a first order optimality system for $(\mathbb{P}_{\text{control}})$. However it turns out, that the most natural choice $\mathbb{V} = H^1(\Omega) \times H^1(\Omega)$ leads to several difficulties, that are discussed in detail at the end of this section and which could not be solved by the author. Therefore we will stick to a more restrictive setting first and set for this section

$$\mathbb{V} := \mathbb{L}^\infty(\Omega) := L^\infty(\Omega) \times L^\infty(\Omega)$$

But also in this restrictive setting, the Frechét-differentiability of the solution operator $S : W_{ad} \rightarrow \mathbb{H}_1$ can not be shown via standard arguments. This is because the function $g(\cdot, \cdot)$ is not Frechet-differentiable as a mapping from $\mathbb{H}_1 \times \mathbb{V}$ to \mathbb{H}_1^* and consequently the classical implicit function theorem in Banach spaces, cf. [HPUU08] is not applicable. The main reason for that is the well known norm gap in the differentiability theory of superposition operators. The term 'norm gap' comes from the fact, that for $q \geq p$ the superposition operator

$$\phi : L^p(\Omega; X) \rightarrow L^q(\Omega; Y) \quad u \mapsto f(\cdot, u(\cdot))$$

can only be Frechét-differentiable, if the function $f(\cdot, \cdot)$ is affine in the second component. Here X, Y are some finite dimensional normed spaces and $f : \Omega \times X \rightarrow Y$ denotes a so called *Carathéodory function*. This statement and a lot more information can be found in [Kra76]. As a conclusion from the last lines, we infer that the nonlinear operator in (5.13)

$$\begin{aligned} N(\alpha) : \mathbb{H}_1 &\rightarrow \mathbb{H}_1^* \\ \langle N(\alpha)x, v \rangle_{\mathbb{H}_1^*, \mathbb{H}_1} &:= \int_{\Omega} \alpha_1 h(\nabla u - w) \cdot (\nabla v_1 - v_2) dx + \int_{\Omega} \alpha_0 h(\mathcal{E}w) \cdot \mathcal{E}v_2 dx \quad \text{for } v = (v_1, v_2) \in \mathbb{H}_1 \end{aligned}$$

and consequently $g(\cdot, \cdot)$ itself is not Frechét-differentiable, as the superposition operators generated by $f_i(x, u) = \alpha_i(x)h(u)$ are not affine in the second component.

To circumvent this issue, we will apply the classical regularity result in [Grö89] for second order quasilinear PDE's to get even higher regularity of the solution $x = S(\alpha)$ and combine it with the following version of the implicit function theorem by G. Wachsmuth, which has recently been used in the optimal control of quasi linear PDE's.

Theorem 36 (Wachsmuth, 2014). *Let Y^0, Y^+, U, Z^0 be Banach spaces such that $Y^+ \hookrightarrow Y^0$ dense and continuous. Let $e : Y^0 \times U \rightarrow Z^0$ be given and $(y_0, u_0) \in Y^+ \times U$ such that $e(y_0, u_0) = 0$ and the following holds true:*

1. $e : Y^+ \times U \rightarrow Z^0$ is Frechet-differentiable at (y_0, u_0) .
2. The partial derivative $e_y(y_0, u_0) \in \mathcal{L}(Y^+, Z^0)$ can be extended to an element of $\mathcal{L}(Y^0, Z^0)$ (denoted the same) and $e_y(y_0, u_0) \in \mathcal{L}(Y^0, Z^0)$ is bijective

Moreover, we assume that there exists a solution map $S : \mathcal{U} \rightarrow Y^+$, where \mathcal{U} is a neighborhood of u_0 , such that $e(S(u), u) = 0$ for all $u \in \mathcal{U}$ and that $S(\cdot)$ is Lipschitz continuous at u_0 , i.e

$$\|S(u) - S(u_0)\|_{Y^+} \leq L \|u - u_0\|_U$$

for all $u \in \mathcal{U}$ and some $L = L(u_0) > 0$.

Then the solution operator $S : \mathcal{U} \rightarrow Y^0$ is Fréchet-differentiable at u_0 and the derivative is given by

$$S'(u_0)[h] = -e_y(S(u_0), u_0)^{-1} \circ e_u(S(u_0), u_0)[h]$$

Proof. For a proof, we refer to [Wac14], Theorem 2.1. □

The next part of the section will tailor Theorem 36 to our situation. As the argumentation is pretty lengthy, it is beneficial to proceed in several steps and lemmata.

We start by showing, that the function

$$g : \mathbb{W}_{1,p} \times \mathbb{V} \rightarrow \mathbb{H}_1^* \quad \langle g(x, \alpha), v \rangle_{\mathbb{H}_1^*, \mathbb{H}_1} = \langle Ax, v \rangle_{\mathbb{H}_1^*, \mathbb{H}_1} + \langle N(\alpha)x, v \rangle_{\mathbb{H}_1^*, \mathbb{H}_1}$$

is Fréchet-differentiable for every $p > 2$. The operators $A, N : \mathbb{H}_1 \rightarrow \mathbb{H}_1^*$ are defined as in the definition of $(\mathbb{P}_{\text{control}})$. To do so, we study first differentiability properties of the superposition operator, associated with $\alpha_i h(\cdot)$.

Lemma 5 (Differentiability of the nonlinearity). *Let $X \in \{\mathbb{R}^n, \mathbb{R}^{n \times n}\}$. Then the function*

$$\Phi : L^q(\Omega) \times L^p(\Omega; X) \rightarrow L^2(\Omega; X) \quad \Phi(\alpha, u)(x) := \alpha(x)h(u(x))$$

is continuously Fréchet-differentiable for every $p > 2$ and $q \geq \max(2p/(p-2), 4)$, including the case $q = \infty$. The (continuous) partial Fréchet-derivatives are given by

$$\Phi'_1 : L^q(\Omega) \times L^p(\Omega; X) \rightarrow \mathcal{L}(L^q(\Omega), L^2(\Omega; X)) \quad \Phi'_1(\alpha, u)[v](x) = v(x)h(u(x)) \quad (5.30)$$

$$\Phi'_2 : L^q(\Omega) \times L^p(\Omega; X) \rightarrow \mathcal{L}(L^p(\Omega; X), L^2(\Omega; X)) \quad \Phi'_2(\alpha, u)[v](x) = \alpha(x)h'(u(x))[v(x)] \quad (5.31)$$

Moreover, if even $\alpha \in L^\infty(\Omega)$, then $\Phi'_2(\alpha, u) \in \mathcal{L}(L^p(\Omega; X), L^2(\Omega; X))$ admits a natural extension to

$$\hat{\Phi}'_2(\alpha, u) \in \mathcal{L}(L^2(\Omega; X), L^2(\Omega; X)) \quad \hat{\Phi}'_2(\alpha, u)[v](x) = \alpha(x)h'(u(x))v(x)$$

Proof. At first note, that indeed $\Phi(\cdot)$ maps all of $L^q(\Omega) \times L^p(\Omega; X)$ into $L^2(\Omega; X)$, since $L^q(\Omega) \hookrightarrow L^2(\Omega)$ for $q \geq 2p/p-2 \geq 2$ and $h(u(\cdot)) \in L^\infty(\Omega; X)$. Now we use the well known fact from analysis, see [CC71], section 2.6, that a function $F : X_1 \times X_2 \rightarrow Y$, mapping from a product of two Banach spaces X_1, X_2 into another Banach space Y is continuously Fréchet-differentiable, if and only if every partial Fréchet-derivative $F'_i : X_1 \times X_2 \rightarrow \mathcal{L}(X_i, Y)$ exists and is continuous.

Step 1: Show, that $\Phi'_1 : L^q(\Omega) \times L^p(\Omega; X) \rightarrow \mathcal{L}(L^q(\Omega), L^2(\Omega; X))$ exists and is continuous:

Since $\alpha \mapsto \Phi(\alpha, u)$ is linear and continuous from $L^q(\Omega)$ to $L^2(\Omega; X)$, we see that (5.30) must hold. For

the continuity, we take sequences , such that $\alpha_n \rightarrow \alpha$ in $L^q(\Omega)$ and $u_n \rightarrow u$ in $L^p(\Omega)$. We use the Cauchy-Schwartz inequality and obtain for every $v \in L^q(\Omega)$

$$\begin{aligned} \|\Phi'_1(\alpha_n, u_n)[v] - \Phi'_1(\alpha, u)[v]\|_{L^2}^2 &= \int_{\Omega} |h(u_n) - h(u)|^2 |v|^2 dx \leq \|h(u_n) - h(u)\|_{L^4}^2 \|v\|_{L^4}^2 \\ &\leq C^2 \|h(u_n) - h(u)\|_{L^4}^2 \|v\|_{L^q}^2 \end{aligned}$$

Where $C > 0$ is an embedding constant for $L^q(\Omega) \hookrightarrow L^4(\Omega)$. Hence, we infer

$$\|\Phi'_1(\alpha_n, u_n) - \Phi'_1(\alpha, u)\|_{\mathcal{L}} \leq C \|h(u_n) - h(u)\|_{L^4} \rightarrow 0 \quad (5.32)$$

Note, that the limit in (5.32) holds, since the superposition operator $u \rightarrow h(u(\cdot))$ is continuous from $L^p(\Omega; X)$ to $L^4(\Omega; X)$. This is again a consequence of theorem 4 in [GKT92] and the boundedness of $h(\cdot)$. By (5.32) Φ'_1 is continuous.

Step 2: Show, that $\Phi'_2 : L^q(\Omega) \times L^p(\Omega; X) \rightarrow \mathcal{L}(L^p(\Omega; X), L^2(\Omega; X))$ exists and is continuous.

Introduce now the function

$$f : \Omega \times X \rightarrow X \quad (x, u) \mapsto \alpha(x)h(u)$$

Since $u \mapsto f(x, u)$ is C^1 for a.e. $x \in \Omega$, it's clearly Carathéodory. Moreover the associated Nemytskii operator

$$F_{\alpha} : L^p(\Omega; X) \rightarrow L^2(\Omega; X) \quad F_{\alpha}(u)(x) = \alpha(x)h(u(x))$$

maps all of $L^p(\Omega; X)$ into $L^q(\Omega; X) \hookrightarrow L^2(\Omega; X)$, since $|h(\cdot)| \leq 1$ and $\alpha \in L^q(\Omega)$. This implies, that $F_{\alpha} : L^p(\Omega; X) \rightarrow L^2(\Omega; X)$ is well-defined and continuous, cf. [GKT92], theorem 4. Now consider the partial derivative

$$f'_u : \Omega \times X \rightarrow \mathcal{L}(X) \quad f'_u(x, u)[v] = \alpha(x)h'(u)[v] \quad \text{for } v \in X$$

Again we see, that $f'_u(\cdot, \cdot)$ is Carathéodory, since $h' : X \rightarrow \mathcal{L}(X)$ is continuous. Now introduce the associated superposition operator

$$G_{\alpha} : L^p(\Omega; X) \rightarrow L^r(\Omega; \mathcal{L}(X)) \quad G_{\alpha}(u)(x) = f'_u(x, u(x)) \in \mathcal{L}(X) \quad (5.33)$$

By the same argumentation as above, recall that $h'(u(\cdot)) \in L^{\infty}(\Omega; \mathcal{L}(X))$, we see, that $G_{\alpha} : L^p(\Omega; X) \rightarrow L^r(\Omega; \mathcal{L}(X))$ is also well-defined and even continuous for $r = 2p/(p-2)$. Therefore the conditions of [GKT92], theorem 7 are satisfied and $F_{\alpha} : L^p(\Omega; X) \rightarrow L^2(\Omega; X)$ is continuously differentiable with derivative $u \mapsto DF_{\alpha}(u) \in \mathcal{L}(L^p(\Omega), L^2(\Omega))$, $u \in L^p(\Omega)$ and it holds

$$\Phi'_2(\alpha, u)[v](x) = DF_{\alpha}(u)[v](x) = G_{\alpha}(u)(x)[v(x)] = \alpha(x)h'(u(x))[v(x)] \quad \text{for every } v \in L^p(\Omega)$$

For the continuity of $\Phi'_2 : L^q(\Omega) \times L^p(\Omega; X) \rightarrow \mathcal{L}(L^p(\Omega; X), L^2(\Omega; X))$ we take again sequences such that $u_n \rightarrow u$ in $L^p(\Omega; X)$ and $\alpha_n \rightarrow \alpha$ in $L^q(\Omega)$. Then for $v \in L^p(\Omega; X)$ it holds

$$\|\Phi'_2(\alpha_n, u_n)[v] - \Phi'_2(\alpha, u)[v]\|_{L^2} \leq \|\Phi'_2(\alpha_n, u_n)[v] - \Phi'_2(\alpha, u_n)[v]\|_{L^2} + \|\Phi'_2(\alpha, u_n)[v] - \Phi'_2(\alpha, u)[v]\|_{L^2} \quad (5.34)$$

For the first term, we obtain the estimate

$$\begin{aligned} \|\Phi'_2(\alpha_n, u_n)[v] - \Phi'_2(\alpha, u_n)[v]\|_{L^2}^2 &\leq \int_{\Omega} |\alpha_n - \alpha|^2 |h'(u_n)|^2 |v|^2 dx \leq \|h'\|_{L^{\infty}}^2 \|\alpha_n - \alpha\|_{L^q}^2 \|v\|_{L^p}^2 \\ &\leq C \|h'\|_{L^{\infty}}^2 \|\alpha_n - \alpha\|_{L^q}^2 \|v\|_{L^p}^2 \end{aligned}$$

with an embedding constant $C > 0$ for $L^q \hookrightarrow L^r$ and $r = 2p/(p-2)$ as in (5.33). For the second term in (5.34) we get similarly

$$\|\Phi'_2(\alpha, u_n)[v] - \Phi'_2(\alpha, u)[v]\|_{L^2}^2 \leq \|G_{\alpha}(u_n) - G_{\alpha}(u)\|_{L^r}^2 \|v\|_{L^p}^2$$

in terms of the continuous superposition operator G_u , defined in (5.33). Thus it holds

$$\|\Phi'_2(\alpha_n, u_n) - \Phi'_2(\alpha, u)\|_{\mathcal{L}} \leq C \|h'\|_{L^\infty} \|\alpha_n - \alpha\|_{L^q} + \|G_\alpha(u_n) - G_\alpha(u)\|_{L^r} \longrightarrow 0$$

Thus the continuity of the Frechét-derivative was shown. That in case of $\alpha \in L^\infty(\Omega)$ the partial derivative $\Phi'_2(\alpha, u) \in \mathcal{L}(L^p(\Omega; X), L^2(\Omega; X))$ can be canonically extended to

$$\hat{\Phi}'_2(\alpha, u) \in \mathcal{L}(L^2(\Omega; X), L^2(\Omega; X)) \quad \hat{\Phi}'_2(\alpha, u)[v](x) = \alpha(x)h'(u(x))v(x)$$

is clear, by the boundedness of $\alpha(\cdot)h'(\cdot)$. This cannot be ensured, if $\alpha \notin L^\infty(\Omega)$. \square

Remark 8. The assumptions of the above lemma can be weakened in the sense that the proof works also for $\alpha \in L^q(\Omega)$ with $q > 2p/(p-2)$. However, this requires to work more carefully with the estimates and the exponents. For our purposes, the statement above is sufficient.

Utilizing the last lemma in combination with the classical chain rule, we can now write down the differential of $g : \mathbb{W}_{1,p} \times \mathbb{V} \rightarrow \mathbb{H}_1^*$.

For a fixed point $(x_0, \alpha_0) \in \mathbb{H}_1 \times \mathbb{V}$, we define therefore the linear and continuous operators

$$\begin{aligned} D_1, D_2(x_0, \alpha_0), D(x_0, \alpha_0) : \mathbb{H}_1 &\rightarrow \mathbb{H}_1^* & D_3(x_0) : L^2(\Omega) \times L^2(\Omega) &\rightarrow \mathbb{H}_1^* \\ \langle D_1 x, v \rangle_{\mathbb{H}_1^*, \mathbb{H}_1} &:= \langle K^* K u, v_1 \rangle_{L^2} + \mu_1 \langle u, v_1 \rangle_{L^2} + \mu_2 \langle \nabla u, \nabla v_1 \rangle_{L^2} + \eta \langle w, v_2 \rangle_{H^1} \\ \langle D_2(x_0, \alpha_0)x, v \rangle_{\mathbb{H}_1^*, \mathbb{H}_1} &:= \int_{\Omega} \alpha_{0,1} h'(\nabla u_0 - w_0) [\nabla u - w] \cdot (\nabla v_1 - v_2) \, dx \\ &\quad + \int_{\Omega} \alpha_{0,0} h'(\mathcal{E} w_0) [\mathcal{E} w] \cdot (\mathcal{E} v_2) \, dx \\ \langle D_3(x_0)v_\alpha, v \rangle_{\mathbb{H}_1^*, \mathbb{H}_1} &:= \int_{\Omega} v_{\alpha,1} h(\nabla u_0 - w_0) \cdot (\nabla v_1 - v_2) \, dx + \int_{\Omega} v_{\alpha,0} h(\mathcal{E} w_0) \cdot \mathcal{E} v_2 \, dx \\ \langle D(x_0, \alpha_0)v_\alpha, v \rangle_{\mathbb{H}_1^*, \mathbb{H}_1} &:= \langle D_1 x, v \rangle_{\mathbb{H}_1^*, \mathbb{H}_1} + \langle D_2(x_0, \alpha_0)x, v \rangle_{\mathbb{H}_1^*, \mathbb{H}_1} \end{aligned} \quad (5.35)$$

The Frechét-differential of the function $g : \mathbb{W}_{1,p} \times \mathbb{V} \rightarrow \mathbb{H}_1^*$ at some point $(x_0, \alpha_0) \in \mathbb{W}_{1,p} \times \mathbb{V}$ for any exponent $p > 2$ can then be expressed in terms of the above defined operators. In fact the partial derivatives are given by

$$\begin{aligned} D_x g(x_0, \alpha_0) &\in \mathcal{L}(\mathbb{W}_{1,p}, \mathbb{H}_1^*) & \langle D_x g(x_0, \alpha_0)x, v \rangle_{\mathbb{H}_1^*, \mathbb{H}_1} &= \langle D(x_0, \alpha_0)x, v \rangle_{\mathbb{H}_1^*, \mathbb{H}_1} \\ D_\alpha g(x_0, \alpha_0) &\in \mathcal{L}(\mathbb{V}, \mathbb{H}_1^*) & \langle D_\alpha g(x_0, \alpha_0)v_\alpha, v \rangle_{\mathbb{H}_1^*, \mathbb{H}_1} &= \langle D_3(x_0)v_\alpha, v \rangle_{\mathbb{H}_1^*, \mathbb{H}_1} \end{aligned} \quad (5.36)$$

For $(x_0, \alpha_0) \in \mathbb{W}_{1,p} \times \mathbb{V}$, $v \in \mathbb{H}_1$. Note, that the operators defined in (5.35) are well defined for a broader class of arguments, even for $(x_0, \alpha_0) \in \mathbb{H}_1 \times \mathbb{V}$ and $x, v \in \mathbb{H}_1$, but in this case, they have nothing to do with the Frechét-derivative $Dg(x_0, \alpha_0) \in \mathcal{L}(\mathbb{W}_{1,p} \times \mathbb{V}, \mathbb{H}_1^*)$ for $p > 2$ anymore.

However, the operator $D(x_0, \alpha_0) \in \mathcal{L}(\mathbb{H}_1, \mathbb{H}_1^*)$ defined in (5.35) can be seen as a natural extension of $D_x g(x_0, \alpha_0) \in \mathcal{L}(\mathbb{W}_{1,p}, \mathbb{H}_1^*)$ to the space $\mathcal{L}(\mathbb{H}_1, \mathbb{H}_1^*)$. The next theorem discusses the continuous invertibility of this extension, which will be also useful later when looking for first order conditions with the adjoint method.

Theorem 37 (Invertibility of the extended partial differential). *Let $(x_0, \alpha_0) \in \mathbb{H}_1 \times \mathbb{V}$ and $\alpha_0 \in W_{ad}$ with $\mathbb{V} = L^\infty(\Omega) \times L^\infty(\Omega)$. Moreover let Assumption 4 hold true in that regime. Then the operator*

$$D(x_0, \alpha_0) \in \mathcal{L}(\mathbb{H}_1, \mathbb{H}_1^*) \quad (5.37)$$

defined in (5.35) is continuously invertible.

Proof. We proceed similarly as in the proof of Theorem 34. However, we just need Lax-Milgram theorem from chapter 2, instead of monotone operator theory, since we only deal with linear problems. Exactly like in the proof of Theorem 34 we then see, that the operator $D_1 : \mathbb{H}_1 \rightarrow \mathbb{H}_1^*$ is coercive and continuous, which implies the existence of constants $0 < c_1, c_2$ with

$$\begin{aligned} |\langle D_1 x, v \rangle_{\mathbb{H}_1^*, \mathbb{H}_1}| &\leq c_2 \|x\|_{\mathbb{H}_1} \|v\|_{\mathbb{H}_1} \quad \text{for every } x, v \in \mathbb{H}_1 \\ \langle D_1 x, x \rangle_{\mathbb{H}_1^*, \mathbb{H}_1} &\geq c_1 \|x\|_{\mathbb{H}_1}^2 \quad \text{for every } x \in \mathbb{H}_1 \end{aligned} \quad (5.38)$$

Using the fact, that $h'(x)[y] \cdot y \geq 0$ for $x, y \in X$, cf. Theorem 32, we obtain for every $x \in \mathbb{H}_1$ that

$$\begin{aligned} \int_{\Omega} \alpha_{0,1} h'(\nabla u_0 - w_0)[\nabla u - w] \cdot (\nabla u - w) \, dx &\geq 0 \\ \int_{\Omega} \alpha_{0,0} h'(\mathcal{E} w_0)[\mathcal{E} w] \cdot (\mathcal{E} w) \, dx &\geq 0 \end{aligned} \quad (5.39)$$

leading to

$$\langle D_2(x_0, \alpha_0)x, x \rangle_{\mathbb{H}_1^*, \mathbb{H}_1} \geq 0 \quad \text{for every } x \in \mathbb{H}_1$$

Moreover, the continuity of $D_2(x_0, \alpha_0) : \mathbb{H}_1 \rightarrow \mathbb{H}_1^*$ can be deduced from the following estimates, which take into account the boundedness of $\alpha_i h'(\cdot)$:

$$\begin{aligned} \langle D_2(x_0, \alpha_0)x, v \rangle_{\mathbb{H}_1^*, \mathbb{H}_1} &\leq \|\alpha_{0,1} h'_{\gamma}(\nabla u_0 - w_0)\|_{L^\infty} \|\nabla u - w\|_{L^2} \|\nabla v_1 - v_2\|_{L^2} + \|\alpha_{0,0} h'_{\gamma}(\mathcal{E} w_0)\|_{L^\infty} \|\mathcal{E}\|_{\mathcal{L}}^2 \|w\|_{H^1} \|v_2\|_{H^1} \\ &\leq C \left(\|\alpha_{0,1} h'_{\gamma}(\nabla u_0 - w_0)\|_{L^\infty} + \|\alpha_{0,0} h'_{\gamma}(\mathcal{E} w_0)\|_{L^\infty} \|\mathcal{E}\|_{\mathcal{L}}^2 \right) \|x\|_{\mathbb{H}_1} \|v\|_{\mathbb{H}_1} \end{aligned}$$

Again in the last lines, $C > 0$ denotes some constant. Combining the above estimates with (5.38) and (5.39), we obtain

$$\begin{aligned} |\langle D(x_0, \alpha_0)x, v \rangle_{\mathbb{H}_1^*, \mathbb{H}_1}| &\leq c_3 \|x\|_{\mathbb{H}_1} \|v\|_{\mathbb{H}_1} \\ \langle D(x_0, \alpha_0)x, x \rangle_{\mathbb{H}_1^*, \mathbb{H}_1} &\geq c_1 \|x\|_{\mathbb{H}_1}^2 \end{aligned}$$

for every $x, v \in \mathbb{H}_1$. Notice, that we set here

$$0 < c_3 := c_1 + C \left(\|\alpha_{0,1} h'_{\gamma}(\nabla u_0 - w_0)\|_{L^\infty} + \|\alpha_{0,0} h'_{\gamma}(\mathcal{E} w_0)\|_{L^\infty} \|\mathcal{E}\|_{\mathcal{L}}^2 \right) < \infty$$

By Lax-Milgram theorem, the assertion of the theorem follows. \square

Eventually we are now well prepared for presenting the proof of the Frechét-differentiability of the solution operator (5.19).

Theorem 38 (Differentiability of the solution operator). *Let again Assumption 4 be fulfilled for*

$$W_{ad} \subset \mathbb{V} := \mathbb{L}^\infty(\Omega) = L^\infty(\Omega) \times L^\infty(\Omega)$$

Moreover, fix an element $\alpha_0 \in W_{ad}$ and the corresponding solution $x_0 = S(\alpha_0) \in \mathbb{H}_1$. Then

1. there is a positive radius $R > 0$ such that $S : B_R(\alpha_0) \rightarrow \mathbb{H}_1$ is well-defined and single valued.
2. $S : B_R(\alpha_0) \rightarrow \mathbb{H}_1$ is Frechét-differentiable at $\alpha_0 \in \mathbb{V}$ with respect to the norm of \mathbb{V} and the derivative $z := DS(\alpha_0)[v_\alpha] \in \mathbb{H}_1$ for a direction $v_\alpha \in \mathbb{V}$ is given by the unique solution of the linearized equation

$$\begin{aligned} &\langle K^* K z_1, v_1 \rangle_{L^2} + \mu_K \langle z_1, v_1 \rangle_{L^2} + \mu \langle \nabla z_1, \nabla v_1 \rangle_{L^2} + \eta \langle z_2, v_2 \rangle_{H^1} \\ &+ \int_{\Omega} \alpha_{0,1} h'(\nabla u_0 - w_0)[\nabla z_1 - z_2] \cdot (\nabla v_1 - v_2) \, dx + \int_{\Omega} \alpha_{0,0} h'(\mathcal{E} w_0)[\mathcal{E} z_2] \cdot (\mathcal{E} v_2) \, dx \\ &= - \int_{\Omega} v_{\alpha,1} h(\nabla u_0 - w_0) \cdot (\nabla v_1 - v_2) \, dx - \int_{\Omega} v_{\alpha,0} h(\mathcal{E} w_0) \cdot \mathcal{E} v_2 \, dx \end{aligned} \quad (5.40)$$

for every $v \in \mathbb{H}_1$

Proof. First, note that the linearized equation (5.40) can be shortly written as

$$\langle D(x_0, \boldsymbol{\alpha}_0)z, v \rangle_{\mathbb{H}_1^*, \mathbb{H}_1} = - \langle D_{\boldsymbol{\alpha}} g(x_0) v_{\boldsymbol{\alpha}}, v \rangle_{\mathbb{H}_1^*, \mathbb{H}_1}$$

In terms of the operators, defined in (5.35) and thus, by Theorem 37 the linearized equation admits a unique solution $z \in \mathbb{H}_1$. The existence of a radius $R > 0$, such that the first claim of the theorem holds, is an easy consequence of the fact, that the set

$$M := \{ \boldsymbol{\alpha} \in \mathbb{V} \mid \alpha_i(\cdot) \geq A > 0 \text{ for some constant } A > 0, i = 0, 1 \}$$

is open in the $\mathbb{L}^\infty(\Omega)$ topology, and clearly $\boldsymbol{\alpha} \in W_{ad} \subset M$ by Assumption 4. In fact, we choose $R > 0$ such that $B_R(\boldsymbol{\alpha}_0) \subset M$. Then the elements in $B_R(\boldsymbol{\alpha}_0)$ are still positive uniformly bounded away from zero and we may apply Theorem 34 to see, that $S(\boldsymbol{\alpha})$ is single valued for all those $\boldsymbol{\alpha} \in B_R(\boldsymbol{\alpha}_0)$. For the rest of the proof, we proceed in two steps:

Step 1: Show, that the solution operator actually maps into a space of higher regularity, i.e. there is a $p_0 > 2$ such that

$$S: B_R(\boldsymbol{\alpha}_0) \rightarrow \mathbb{W}_{1, p_0} \quad (5.41)$$

and there is a constant $L = L(\boldsymbol{\alpha}_0) > 0$, such that for every $\boldsymbol{\alpha} \in B_R(\boldsymbol{\alpha}_0)$

$$\|x - x_0\|_{\mathbb{W}_{1, p}} \leq L \|\boldsymbol{\alpha} - \boldsymbol{\alpha}_0\|_{\mathbb{L}^\infty} \quad \text{for } x = S(\boldsymbol{\alpha}) \quad (5.42)$$

To prove those two assertions, we define the operators

$$\begin{aligned} A_i, N(\boldsymbol{\alpha}) &: \mathbb{H}_1 \rightarrow \mathbb{H}_1^* \quad i = 1, 2, 3 \\ \langle A_1 x, v \rangle_{\mathbb{H}_1^*, \mathbb{H}_1} &:= \langle u, v_1 \rangle_{L^2} \\ \langle A_2 x, v \rangle_{\mathbb{H}_1^*, \mathbb{H}_1} &:= \langle K^* K u - K^* f, v_1 \rangle_{L^2} \\ \langle A_3 x, v \rangle_{\mathbb{H}_1^*, \mathbb{H}_1} &:= \mu_K \langle u, v_1 \rangle_{L^2} + \mu \langle \nabla u, \nabla v_1 \rangle_{L^2} + \eta \langle w, v_2 \rangle_H \\ \langle N(\boldsymbol{\alpha}) x, v \rangle_{\mathbb{H}_1^*, \mathbb{H}_1} &= \int_{\Omega} \alpha_1 h(\nabla u - w) \cdot (\nabla v_1 - v_2) \, dx + \int_{\Omega} \alpha_0 h(\mathcal{E} w) \cdot \mathcal{E} v_2 \, dx \end{aligned}$$

By definition of the solution operator (5.19) we see, that any $x = S(\boldsymbol{\alpha}) \in \mathbb{H}_1$ for $\boldsymbol{\alpha} \in B_R(\boldsymbol{\alpha}_0)$ has to satisfy

$$\langle A_1 x + A_3 x, v \rangle_{\mathbb{H}_1^*, \mathbb{H}_1} + \langle N(\boldsymbol{\alpha}_0) x, v \rangle_{\mathbb{H}_1^*, \mathbb{H}_1} = - \langle A_1 + A_2 x, v \rangle_{\mathbb{H}_1^*, \mathbb{H}_1} + \langle N(\boldsymbol{\alpha}_0 - \boldsymbol{\alpha}) x, v \rangle_{\mathbb{H}_1^*, \mathbb{H}_1} \quad (5.43)$$

The Operator on left hand side of (5.43) can be written in a strong form as

$$\begin{bmatrix} \mu_K u + u - \mu \Delta u \\ \eta w + \eta \Delta w \end{bmatrix} + \begin{bmatrix} -\operatorname{div} & 0 \\ -Id & -\operatorname{div} \end{bmatrix} \cdot \begin{bmatrix} \alpha_{0,1} h(\nabla u - w) \\ \alpha_{0,0} h(\mathcal{E} w) \end{bmatrix} : \mathbb{H}_1 \rightarrow \mathbb{H}_1^*$$

This operator is a second order quasilinear partial differential operator, which satisfies the assumption of the theorem 1 in [Grö89], cf. also the discussion in [RSV17]. This regularity theorem ensures, that there is an exponent $p_0 > 2$ such that

$$A_1 + A_3 + N(\boldsymbol{\alpha}_0) : \mathbb{W}_{1, p_0} \rightarrow \mathbb{W}_{-1, p_0} := (\mathbb{W}_{1, q_0})^* \quad (5.44)$$

is continuously invertible and the inverse is even Lipschitz continuous. Here $q_0 < 2$ is the conjugate exponent with $1/p_0 + 1/q_0 = 1$. The invertibility of the operator in (5.44) guarantees (5.41).

Now we use this Lipschitz-continuity of

$$[A_1 + A_3 + N(\boldsymbol{\alpha}_0)]^{-1} : \mathbb{W}_{-1, p_0} \rightarrow \mathbb{W}_{1, p_0}$$

in combination with equation (5.43) to deduce, that for every $x = S(\boldsymbol{\alpha}) \in \mathbb{W}_{1,p_0}$ the following holds true:

$$\|x - x_0\|_{\mathbb{W}_{1,p_0}} \leq L \left(\|A_1 x_0 - A_1 x\|_{\mathbb{W}_{-1,p_0}} + \|A_2 x_0 - A_2 x\|_{\mathbb{W}_{-1,p_0}} + \|N(\boldsymbol{\alpha}_0 - \boldsymbol{\alpha})x\|_{\mathbb{W}_{-1,p_0}} \right) \quad (5.45)$$

We will estimate every term on the right hand side of the last line separately. Therefore fix $v \in \mathbb{W}_{1,q_0}$ and derive

$$\begin{aligned} |\langle A_1 x_0 - A_1 x, v \rangle_{\mathbb{W}_{-1,p_0}, \mathbb{W}_{1,q_0}}| &\leq C \|u_0 - u\|_{L^2} \|v\|_{\mathbb{W}_{1,q_0}} \\ |\langle A_2 x_0 - A_2 x, v \rangle_{\mathbb{W}_{-1,p_0}, \mathbb{W}_{1,q_0}}| &\leq C_1 \|K^* K\|_{\mathcal{L}} \|u_0 - u\|_{L^2} \|v\|_{\mathbb{W}_{1,q_0}} \\ |\langle N(\boldsymbol{\alpha}_0 - \boldsymbol{\alpha})x, v \rangle_{\mathbb{W}_{-1,p_0}, \mathbb{W}_{1,q_0}}| &\leq C_1 \left(\|(\alpha_{0,1} - \alpha_0) h_\gamma(\nabla u - w)\|_{L^\infty} + \|(\alpha_{0,0} - \alpha_1) h_\gamma(\mathcal{E}w)\|_{L^\infty} \|\mathcal{E}\|_{\mathcal{L}} \right) \|v\|_{\mathbb{W}_{1,q_0}} \end{aligned}$$

Where $C_1 > 0$ is again a generic positive number, involving several embedding constants. The next inequality is obtained by inserting these estimates into (5.45):

$$\begin{aligned} \|x - x_0\|_{\mathbb{W}_{1,p_0}} &\leq C_2 (\|K^* K\|_{\mathcal{L}} + 1) \|u - u_0\|_{L^2} \\ &\quad + C_2 \left(\|(\alpha_{0,1} - \alpha_1) h_\gamma(\nabla u - w)\|_{L^\infty} + \|(\alpha_{0,0} - \alpha_0) h_\gamma(\mathcal{E}w)\|_{L^\infty} \|\mathcal{E}\|_{\mathcal{L}} \right) \\ &\leq C_2 (\|K^* K\|_{\mathcal{L}} + 1) \|u - u_0\|_{L^2} + C_1 \|\boldsymbol{\alpha}_0 - \boldsymbol{\alpha}\|_{\mathbb{L}^\infty} \end{aligned} \quad (5.46)$$

For some other constant $C_2 > 0$. Moreover from Theorem 34, statement 2. we get the Lipschitz estimate

$$\|u - u_0\|_{L^2} \leq L_1 \|\boldsymbol{\alpha}_0 - \boldsymbol{\alpha}\|_{\mathbb{L}^\infty}$$

Minding also inequality (5.46), the choice of

$$L = C_2 (\|K^* K\|_{\mathcal{L}} + 1) L_1 + C_1$$

results in the final claim (5.42) of step 1.

step2: Conclusion via Theorem 36.

In the notation of Theorem 36, we set $Y^0 := \mathbb{H}_1$, $Y^+ := \mathbb{W}_{1,p_0} \hookrightarrow Y^0$, $U := \mathbb{V} = \mathbb{L}^\infty(\Omega) = L^\infty(\Omega) \times L^\infty(\Omega)$, $Z^0 := \mathbb{H}_1^*$. For the function $g: Y^0 \times U \rightarrow Z^0$ and the element $(y_0, u_0) := (x_0, \boldsymbol{\alpha}_0) \in Y^+ \times U$, we obtain by the previous discussion in that chapter

1. $g: Y^+ \times U \rightarrow Z^0$ is Frechet-differentiable at (y_0, u_0) .
2. The partial derivative $g_y(y_0, u_0) \in \mathcal{L}(Y^+, Z^0)$ can be extended to an element of $\mathcal{L}(Y^0, Z^0)$ and $g_y(y_0, u_0) \in \mathcal{L}(Y^0, Z^0)$ is bijective, by Theorem 37. The extension is given by the operator in (5.37).

Moreover, by (5.41) the solution map $S: \mathcal{U} \rightarrow Y^+$, $\mathcal{U} := B_R(u_0)$ is well defined and single valued in the neighborhood \mathcal{U} of u_0 . In addition the Lipschitz condition at u_0 , i.e.

$$\|S(u) - S(u_0)\|_{Y^+} \leq L \|u - u_0\|_U$$

for all $u \in \mathcal{U}$ and some $L = L(u_0) > 0$ is also satisfied by (5.42). An application of the Wachsmut theorem yields the desired result. \square

Remark 9. The regularity theorem by Gröger has first been used for bilevel optimization in imaging in [RSV17] and has become a standard tool for proving differentiability of the solution operator for second order regularizers with some underlying quasi linear structure. In the first paper, the authors proved Fréchet-differentiability of the solution operator for the denoising case $K = id_{L^2}$ and constant parameters. Hence, the previous statement is a slight extension of that result. Originally, Gröger only proved the regularity result for C^2 -boundaries and domains that satisfy the so called *Gröger property*. However, the latter property also holds for convex bounded Lipschitz domains, see [Dau92], which is exactly our image domain.

The argumentation in the previous theorem relies on the fact, that the solution operator $S : \mathbb{V} \rightarrow \mathbb{L}^\infty(\Omega)$ is well defined and single-valued on a small $\mathbb{L}^\infty(\Omega)$ -neighborhood of any $\alpha_0 \in \mathbb{L}^\infty(\Omega) \cap W_{ad}$. A similar result for a small $H^1(\Omega) \times H^1(\Omega)$ - neighborhood of α_0 seems unattainable at the moment, since $H^1(\Omega) \times H^1(\Omega)$ -perturbations of α_0 , no matter how small, call them $\alpha \in H^1(\Omega) \times H^1(\Omega)$ are not necessarily positive componentwise anymore. This is due to fact, that $H^1(\Omega)$ does not embed into $L^\infty(\Omega)$ unless the spacedimension is one. As a consequence, the nonlinear operator (5.13) in the definition of $g(\cdot, \cdot)$, given by

$$\langle N(\alpha)x, v \rangle_{\mathbb{H}_1^*, \mathbb{H}_1} := \int_{\Omega} \alpha_0 h(\nabla u - w) \cdot (\nabla v_1 - v_2) dx + \int_{\Omega} \alpha_1 h(\mathcal{E}w) \cdot \mathcal{E}v_2 dx \quad (5.47)$$

cannot be guaranteed to be monotonous anymore. Also the more general monotonicity concept, called pseudomonotonicity, see [ZB89] cannot be applied, since the operator $N(\alpha) : \mathbb{H}_1 \rightarrow \mathbb{H}_1^*$ is also known to be not pseudo monotone, which is a consequence of the well known characterization of pseudo monotone operators by Boccardo et. al. [BD84]. To make it even more complicated, it can be shown, that $N(\alpha) : \mathbb{H}_1 \rightarrow \mathbb{H}_1^*$ is Hölder continuous, with any parameter $\beta \in (0, 1)$

$$\|N(\alpha)x_1 - N(\alpha)x_2\|_{\mathbb{H}_1^*} \leq L \|x_1 - x_2\|_{\mathbb{H}_1}^\beta$$

but Lipschitz continuity ($\beta = 1$) can not be achieved, since $\alpha \in H^1(\Omega) \times H^1(\Omega)$ is again perhaps unbounded. This makes it difficult to apply standard fixpoint techniques, which mostly require that the involved operator is even contractive. It may be possible that more sophisticated methods, like some (set valued) generalized implicit function theorem, for instance the version of Bartle and Graves, [Don96] or more general solution concepts from PDE theory can be applied to show that $S : B_R(\alpha_0) \rightarrow \mathbb{H}_1$ is still well defined and single valued for the choice of the parameter space $\mathbb{V} = H^1(\Omega) \times H^1(\Omega)$, but this requires further study, which is out of the scope of this thesis. However, we can state a differentiability result for

$$S : H^1(\Omega) \times H^1(\Omega) \rightarrow \mathbb{H}_1$$

which takes the local existence of the solution operator as a requirement.

Theorem 39 (Differentiability under existence assumption). *Let Assumption 4 hold true, but this time take*

$$W_{ad} \subset \mathbb{V} := H^1(\Omega) \times H^1(\Omega)$$

and fix an element $\alpha_0 \in W_{ad}$. Moreover assume, that there exists a single-valued solution operator

$$S : B_R(\alpha_0) \rightarrow \mathbb{H}_1$$

in a small \mathbb{V} -neighborhood of α_0 . Then S is Frechét-differentiable at α_0 with the Frechét derivative $DS(\alpha_0) \in \mathcal{L}(\mathbb{V}, \mathbb{H}_1)$ and its evaluation in direction $v_\alpha \in \mathbb{V}$ is given by the unique solution $z := DS(\alpha_0)[v_\alpha] \in \mathbb{H}_1$ of the linearized equation (5.40).

Proof. The proof is identical to the proof of Theorem 38. We skip it here, since the assumptions cannot be verified for the time being, compare the foregoing discussion. \square

5.4 Optimality System and Adjoint Based Descent Algorithm

This Section is devoted to the study of necessary first order conditions for stationary points of $(\mathbb{P}_{\text{control}})$. The method of choice will be a procedure, which is well known in the optimal control literature as **adjoint method**, see [HPUU08] for details. Furthermore, we will switch again back to the configuration

$$\mathbb{V} = \mathbb{H}^1(\Omega) = H^1(\Omega) \times H^1(\Omega)$$

and take the position of Theorem 39, that the solution operator $S : \mathbb{H}^1(\Omega) \rightarrow \mathbb{H}_1$ is well defined and single valued in a small $\mathbb{H}^1(\Omega)$ -neighborhood of W_{ad} , forgetting (for the moment) the discussion at the end of the last section, which dealt with the possible nonexistence of such a mapping. Consequently $S : W_{ad} \rightarrow \mathbb{H}_1$ is Frechét-differentiable and the derivative $DS(\boldsymbol{\alpha}) \in \mathcal{L}(\mathbb{V}, \mathbb{H}_1)$ at a point $\boldsymbol{\alpha} \in \mathbb{V}$ is given by

$$DS(\boldsymbol{\alpha}) [v_\alpha] = -D(S(\boldsymbol{\alpha}), \boldsymbol{\alpha})^{-1} \circ D_\alpha g(S(\boldsymbol{\alpha}), \boldsymbol{\alpha})[v_\alpha] \quad \text{for } v_\alpha \in \mathbb{V} \quad (5.48)$$

In terms of the operator $D(S(\boldsymbol{\alpha}), \boldsymbol{\alpha}) \in \mathcal{L}(\mathbb{H}_1, \mathbb{H}_1^*)$, which is defined in (5.35) as the extension of the Frechét-derivate $D_x g(S(\boldsymbol{\alpha}), \boldsymbol{\alpha}) \in \mathcal{L}(\mathbb{W}_{1,p_0}, \mathbb{H}_1^*)$ for some $p_0 > 2$.

$$\begin{aligned} D(S(\boldsymbol{\alpha}), \boldsymbol{\alpha})x, v \rangle_{\mathbb{H}} &= \langle K^* K z_1, v_1 \rangle_{L^2} + \mu_K \langle z_1, v_1 \rangle_{L^2} + \mu \langle \nabla z_1, \nabla v_1 \rangle_{L^2} + \eta \langle z_2, v_2 \rangle_{H^1} \\ &+ \int_{\Omega} \alpha_1 h'(\nabla u_0 - w_0) [\nabla z_1 - z_2] \cdot (\nabla v_1 - v_2) \, dx + \int_{\Omega} \alpha_0 h'(\mathcal{E} w_0) [\mathcal{E} z_2] \cdot (\mathcal{E} v_2) \, dx \end{aligned}$$

and the derivative $D_\alpha g(x_0, \boldsymbol{\alpha}) \in \mathcal{L}(\mathbb{V}, \mathbb{H}_1^*)$:

$$\langle D_\alpha g(x_0, \boldsymbol{\alpha}) v_\alpha, v \rangle_{\mathbb{H}_1^*, \mathbb{H}_1} := \int_{\Omega} v_{\alpha,0} h(\nabla u_0 - w_0) \cdot (\nabla v_1 - v_2) \, dx + \int_{\Omega} v_{\alpha,1} h(\mathcal{E} w_0) \cdot \mathcal{E} v_2 \, dx$$

We now consider the derivative of the upper level objective

$$\mathcal{J} : \mathbb{H}_1 \times \mathbb{V} \rightarrow \mathbb{R} \quad (x, \boldsymbol{\alpha}) \mapsto \mathcal{F}(x) + \mathcal{H}_\lambda(\boldsymbol{\alpha})$$

where we set for abbreviation

$$\mathcal{H}_\lambda : \mathbb{H}^1(\Omega) \rightarrow \mathbb{R}, \quad \boldsymbol{\alpha} \mapsto \frac{\lambda}{2} (\|\alpha_0\|_{H^1}^2 + \|\alpha_1\|_{H^1}^2)$$

By Assumption 4, the upper level objective is continuously Frechét-differentiable as a mapping from $\mathbb{H}_1 \times \mathbb{V}$ to \mathbb{R} and the derivative is given by

$$\begin{aligned} D\mathcal{J} : \mathbb{H}_1 \times \mathbb{V} &\rightarrow (\mathbb{H}_1 \times \mathbb{V})^* \\ \langle D\mathcal{J}(x, \boldsymbol{\alpha}), (v_x, v_\alpha) \rangle &= \langle D\mathcal{F}(x), v_x \rangle_{\mathbb{H}_1^*, \mathbb{H}_1} + \langle D\mathcal{H}_\lambda(\boldsymbol{\alpha}), v_\alpha \rangle_{\mathbb{V}^*, \mathbb{V}} \quad \text{for } v = (v_x, v_\alpha) \in \mathbb{H}_1 \times \mathbb{V} \end{aligned}$$

A common strategy to obtain first order conditions for control problems, is to consider the **reduced functional**, which is defined as

$$\hat{\mathcal{J}} : \mathbb{V} \supset W_{ad} \rightarrow \mathbb{R} \quad \boldsymbol{\alpha} \mapsto \mathcal{J}(S(\boldsymbol{\alpha}), \boldsymbol{\alpha})$$

Minding the classical chain rule, the reduced objective is differentiable and the first order conditions at a point $\boldsymbol{\alpha}_0 \in W_{ad}$ for solving $(\mathbb{P}_{\text{control}})$ simply read

$$\langle D\hat{\mathcal{J}}(\boldsymbol{\alpha}_0), \boldsymbol{\alpha} - \boldsymbol{\alpha}_0 \rangle_{\mathbb{V}^*, \mathbb{V}} \geq 0 \quad \text{for every } \boldsymbol{\alpha} \in W_{ad} \quad (5.49)$$

Moreover, the concrete formula for the differential of the reduced derivative can be computed via

$$\begin{aligned} \langle D\hat{\mathcal{J}}(\boldsymbol{\alpha}), v \rangle_{\mathbb{V}^*, \mathbb{V}} &= \langle D\mathcal{F}(S(\boldsymbol{\alpha})), DS(\boldsymbol{\alpha})v \rangle_{\mathbb{H}_1^*, \mathbb{H}_1} + \langle D\mathcal{H}_\lambda(\boldsymbol{\alpha}), v \rangle_{\mathbb{H}_1^*, \mathbb{H}_1} \\ &= \langle DS(\boldsymbol{\alpha})^* D\mathcal{F}(S(\boldsymbol{\alpha})), v \rangle_{\mathbb{H}_1^*, \mathbb{H}_1} + \langle D\mathcal{H}_\lambda(\boldsymbol{\alpha}), v \rangle_{\mathbb{H}_1^*, \mathbb{H}_1} \end{aligned}$$

where adjoint operator $DS(\boldsymbol{\alpha})^* \in \mathcal{L}(\mathbb{H}_1^*, \mathbb{H}_1^*)$ is given by

$$DS(\boldsymbol{\alpha})^* = -D_\alpha g(S(\boldsymbol{\alpha}), \boldsymbol{\alpha})^* \circ D(S(\boldsymbol{\alpha}), \boldsymbol{\alpha})^{-*}$$

Now introduce $x^* = x^*(\boldsymbol{\alpha}) \in \mathbb{H}_1^*$ as the unique solution of the equation

$$D(S(\boldsymbol{\alpha}), \boldsymbol{\alpha})^* x^* = -D\mathcal{F}(S(\boldsymbol{\alpha})) \quad \text{in } \mathbb{H}_1^*$$

Taking into account Theorem 37 and standard functional analysis, we ensure, that the adjoint operator on the lefthand side is also continuously invertible and such a solution really exists and is unique. Consequently the necessary first order optimality system for a locally optimal pair $(\bar{x}, \bar{\alpha}) \in \mathbb{H}_1 \times W_{ad}$ of $(\mathbb{P}_{\text{control}})$ is given by

$$\begin{aligned} g(\bar{x}, \bar{\alpha}) &= 0 && \text{in } \mathbb{H}_1^* \\ D(\bar{x}, \bar{\alpha})^* \bar{x}^* &= -D\mathcal{F}(\bar{x}) && \text{in } \mathbb{H}_1^* \\ \langle D_{\alpha} g(\bar{x}, \bar{\alpha})^* \bar{x}^*, \alpha - \bar{\alpha} \rangle_{\mathbb{H}_1^*, \mathbb{H}_1} + \langle D\mathcal{H}_{\lambda}(\bar{\alpha}), \alpha - \bar{\alpha} \rangle_{\mathbb{H}_1^*, \mathbb{H}_1} &\geq 0 && \text{for every } \alpha \in W_{ad} \end{aligned} \quad (5.50)$$

Identifying the Hilbert spaces $\mathbb{H}_1^{**} \simeq \mathbb{H}_1$ and inserting the concrete expressions for $g(\cdot, \cdot)$, $D(\bar{x}, \bar{\alpha})$ and $\mathcal{H}_{\lambda}(\cdot)$ into the abstract optimality system above, we obtain

Theorem 40 (First order optimality system). *Let $(\bar{x}, \bar{\alpha}) \in \mathbb{H}_1 \times W_{ad}$ be a solution of the optimal control problem $(\mathbb{P}_{\text{control}})$, then there exists an **adjoint state** $\bar{x}^* = \bar{x}^*(\bar{\alpha}) \in \mathbb{H}_1$ such that the following system is satisfied:*

$$\begin{aligned} 0 &= \langle K^* K \bar{u} - K^* f, v_1 \rangle_{L^2} + \mu_K \langle \bar{u}, v_1 \rangle_{L^2} + \mu \langle \nabla \bar{u}, \nabla v_1 \rangle_{L^2} + \eta \langle \bar{w}, v_2 \rangle_{H^1} && \text{(S)} \\ &\int_{\Omega} \bar{\alpha}_0 h(\nabla \bar{u} - \bar{w}) \cdot (\nabla v_1 - v_2) \, dx + \int_{\Omega} \bar{\alpha}_1 h(\mathcal{E} \bar{w}) \cdot \mathcal{E} v_2 \, dx && \text{for all } v \in \mathbb{H}_1 \\ -D\mathcal{F}(\bar{x})[v] &= \langle K^* K u^*, v_1 \rangle_{L^2} + \mu_K \langle \bar{u}^*, v_1 \rangle_{L^2} + \mu \langle \nabla \bar{u}^*, \nabla v_1 \rangle_{L^2} + \eta \langle \bar{w}^*, v_2 \rangle_{H^1} && \text{(A)} \\ &+ \int_{\Omega} \bar{\alpha}_1 h'(\nabla \bar{u} - \bar{w}) [\nabla \bar{u}^* - \bar{w}^*] \cdot (\nabla v_1 - v_2) \, dx \\ &+ \int_{\Omega} \bar{\alpha}_1 h'(\mathcal{E} \bar{w}) [\mathcal{E} \bar{w}^*] \cdot (\mathcal{E} v_2) \, dx && \text{for all } v \in \mathbb{H}_1 \\ 0 &\leq \int_{\Omega} (\alpha_1 - \bar{\alpha}_1) h(\nabla \bar{u} - \bar{w}) \cdot (\nabla \bar{u}^* - \bar{w}^*) \, dx + \int_{\Omega} (\alpha_0 - \bar{\alpha}_0) h(\mathcal{E} \bar{w}) \cdot \mathcal{E} \bar{w}^* \, dx && \text{(VI)} \\ &+ \lambda \langle \bar{\alpha}_0, \alpha_0 - \bar{\alpha}_0 \rangle_{H^1} + \lambda \langle \bar{\alpha}_1, \alpha_1 - \bar{\alpha}_1 \rangle_{H^1} && \text{for all } \alpha \in W_{ad} \end{aligned}$$

Proof. The proof just consists of adjusting the lines in (5.50) to the present situation, and inserting the corresponding equations and derivatives. For the derivation of the concrete (A), recall that the derivative $h'(x)[\cdot, \cdot]$ is symmetric, cf. Theorem 32! \square

More generally, given an arbitrary control $\alpha \in W_{ad}$, which is not necessarily optimal and an associated state $x = S(\alpha) \in \mathbb{H}_1$, then any solution $x^* = x^*(\alpha) \in \mathbb{H}_1$ to the system

$$\begin{aligned} -D\mathcal{F}(x)[v] &= \langle K^* K u^*, v_1 \rangle_{L^2} + \mu_1 \langle u^*, v_1 \rangle_{L^2} + \mu_2 \langle \nabla u^*, \nabla v_1 \rangle_{L^2} + \eta \langle w^*, v_2 \rangle_{H^1} \\ &+ \int_{\Omega} \alpha_0 h'(\nabla u - w) [\nabla u^* - w^*] \cdot (\nabla v_1 - v_2) \, dx && (5.51) \\ &+ \int_{\Omega} \alpha_1 h'(\mathcal{E} w) [\mathcal{E} w^*] \cdot (\mathcal{E} v_2) \, dx \quad \text{for all } v = (v_1, v_2) \in \mathbb{H}_1 \end{aligned}$$

is also called adjoint state for α and x . The adjoint state was once introduced in order to circumvent the costly computation of the inverse $D(S(\alpha), \alpha)^{-1}$ in the formula for the derivative of the solution operator (5.48). Moreover it yields a method of calculating the gradient of the reduced objective in an amenable fashion, since for $\alpha \in W_{ad}$ we have

$$\begin{aligned} \langle D\hat{\mathcal{J}}(\alpha), v \rangle_{\mathbb{V}^*, \mathbb{V}} &= \int_{\Omega} v_1 h(\nabla u - w) \cdot (\nabla u^*(\alpha) - w^*(\alpha)) \, dx + \int_{\Omega} v_2 h(\mathcal{E} w) \cdot \mathcal{E} w^*(\alpha) \, dx \\ &+ \lambda \langle \alpha_0, v_1 \rangle_{H^1} + \lambda \langle \alpha_1, v_2 \rangle_{H^1} \end{aligned} \quad (5.52)$$

Subsequently, the gradient can be calculated via the inverse Riesz map

$$\mathcal{R}_{\mathbb{V}} : \mathbb{V} \rightarrow \mathbb{V}^* : \quad \langle \mathcal{R}_{\mathbb{V}}(x), v \rangle_{\mathbb{V}^*, \mathbb{V}} = \langle x_1, v_1 \rangle_{H^1} + \langle x_2, v_2 \rangle_{H^1}$$

which is known to be an isometric isomorphism. Therefore we get

$$\nabla \widehat{\mathcal{J}}(\boldsymbol{\alpha}) = \mathcal{R}_{\mathbb{V}}^{-1}(D\widehat{\mathcal{J}}(\boldsymbol{\alpha})) \in \mathbb{V} \quad (5.53)$$

With help of the gradient we can now specify a projected gradient descent in the Hilbert space \mathbb{V} . In order to produce strictly decreasing function values of the reduced objective, an Armijo linesearch strategy is applied. The proposed method can be analogously found in [HPUU08] in an abstract form and also in the recent works [HRWL17], [HPRS20].

Algorithm 1: Projected gradient descent in function space

1 **Data:** Get $K, f, \mu_K, \mu, \eta, \delta, \gamma, \lambda$ as in Assumption 4, Armijo parameters $\tau_0 > 0, c \in (0, 1)$ and $0 < \theta^- < 1 \leq \theta^+$.

2 **Initialization :**

3 Set $\boldsymbol{\alpha}_0 \in W_{ad}$ arbitrary;

4 Set $k = 0$;

5 **while** *Some stopping criterion is not satisfied* **do**

6 Solve the state equation **(S)** to get the unique solution $x_k \in \mathbb{H}^1$;

7 Solve the adjoint equation **(A)** for $x_k^* \in \mathbb{H}^1$;

8 Compute the gradient $\nabla \widehat{\mathcal{J}}(\boldsymbol{\alpha}_k)$ of the reduced objective at $\boldsymbol{\alpha}_k \in \mathbb{V}$ via (5.52) and (5.53);

9 Compute the projection $P_{W_{ad}} : \mathbb{V} \rightarrow W_{ad}$ on W_{ad}

$$\boldsymbol{\alpha}_{k+1} = P_{W_{ad}}(\boldsymbol{\alpha}_k - \tau_k \nabla \widehat{\mathcal{J}}(\boldsymbol{\alpha}_k)) \quad (5.54)$$

while $\widehat{\mathcal{J}}(\boldsymbol{\alpha}_{k+1}) > \widehat{\mathcal{J}}(\boldsymbol{\alpha}_k) + c \langle \nabla \widehat{\mathcal{J}}(\boldsymbol{\alpha}_k), \boldsymbol{\alpha}_{k+1} - \boldsymbol{\alpha}_k \rangle$ **do**

10 Set $\tau_k = \theta^- \tau_k$;

11 Recompute

$$\boldsymbol{\alpha}_{k+1} = P_{W_{ad}}(\boldsymbol{\alpha}_k - \tau_k \nabla \widehat{\mathcal{J}}(\boldsymbol{\alpha}_k))$$

end

12 Set $\tau_{k+1} = \theta^+ \tau_k$;

13 Set $k = k + 1$;

14 **end**

15 Set $(\bar{x}, \bar{x}^*, \bar{\boldsymbol{\alpha}}) = (x_k, x_k^*, \boldsymbol{\alpha}_k)$

Note that a point $\boldsymbol{\alpha} \in \mathbb{V}$ satisfies the first order conditions (5.49) if and only if

$$\boldsymbol{\alpha} - P_{W_{ad}}(\boldsymbol{\alpha} - \nabla \widehat{\mathcal{J}}(\boldsymbol{\alpha})) = 0 \quad (5.55)$$

Therefore a reliable stopping criterion for algorithm 1 is to check, if the iterates $\boldsymbol{\alpha}_k$ satisfy

$$\|\boldsymbol{\alpha}_k - P_{W_{ad}}(\boldsymbol{\alpha}_k - \nabla \widehat{\mathcal{J}}(\boldsymbol{\alpha}_k))\|_{\mathbb{V}} < tol$$

for some given tolerance $tol > 0$.

Regarding the convergence of the above algorithm one can show the following theorem:

Theorem 41. *Let $\{\boldsymbol{\alpha}_n\}_n \subset \mathbb{V}$ be generated by algorithm 1. Then any limit point $\bar{\boldsymbol{\alpha}} \in \mathbb{V}$ of the sequence $\{\boldsymbol{\alpha}_n\}_n$ is stationary, i.e. satisfies (5.55). Moreover it holds*

$$\lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \boldsymbol{\alpha}_n - P_{W_{ad}}(\boldsymbol{\alpha}_n - \nabla \widehat{\mathcal{J}}(\boldsymbol{\alpha}_n)) = 0 \quad \text{in } \mathbb{V}. \quad (5.56)$$

Proof. The proof can be done similarly as in the work [HRWL17]. One needs to show that the reduced gradient $\boldsymbol{\alpha} \mapsto \nabla \widehat{\mathcal{J}}(\boldsymbol{\alpha})$ is Lipschitz continuous on $W_{ad} \subset \mathbb{V}$. The assertion of the theorem is then a consequence of [Ber76], see also [GB⁺82] where the Lipschitz assumption on the gradient is even weakened. As the rigorous proof is pretty lengthy, we skip it here and only sketch the main points: First it is shown via Theorem 34 that the solution $\boldsymbol{\alpha} \mapsto x(\boldsymbol{\alpha}) = S(\boldsymbol{\alpha})$ is Lipschitz continuous on W_{ad} . As a second step we use the latter information to show that $\boldsymbol{\alpha} \mapsto D\mathcal{F}(x(\boldsymbol{\alpha})) \in \mathbb{H}_1^*$ is Lipschitz continuous on W_{ad} . For that result it is important to take into account the fact, that $W_{ad} \subset \mathbb{L}^\infty(\Omega)$. Exploiting, that the solution of the adjoint equation depends Lipschitz continuously on the data (by Lax-Milgram), we also deduce the Lipschitz continuity of the mapping $\boldsymbol{\alpha} \mapsto x^*(\boldsymbol{\alpha}) \in \mathbb{H}_1$ to the adjoint state. Minding formula (5.52) and the boundedness of $h(\cdot) \leq 1$, we conclude the Lipschitz continuity of $\boldsymbol{\alpha} \mapsto D\widehat{\mathcal{J}}(\boldsymbol{\alpha}) \in \mathbb{H}_1^*$ and, as the Riesz map is always an isometry, also the Lipschitz continuity of $\boldsymbol{\alpha} \mapsto \nabla \widehat{\mathcal{J}}(\boldsymbol{\alpha}) \in \mathbb{H}_1^*$. \square

We should once again review the assumptions we made at the beginning of this chapter, where we took it for granted that the solution operator

$$S : W_{ad} \rightarrow \mathbb{H}_1$$

is well defined and consequently Frechét-differentiable, by Theorem 39. However, the nonboundedness of $H^1(\Omega)$ functions in dimensions greater than one caused several difficulties, as seen in Theorem 38, Theorem 39 and the discussion in between. To the best knowledge of the author it is up to now unclear, whether such a neighborhood can be constructed, or whether every $H^1(\Omega) \times H^1(\Omega)$ -neighborhood of W_{ad} contains at least one $\boldsymbol{\alpha} \in \mathbb{V}$, such that $S(\boldsymbol{\alpha}) = \emptyset$.

In the latter case, Frechét-differentiability of $S : W_{ad} \rightarrow \mathbb{H}_1$ cannot be ensured in the $H^1(\Omega) \times H^1(\Omega)$ -topology. Consequently the chain-rule is not applicable and other methods have to be used to obtain first order systems.

One possible workaround could be to consider instead the parameter space

$$\mathbb{V}_1 := \mathbb{H}^1(\Omega) \cap \mathbb{L}^\infty(\Omega) \quad \|\cdot\|_{\mathbb{V}_1} := \|\cdot\|_{\mathbb{H}^1} + \|\cdot\|_{\mathbb{L}^\infty} \quad (5.57)$$

It can be easily checked, that the space \mathbb{V}_1 , endowed with the norm $\|\cdot\|_{\mathbb{V}_1}$ is a Banach space, which is continuously and densely embedded into $\mathbb{H}^1(\Omega)$ and also into $\mathbb{L}^\infty(\Omega)$. Therefore, the differentiability of $\mathcal{J}(\cdot, \cdot)$ on the space $\mathbb{H}_1 \times \mathbb{H}^1(\Omega)$ and the differentiability of $S(\cdot)$ on $\mathbb{L}^\infty(\Omega)$ carry over to that new setting and we can obtain similar results as in Theorem 40.

The same is true for the choice

$$\mathbb{V}_2 := \mathbb{W}^{1,p}(\Omega) \quad \|\cdot\|_{\mathbb{V}_2} := \|\cdot\|_{\mathbb{W}^{1,p}} \quad \text{for some } p > 2 \quad (5.58)$$

in combination with the space dimension $n = 2$. However to obtain existence of solutions in the space \mathbb{V}_2 , we need to modify the upperlevel objective, which then reads

$$\mathcal{J}(x, \boldsymbol{\alpha}) = F \circ R(u) + \frac{1}{p} \left(\|\alpha_0\|_{\mathbb{W}^{1,p}(\Omega)}^p + \|\alpha_1\|_{\mathbb{W}^{1,p}(\Omega)}^p \right)$$

Also for the choice \mathbb{V}_2 , the differentiability of the upperlevel objective can be shown and due to the embedding $\mathbb{W}^{1,p}(\Omega) \hookrightarrow \mathbb{L}^\infty(\Omega)$ in dimension $n = 2$ we may also deduce the differentiability of the solution operator $S : \mathbb{V}_2 \rightarrow \mathbb{H}_1$ on $W_{ad} \subset \mathbb{V}_2$. In contrast to the optimality system, the projected descent algorithm, algorithm 1 cannot be adopted to the Banach space configuration, since a Riesz map is not available there. However in this regime, recent results on extensions of projected gradient schemes to Banach spaces could be applicable [BR17]. The authors of the latter work constructed a projected gradient type algorithm with applications to structural topology optimization. The algorithm, which is proposed there, works also in $\mathbb{H}^1(\Omega) \cap \mathbb{L}^\infty(\Omega)$ and a rigorous convergence analysis is provided. Nevertheless, a thorough adjustment of these results to our case would take some effort and, for the time being, it remains only an outlook on some possible future investigations.

Chapter 6

Numerical Solution

As the last chapters were more of theoretical nature, we should now discuss, how to solve ($\mathbb{P}_{\text{control}}$) numerically on a computer. For that purpose, we will explain briefly, how the continuous control problem can be transferred to a discrete setting. In our argumentation, we follow loosely the paper [HPRS20]. For clarity of presentation, we will again only consider the space dimension $n = 2$ and quadratic regular grids of size $N \times M$ with $N, M \in \mathbb{N}$:

$$\Omega_{M,N}^h := \{(ih, jh) \mid 1 \leq i \leq N \text{ and } 1 \leq j \leq M\}$$

and sometimes if the number of pixels is clear, we will just write Ω^h instead of Ω_{NM}^h . A grey valued image $u : \Omega_{M,N}^h \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ is then given by its evaluation on this discrete grid. We simply write

$$u_{i,j} = u(ih, jh)$$

for $1 \leq i \leq N$ and $1 \leq j \leq M$. Moreover we introduce the discrete functionspaces

$$U_{M,N}^h := \mathbb{R}^{NM} \quad W_{M,N}^h := U_{M,N}^h \times U_{M,N}^h \simeq \mathbb{R}^{2NM} \quad V_{M,N}^h := U_{M,N}^h \times U_{M,N}^h \times U_{M,N}^h \simeq \mathbb{R}^{3NM}$$

Clearly, $U_{M,N}^h$ is the discrete version of the space $L^2(\Omega)$, $W_{M,N}^h$ of $L^2(\Omega, \mathbb{R}^n)$ and $V_{M,N}^h$ is the finite dimensional counterpart of $L^2(\Omega, \mathbb{R}_{sym}^{n \times n})$. These spaces are turned into Hilbert spaces when equipped with the inner products

$$\begin{aligned} \langle u_1, u_2 \rangle_{U_{M,N}^h} &:= \sum_{i,j} (u_1)_{ij} (u_2)_{ij} & u_i &\in U_{M,N}^h \\ \langle w_1, w_2 \rangle_{W_{M,N}^h} &:= \sum_{i,j} (w_1)_{ij}^1 (w_2)_{ij}^1 + \sum_{i,j} (w_1)_{ij}^2 (w_2)_{ij}^2 & w_i &= ((w_i)^1, (w_i)^2) \in W_{M,N}^h \\ \langle p_1, p_2 \rangle_{V_{M,N}^h} &:= \sum_{i,j} (p_1)_{ij}^{1,1} (p_2)_{ij}^{1,1} + \sum_{i,j} (p_1)_{ij}^{2,2} (p_2)_{ij}^{2,2} + 2 \sum_{i,j} (p_1)_{ij}^{1,2} (p_2)_{ij}^{1,2} & p_i &= ((p_i)^{1,1}, (p_i)^{2,2}, (p_i)^{1,2}) \in V_{M,N}^h \end{aligned} \quad (6.1)$$

If the numbers of pixels, $N, M \in \mathbb{N}$ are clear, we will remove them from the notation for simplicity.

In order to discretize the first order differential operators, we utilize forward and backward finite differences. The forward differences $\partial_{1+}^h, \partial_{2+}^h : U_{M,N}^h \rightarrow U_{M,N}^h$ are defined component wise via

$$(\partial_{1+}^h u)_{ij} := \begin{cases} \frac{1}{h} (u_{i+1,j} - u_{ij}) & \text{for } 1 \leq i < N \\ 0 & \text{else} \end{cases} \quad (\partial_{2+}^h u)_{ij} := \begin{cases} \frac{1}{h} (u_{i,j+1} - u_{ij}) & \text{for } 1 \leq j < M \\ 0 & \text{else} \end{cases}$$

and the backward differences $\partial_{1-}^h, \partial_{2-}^h : U_{M,N}^h \rightarrow U_{M,N}^h$ are given by

$$(\partial_{1-}^h u)_{i,j} := \begin{cases} \frac{1}{h} u_{ij} & \text{for } i = 1 \\ \frac{1}{h} (u_{ij} - u_{i-1,j}) & \text{for } 1 < i < N \\ -\frac{1}{h} u_{i-1,j} & \text{for } i = N \end{cases} \quad (\partial_{2-}^h u)_{ij} := \begin{cases} \frac{1}{h} u_{ij} & \text{for } j = 1 \\ \frac{1}{h} (u_{ij} - u_{i,j-1}) & \text{for } 1 < j < M \\ -\frac{1}{h} u_{i,j-1} & \text{for } j = M \end{cases}$$

These operators are then used to define the discrete gradient and the symmetrized jacobian:

$$\begin{aligned} \nabla^h : U_{M,N}^h &\rightarrow W_{M,N}^h & \nabla^h u &:= (\partial_{1+}^h u, \partial_{2+}^h u) \\ \mathcal{E}^h : W_{M,N}^h &\rightarrow V_{M,N}^h & \mathcal{E}^h w &:= (\partial_{1+}^h w^1, \partial_{2+}^h w^2, (\partial_{1+}^h w^1 + \partial_{2+}^h w^2) / 2) \end{aligned}$$

Moreover, the discrete divergences are chosen as follows

$$\begin{aligned} \operatorname{div}^h : W_{M,N}^h &\rightarrow U_{M,N}^h & \operatorname{div}^h w &:= \partial_{1-}^h w^1 + \partial_{2-}^h w^2 & \text{for } w = (w^1, w^2) \in W_{M,N}^h. \\ \operatorname{div}^h : V_{M,N}^h &\rightarrow W_{M,N}^h & \operatorname{div}^h p &:= \begin{pmatrix} \partial_{1-}^h p^{1,1} + \partial_{2-}^h p^{1,2} \\ \partial_{1-}^h p^{1,2} + \partial_{2-}^h p^{2,2} \end{pmatrix} & \text{for } p = (p^{1,1}, p^{2,2}, p^{1,2}) \in V_{M,N}^h. \end{aligned}$$

It is shown in [BL19], that the following adjoint relations holds true, which is consistent to the infinite dimensional setting:

$$\langle \nabla^h u, w \rangle_{W^h} = -\langle u, \operatorname{div}^h w \rangle_{U^h} \quad \langle \mathcal{E}^h w, p \rangle_{V^h} = -\langle u, \operatorname{div}^h p \rangle_{W^h} \quad (6.2)$$

Note, that the adjoint relation with respect to the inner products $\langle \cdot, \cdot \rangle_{U^h}$, $\langle \cdot, \cdot \rangle_{W^h}$ and $\langle \cdot, \cdot \rangle_{V^h}$ does not mean, that the corresponding representation matrices are transposed to each other. Indeed, it holds

$$-\operatorname{div}^h = (\nabla^h)^T \in \mathbb{R}^{NM \times 2NM}$$

but

$$-\operatorname{div}^h \neq (\mathcal{E}^h)^T \in \mathbb{R}^{2NM \times 3NM} \quad (6.3)$$

The latter statement (6.3) can be seen by looking at the matrices

$$\operatorname{div}^h = \begin{bmatrix} \partial_{1-}^h & 0 & \partial_{2-}^h \\ 0 & \partial_{2-}^h & \partial_{1-}^h \end{bmatrix} \quad \text{and} \quad \mathcal{E}^h = \begin{bmatrix} \partial_{1+}^h & 0 \\ 0 & \partial_{2+}^h \\ \frac{1}{2}\partial_{2+}^h & \frac{1}{2}\partial_{1+}^h \end{bmatrix}$$

and by taking also into account, that

$$(\partial_{i-}^h)^T = -\partial_{i+}^h \quad \text{for } i = 1, 2$$

see again [BL19] for the last equation. This is important for the numerical implementation later on. For the discrete Laplace operator we use the standard 5-point stencil implementation with Neumann boundary conditions, denoted as

$$\Delta^h = \Delta_N^h : U_{M,N}^h \rightarrow U_{M,N}^h$$

Its vectorial counterpart, which is denoted the same

$$\Delta^h : W_{M,N}^h \rightarrow W_{M,N}^h$$

is defined componentwise via

$$\Delta^h w := (\Delta^h w^1, \Delta^h w^2) \quad \text{for } (w^1, w^2) \in W_{M,N}^h.$$

It is important to keep in mind for the subsequent part, that we will do not distinguish in the notation between linear operators and their corresponding representation matrices.

We continue with the discrete versions of the Lebesgue and Sobolev norms, which read

$$\|u\|_{\ell^2(\Omega^h)}^2 := h^2 \sum_{i,j} u_{ij}^2 \quad \|u\|_{H^1(\Omega^h)}^2 := h^2 u^T (I_{2NM} - \Delta^h) u \quad \|\nabla u\|_{\ell^2(\Omega^h)}^2 := h^2 u^T (-\Delta^h) u$$

where $I_K \in \mathbb{R}^{K \times K}$ denotes the identity matrix for some $K \in \mathbb{N}$. We now state the discrete version of $(\mathbb{P}_{\text{control}})$. However, instead of solving the control problem for both parameters being spatially varying, we will keep in the discrete regime $\alpha_0 \in \mathbb{R}$ constant. Note, that this does not mean a major restriction, as the regularization effect mainly depends on the ratio of the two regularization parameters, cf. also the experiments in [HPRS20].

In addition, we allow that the sample domain, where the measurement f is taken, can be multidimensional. This is important as we will later consider a model for MRI reconstruction, in which the noisy data is acquired in the Fourier domain $\mathbb{C} \simeq \mathbb{R}^2$. In fact we will look at multidimensional measurements of the form

$$f \in \underbrace{U_{M,N}^h \times \dots \times U_{M,N}^h}_{l\text{-times}}$$

and the discrete minimization problem :

$$\begin{aligned} \min_{(u, \alpha) \in U_{M,N}^h \times W_{ad}^h} \mathcal{J}^h(u, \alpha) &= \sum_{i=1}^l F^h \circ R_i^h(u) + \frac{\lambda_1}{2} \|\alpha_1\|_{\ell^2(\Omega^h)}^2 + \frac{\lambda_2}{2} \|\nabla \alpha_1\|_{\ell^2(\Omega^h)}^2 & (\mathbb{P}^h) \\ \text{s.t } g^h(u, w, \alpha) &= 0 \end{aligned}$$

The discretized cost functional is given by

$$F^h : U_{M,N}^h \rightarrow \mathbb{R} \quad F^h(v) := \frac{1}{2} \|(v - \bar{\sigma}^2)_+\|_{\ell^2(\Omega^h)}^2 + \frac{1}{2} \|(\underline{\sigma}^2 - v)_+\|_{\ell^2(\Omega^h)}^2 \quad (6.4)$$

$$R_i^h : U_{M,N}^h \rightarrow U_{M,N}^h \quad R_i^h(u) = W_{n_w} * \left[\pi_i(K^h u - f) \right]^2 \quad (6.5)$$

Here $W_{n_w} = \mathbf{1}_{[-n_w, n_w] \times [-n_w, n_w]}$ denotes a filter of size $n_w \times n_w$, $n_w \in \mathbb{N}$ and $*$ is a discrete convolution with periodic boundary conditions. The spaces $U_{M,N}^h$ where the samples are taken, are defined as in the beginning of this section. The function $\pi_i : U_{M,N}^h \times \dots \times U_{M,N}^h \rightarrow U_{M,N}^h$ is the linear projection on the i -th component. The function $g^h(\cdot)$ is discretized via

$$\begin{aligned} g^h : (U_{M,N}^h \times W_{M,N}^h) \times W_{M,N}^h &\rightarrow U_{M,N}^h \times W_{M,N}^h & (6.6) \\ (u, w, \alpha) &\mapsto \begin{bmatrix} K^T K u - K^T f + \mu_K u - \mu \Delta^h u \\ \eta w - \eta \Delta^h w \end{bmatrix} + \begin{bmatrix} -\text{div}^h & 0 \\ -I_{2NM} & -\text{div}^h \end{bmatrix} \cdot \begin{bmatrix} \alpha_1 h(\nabla^h u - w) \\ \alpha_0 h(\mathcal{E}^h w) \end{bmatrix} \end{aligned}$$

The admissible controls W_{ad}^h are given by the cartesian product of the following two sets

$$\begin{aligned} (W_{ad}^h)_1 &= \left\{ \alpha_1 \in U_{M,N}^h \mid \underline{\alpha}_1 \leq (\alpha_1)_{ij} \leq \bar{\alpha}_1 \quad \text{for } (i, j) \in \mathbb{N}^2 \right\} \\ (W_{ad}^h)_0 &= \left\{ \alpha_0 \in \mathbb{R} \mid \underline{\alpha}_0 \leq \alpha_0 \leq \bar{\alpha}_0 \right\} \end{aligned} \quad (6.7)$$

The upper and lower bounds $\underline{\alpha}_i, \bar{\alpha}_i > 0$ for $i = 0, 1$ are chosen to be positive constants.

6.1 Solution of the Lower Level Problem

Each descent step of the discrete version of the projected gradient method algorithm 1 requires a solution of the discretized state equation

$$x \rightarrow g^h(x, \boldsymbol{\alpha}) = 0 \quad (6.8)$$

Thus it is essential to be able to solve the state equation within a short time and with high accuracy. To achieve this goal, we use a Newton type algorithm, which was originally proposed in [HS06] for TV regularization and that was recently adopted for solving Huberized TGV problems, see [RSV17] and [HPRS20]. The advantage of Newton type algorithms is, that they feature at least a locally superlinear convergence behavior, in many cases (if Lipschitz continuity of the objective can be shown) even local quadratic convergence is attained. We briefly explain the approach in [HPRS20]. Instead of solving the state equation (6.8) directly, an equivalent primal dual formulation of the latter is considered, which reads:

$$x \rightarrow g_{pd}^h(u, w, p, q, \boldsymbol{\alpha}) = 0 \quad (6.9)$$

The function $g_{pd}^h(\cdot)$ is defined as

$$g_{pd}^h : \left(U_{M,N}^h \times W_{M,N}^h \times W_{M,N}^h \times V_{M,N}^h \right) \times W_{M,N}^h \rightarrow U_{M,N}^h \times W_{M,N}^h \times W_{M,N}^h \times V_{M,N}^h$$

$$(u, w, p, q, \boldsymbol{\alpha}) \mapsto \begin{pmatrix} K^T K u + \mu_K u - K^T f - \mu \Delta^h u - \operatorname{div}^h p \\ -\eta \Delta^h w + \eta w - p - \operatorname{div}^h q \\ -\alpha_1 (\nabla^h u - w) + p m_\delta(|\nabla^h u - w|, \gamma) \\ -\alpha_0 \mathcal{E}^h w + q m_\delta(|\mathcal{E}^h w|, \gamma) \end{pmatrix} \quad (6.10)$$

and it can be easily checked, that $g_{pd}^h(u, w, p, q) = 0$ if and only if $g^h(u, w) = 0$, $p = \alpha_1 h(\nabla^h u - w)$ and $q = \alpha_0 h(\mathcal{E}^h w)$ pointwise in every $i, j \in \mathbb{N}$. A typical Newton scheme for solving (6.9) with fixed $\boldsymbol{\alpha} \in W_{M,N}^h$, starting at some point $x_0 = (u_0, w_0, p_0, q_0) \in U_{M,N}^h \times W_{M,N}^h \times W_{M,N}^h \times V_{M,N}^h$ solves in every iteration step the equation

$$D_x g_{pd}^h(x_k, \boldsymbol{\alpha}) x_{k+1} = D_x g_{pd}^h(x_k, \boldsymbol{\alpha}) x_k - g_{pd}^h(x_k, \boldsymbol{\alpha}) \quad (6.11)$$

for some new $x_{k+1} \in U_{M,N}^h \times W_{M,N}^h \times W_{M,N}^h \times V_{M,N}^h$. Note, that the continuous differentiability of $g(\cdot, \cdot)$ in finite dimension follows from standard arguments and the differential $D_x g_{pd}^h(x_k, \boldsymbol{\alpha})$ in the k -th iteration is given in terms of the following block matrices

$$A := \begin{bmatrix} K^T K + \mu_K I_{NM} - \mu_2 \Delta^h & 0 \\ 0 & \eta (I_{2NM} - \Delta^h) \end{bmatrix} \quad B := \begin{bmatrix} -\operatorname{div}^h & 0 \\ -I_{2NM} & -\operatorname{div}^h \end{bmatrix} \quad (6.12)$$

$$D_k := \begin{bmatrix} m_\delta(|\nabla^h u_k - w_k|, \gamma) & 0 \\ 0 & m_\delta(|\mathcal{E}^h w_k|, \gamma) \end{bmatrix}$$

$$C_k := \begin{bmatrix} -\alpha_0 \nabla^h + p_k m'_\delta(|\nabla^h u_k - w_k|, \gamma) \frac{(\nabla^h u_k - w_k)}{|\nabla^h u_k - w_k|} \cdot \nabla^h & \alpha_0 I_{2NM} + p_k m'_\delta(|\nabla^h u_k - w_k|, \gamma) \frac{(\nabla^h u_k - w_k)}{|\nabla^h u_k - w_k|} \cdot (-I_{2NM}) \\ 0 & -\alpha_1 \mathcal{E}^h + q_k m'_\delta(|\mathcal{E}^h w_k|, \gamma) \frac{\mathcal{E}^h w_k}{|\mathcal{E}^h w_k|} \cdot \mathcal{E}^h \end{bmatrix}$$

which yield a compact representation of the Jacobian:

$$D_x g_{pd}^h(x_k, \boldsymbol{\alpha}) = \begin{bmatrix} A & B \\ C_k & D_k \end{bmatrix}$$

Note also that in (6.12), in particular in the definition of D_k and C_k the submatrices are again understood in the diagonal sense. Since the matrix D_k is diagonal with positive ($\geq \gamma$) diagonal entries, it is

clearly invertible and we can reduce the system above via the Schur complement. This mean simply that $x_k = (x_{k+1,1}, x_{k,2})$ solves (6.11) if and only if $x_{k+1,1}, x_{k+1,2}$ solve the system

$$\begin{aligned} [A - BD_k^{-1}C_k] x_{k+1,1} &= b_{k,1} - BD_k^{-1}b_{k,2} \\ x_{k+1,2} &= D_k^{-1} [x_{k,2} - C_k x_{k,1}] \end{aligned} \quad (6.13)$$

where only the first equation requires to solve a linear system. In the last equation, we also set

$$b_{k,1} = \begin{pmatrix} K^T f \\ 0 \end{pmatrix} \quad b_{k,2} = \begin{pmatrix} p_k m'_\delta(|\nabla^h u_k - w_k|, \gamma) |\nabla^h u_k - w_k| \\ q_k m'_\delta(|\mathcal{E}^h w_k|, \gamma) |\mathcal{E}^h w_k| \end{pmatrix} \quad (6.14)$$

Unfortunately, the system in (6.13) cannot be solved directly, but under some mild conditions on the dual multipliers, we obtain

Theorem 42 (Unique solvability of the reduced Newton step equation). *If $|(p_k)| \leq \alpha_0$ and $|(q_k)| \leq \alpha_1$, understood pointwise in every $i, j \in \mathbb{N}$, the matrix $H_k := [A - BD_k^{-1}C_k]$ is positive definite and $\lambda_{\min}(H_k) \geq \lambda_{\min}(A)$. Here $\lambda_{\min}(X)$ denotes the smallest eigenvalue of a Matrix X .*

Proof. A similar result is proven in [HS06] for nonsmooth huber TV. However, the arguments there can be easily adapted to the TGV case. \square

Algorithm 2: Infeasible Newton algorithm

Data:

Regularization parameters $\alpha = (\alpha_0, \alpha_1) \in W_{M,N}^h$, which are positive component wise.
Tolerance for the stopping criterion $tol_g > 0$

1 Initialization :

2 Chose $x_0 = (u_0, w_0, p_0, q_0) \in U_{M,N}^h \times W_{M,N}^h \times W_{M,N}^h \times V_{M,N}^h$ with $|p_0| \leq \alpha_1$ and $|q_0| \leq \alpha_0$ pointwise ;

3 Set $k = 0$;

4 **while** $\|g_{pd}^h(x_k)\| \geq tol_g \|g_{pd}^h(x_0)\|$ **do**

5 Solve the reduced Newton step equation for

$$x_{k+1} = (x_{k+1,1}, x_{k+1,2}) \in U_{M,N}^h \times W_{M,N}^h \times W_{M,N}^h \times V_{M,N}^h,$$

6 which reads again

$$[A - BD_k^{-1}C_k] x_{k+1,1} = b_{k,1} - BD_k^{-1}b_{k,2}$$

7 and subsequently set

$$\hat{x}_{k+1,2} = D_k^{-1} [b_{k,2} - C_k d_{k,1}]$$

8 Now compute the projection of $\hat{x}_{k+1,2} = (\hat{p}_{k+1,2}, \hat{q}_{k+1,2})$ on the feasible sets

9 $\{p \mid |p| \leq \alpha_1\}$ and $\{q \mid |q| \leq \alpha_0\}$ by

$$p_{k+1} = \frac{\hat{p}_{k+1}}{\max(1, |\hat{p}_{k+1}|/\alpha_1)} \quad q_{k+1} = \frac{\hat{q}_{k+1}}{\max(1, |\hat{q}_{k+1}|/\alpha_0)}$$

10 Eventually set $x_{k+1} = (x_{k+1,1}, x_{k+1,2})$, where $x_{k+1,2} = (p_{k+1}, q_{k+1}) \in W_{M,N}^h \times V_{M,N}^h$.

11 Set $k = k + 1$;

12 **end**

13 Set $\bar{x} = x_k$.

To circumvent this issue, the authors in [Hintermüller2006] proposed an additional projection step after solving (6.13) in each iteration. The same technique was recently applied to the Huberized TGV problem in [HPRS20], which lead directly to the algorithm 2. Note that, because of the extra projection step, the local superlinear convergence of algorithm 2 cannot be shown via standard arguments. However in [HS06] a convergence result is proven for the semi smooth newton TV case and exactly the same argumentation also applies to the TGV case. However a rigorous convergence analysis is omitted here, since it would expand this work considerably. We only state the convergence theorem and leave the concrete adaption of the arguments in [HS06] to the reader

Theorem 43 (Local convergence of the infeasible newton method). *Consider algorithm 2 without taking into account the stopping criterion. Moreover, let*

$$x_0 = (u_0, w_0, p_0, q_0) \in X^h := U_{M,N}^h \times W_{M,N}^h \times W_{M,N}^h \times V_{M,N}^h$$

with $|p_0| \leq \alpha_1$ and $|q_0| \leq \alpha_0$ pointwise, such that $\|x_0 - \bar{x}\|_{X^h}$ is sufficiently small, where $\bar{x} \in X^h$ solves (6.9). Then the iterates $(x_n)_n$, generated by algorithm 2 converge to \bar{x} with a superlinear rate, i.e.

$$\lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \frac{\|x_{k+1} - \bar{x}\|_{X^h}}{\|x_k - \bar{x}\|_{X^h}} = 0$$

6.2 Finite Dimensional Projected Gradient Algorithm.

We will now state the finite dimensional approximation of the projected gradient descent algorithm in the last chapter. For that purpose, we need to solve the discrete version of the adjoint equation (A) several times. Given a solution $x = x(\alpha) = (u, w) \in U_{M,N}^h \times W_{M,N}^h$ of (6.8), the discretization of the latter equation reads

$$[A - BE]x^* = \begin{pmatrix} b_1^* \\ 0 \end{pmatrix} \quad \text{with the discrete adjoint state } x^* = (u^*, w^*) \in U_{M,N}^h \times W_{M,N}^h \quad (6.15)$$

where A, B are again defined as in (6.12) and E is given by

$$E = \begin{bmatrix} \alpha_1 h'(\nabla^h u - w) [\nabla^h u - w] \cdot \nabla^h & \alpha_1 h'(\nabla^h u - w) [\nabla^h u - w] \cdot (-I_{2NM}) \\ 0 & \alpha_0 h'(\mathcal{E}^h w) [\mathcal{E}^h w] \cdot \mathcal{E}^h \end{bmatrix}$$

The $b_1^* \in U_{M,N}^h$ on the righthand side of (6.15) is given by

$$b_1^* = -2 \sum_{i=1}^l K^T \pi_i^T \left[(\pi_i K u - \pi_i f) W_{nw} * \left((R_i^h(u) - \bar{\sigma}^2)_+ - (\underline{\sigma}^2 - R_i^h(u))_+ \right) \right]$$

It can be shown via the same arguments as in the continuous case, c.f. Theorem 37, that the matrix $(A - BE)$ in (6.15) is positive definite and therefore invertible.

Subsequently we calculate the Jacobian of the reduced objective via

$$\begin{aligned} D_{\alpha} \hat{\mathcal{J}}^h(\alpha) &= D_{\alpha} g^h(x, \alpha)^* x^* \\ &= [h(\nabla^h u - w) \cdot (\nabla^h u^* - w^*) + \lambda_1 \alpha_1 - \lambda_2 \Delta^h \alpha_1 \quad h(\mathcal{E}^h w) \cdot \mathcal{E}^h w^*] \in \mathbb{R}^{NM \times (NM+1)} \end{aligned}$$

where $(\cdot)^*$ denotes the adjoint with respect to the inner products in (6.1) and the matrix is again understood in the diagonal sense.

Now, we compute the gradient using the inverse discretized Riesz map

$$\begin{aligned} \nabla_{\alpha_1} \hat{\mathcal{J}}^h(\alpha) &= [I_{NM} - \Delta^h]^{-1} \left(h(\nabla^h u - w) \cdot (\nabla^h u^* - w^*) + \lambda_1 \alpha_1 - \lambda_2 \Delta^h \alpha_1 \right) \\ \nabla_{\alpha_0} \hat{\mathcal{J}}^h(\alpha) &= \left(h(\mathcal{E}^h w) \cdot (\mathcal{E}^h w^*) \right) \end{aligned} \quad (6.16)$$

Note that for the second equation, the inverse Riesz map is not needed, as we chose $\alpha_1 \in \mathbb{R}$. Having the gradient of the reduced objective calculated, we need a way to compute its discrete H^1 -projection on the feasible set W_{ad}^h , which is done in each coordinate separately. Therefore we need to solve another minimization problem, namely

$$P_{(W_{ad}^h)_1}(\hat{\alpha}) = \arg \min_{\alpha \in (W_{ad}^h)_1} \frac{1}{2} \|\alpha - \hat{\alpha}_1\|_{H^1(\Omega^h)}^2 = \frac{h}{2} (\alpha - \hat{\alpha}_1)^T [I_{NM} - \Delta^h] (\alpha - \hat{\alpha}_1) \quad (6.17)$$

$$P_{(W_{ad}^h)_0}(\hat{\alpha}) = \max(\min(\hat{\alpha}, \bar{\alpha}_0), \underline{\alpha}_0) \quad (6.18)$$

The problem (6.17) is then first approximated by the unconstrained problem

$$\min_{\alpha \in U_{M,N}^h} \frac{1}{2} \|\alpha - \hat{\alpha}_1\|_{H^1(\Omega^h)}^2 + \frac{1}{\epsilon_\alpha} \left(\frac{1}{2} \|(\alpha - \bar{\alpha}_1)_+\|_{\ell^2(\Omega^h)}^2 + \frac{1}{2} \|(\underline{\alpha}_1 - \alpha)_+\|_{\ell^2(\Omega^h)}^2 \right) \quad (6.19)$$

for some small regularization parameter $\epsilon_\alpha > 0$ and eventually problem (6.19) is solved by a Semi-smooth newton method, which was originally developed in [HK06] for a broader class of problems. We only state a version, which was customized especially for the projection problem above in [HRWL17] and recently in [HPRS20]

Algorithm 3: α -Projection

Data: Get $\hat{\alpha} \in U_{M,N}^h$, tolerance $tol_\alpha > 0$ and regularization parameter $\epsilon_\alpha > 0$.

1 **Initialize :**

2 $\alpha_0 \in U_{M,N}^h$ and $k := 0$

3 Compute the residual

$$r_0 := [I_{NM} - \Delta^h] (\alpha_0 - \hat{\alpha}_1) + \frac{1}{\epsilon_\alpha} ((\alpha_0 - \bar{\alpha}_1)_+ - (\alpha_0 - \underline{\alpha}_1)_+)$$

while $\|r_k\|_{H^1(\Omega^h)^*} \geq tol_\alpha \|r_0\|_{H^1(\Omega^h)^*}$ **do**

4 Compute Newton step $d_k \in U_{M,N}^h$ via solving

$$[I_{NM} - \Delta^h + \text{diag}(\xi_k)] d_k = r_k$$

where $\xi_k \in U_{M,N}^h$ is given by

$$\xi_{k,i} = \begin{cases} 1 & \text{if } \alpha_{k,i} > \bar{\alpha} \text{ or } \alpha_{k,i} < \underline{\alpha} \\ 0 & \text{Otherwise} \end{cases}$$

Update

$$\alpha_{k+1} := \alpha_k + d_k$$

$$r_{k+1} := [I_{NM} - \Delta^h] (\alpha_{k+1} - \hat{\alpha}_1) + \frac{1}{\epsilon_\alpha} ((\alpha_{k+1} - \bar{\alpha}_1)_+ - (\alpha_{k+1} - \underline{\alpha}_1)_+)$$

Set $k = k + 1$.

5 **end**

In the algorithm above, following [HRWL17], we used the discrete dual norm

$$\|r_k\|_{H^1(\Omega^h)^*} = h \sqrt{r^T [I_{NM} - \Delta^h] r}$$

A rigorous convergence analysis of a more general class of quadratic constrained problems, to which the projection problem (6.17) belongs, can be again found in [HK06]. In the latter work the reader will also find an elegant way of choosing $\epsilon_\alpha > 0$ rigorously. We again won't go further in that direction at that point in order not to exceed the scope of the thesis. We have now collected all prerequisites together, which are needed to state the discretized version of algorithm 1

Algorithm 4: Discrete projected gradient descent

Data: Get $f, \mu, \mu_K, \eta, \delta, \gamma, \lambda$, armijo parameters $\tau_0^1, \tau_0^2 > 0, c \in (0, 1)$ and $0 < \theta^- < 1 \leq \theta^+$.

1 Initialization :

2 Set $\alpha_0 \in W_{ad}^h$ arbitrary.

3 Set $k = 0$.

4 while *Some stopping criterion is not satisfied* **do**

5 Solve the discrete state equation

6

$$x \mapsto g^h(x, \alpha_k) = 0$$

via algorithm 2 for a the unique solution $x_k = (u_k, w_k) \in U_{M,N}^h \times W_{M,N}^h$;

7 Solve the discrete adjoint equation (6.15) for $x_k^* = (u_k^*, w_k^*) \in U_{M,N}^h \times W_{M,N}^h$;

8 Compute the discrete gradient $\nabla \hat{\mathcal{J}}^h(\alpha_k) \in \mathbb{R} \times U_{M,N}^h$ of the reduced objective at $\alpha_k \in \mathbb{R} \times U_{M,N}^h$ via (6.16) ;

9 Compute the projection $P_{W_{ad}^h} : \mathbb{R} \times U_{M,N}^h \rightarrow W_{ad}^h$ on W_{ad}^h by solving equations (6.17) and (6.18) via algorithm 3.

$$\alpha_{k+1,1} = P_{(W_{ad}^h)_1} (\alpha_{k,1} - \tau_k^1 \nabla_{\alpha_1} \hat{\mathcal{J}}^h(\alpha_k))$$

$$\alpha_{k+1,0} = P_{(W_{ad}^h)_0} (\alpha_{k,0} - \tau_k^0 \nabla_{\alpha_0} \hat{\mathcal{J}}^h(\alpha_k))$$

while $\hat{\mathcal{J}}^h(\alpha_{k+1}) > \hat{\mathcal{J}}^h(\alpha_k) + c \langle \nabla \hat{\mathcal{J}}^h(\alpha_k), \alpha_{k+1} - \alpha_k \rangle_{U^h \times U^h}$ **do**

10 Set $\tau_k^0 = \theta^- \tau_k^0, \tau_k^1 = \theta^- \tau_k^1$

11 Recompute

$$\alpha_{k+1,1} = P_{(W_{ad}^h)_1} (\alpha_{k,1} - \tau_k^1 \nabla_{\alpha_1} \hat{\mathcal{J}}^h(\alpha_k))$$

$$\alpha_{k+1,0} = P_{(W_{ad}^h)_0} (\alpha_{k,0} - \tau_k^0 \nabla_{\alpha_0} \hat{\mathcal{J}}^h(\alpha_k))$$

12 **end**

13 Set $\tau_{k+1}^0 = \theta^+ \tau_k^0, \tau_{k+1}^1 = \theta^+ \tau_k^1$.

14 Set $k = k + 1$;

15 **end**

The convergence behavior of the above algorithm can be investigated via the same arguments as in the continuous case.

Chapter 7

Experiments on Fourier Inpainting

As a concrete numerical example, we will now consider the inverse problem of Fourier inpainting, which is a commonly used model for magnet resonance imaging (MRI). In MRI one tries to reconstruct a slice of the body by collecting only a few Fourier coefficients along a given sampling pattern. Subsequently these Fourier coefficients are transformed back into the image domain and provide insights into the patients inner body. As a typical goal is, to collect less and less Fourier coefficients, this ends up in a highly ill posed reconstruction problem. Simply filling in zero for the missing coefficients leads to the least squares approximation. However, the latter induces well known *aliasing* artifacts, see Figure 7.4 and [BL19] for a theoretical investigation of that effect. To overcome this shortcoming, several regularization approaches have been proposed in the literature. Consider for example the Phd Thesis [Ehr15] for a modern mathematical account on MRI reconstruction.

Figure 7.1: Visualization of the sampling pattern. Fourier coefficients along the white lines are kept (43%), while those ones along the black lines are thrown away.

Among the most successful variational regularization strategies were those ones, involving TV or even TGV semi norms, cf. [BUF07] and [KBPS11]. These approaches lead to reconstructions that are either more piecewise constant (TV) or more piecewise affine (TGV). The success of those methods motivates the question, whether the usage of spatially adaptive parameters as investigated theoretically in this thesis can even improve on these results. Furthermore, we want to check whether the automatic parameter choice strategy also delivers good results for the case of Fourier inpainting. In this context we again mention the recent works [HR17] and [HRWL17], where TV regularization with distributed parameters was tested on Fourier inpainting and also the paper [HPRS20], in which the automatic parameter choice strategy for spatially adaptive TGV was proposed for image denoising.

To eventually use the framework, presented in the last chapters, we introduce the operator

$$K = \mathcal{S} \circ \mathcal{F}_c \circ \pi_1^T : U_{M,N}^h \rightarrow U_{M_s,N_s}^h \times U_{M_s,N_s}^h \simeq \mathbb{C}^{N_s M_s} \quad (7.1)$$

where $\pi_1 : \mathbb{C}^{NM} \simeq U_{M,N}^h \times U_{M,N}^h \rightarrow U_{M,N}^h$ is the projection on the first coordinate or the real part of the given complex valued function respectively.

$$\mathcal{S} : U_{M,N}^h \times U_{M,N}^h \simeq \mathbb{C}^{NM} \rightarrow \mathbb{C}^{N_s M_s} \simeq U_{M_s,N_s}^h \times U_{M_s,N_s}^h$$

denotes a linear subsampling operator, which is specified later.

For the discrete two dimensional Fourier transform $\mathcal{F} : \mathbb{C}^{N \times M} \simeq W_{M,N}^h \rightarrow \mathbb{C}^{N \times M} \simeq W_{M,N}^h$ we use the

standard definition

$$(\mathcal{F}u)_{k,l} = \hat{u}_{k,l} := \frac{1}{\sqrt{MN}} \sum_{p=1}^N \sum_{q=1}^M u_{p,q} \exp\left(-\frac{2\pi i k p}{N}\right) \exp\left(-\frac{2\pi i k q}{M}\right) \quad \text{for } k = 1, \dots, N \text{ and } l = 1, \dots, M$$

together with its inverse

$$(\mathcal{F}^{-1}\hat{u})_{p,q} := \frac{1}{\sqrt{MN}} \sum_{k=1}^N \sum_{l=1}^M \hat{u}_{k,l} \exp\left(\frac{2\pi i k p}{N}\right) \exp\left(\frac{2\pi i l q}{M}\right) \quad \text{for } p = 1, \dots, N \text{ and } q = 1, \dots, M$$

Moreover we put the lowest frequencies in the center of the image by applying the following permutation

$$\begin{aligned} c_1 : \{1, \dots, N\} &\rightarrow \{1, \dots, N\} & c_1(k) &:= k + N \bmod N \\ c_2 : \{1, \dots, M\} &\rightarrow \{1, \dots, M\} & c_2(l) &:= l + M \bmod M \end{aligned}$$

Together with the corresponding linear and invertible permutation operator

$$(M_c x)_{k,l} := x_{c_1(k), c_2(l)}$$

we obtain the centered unitary Fourier transform

$$\mathcal{F}_c u = M_c \circ \mathcal{F}$$

In order to compute adjoint operators, we use the inner products $\langle u, v \rangle_{W^h}$ for $u, v \in U_{N,M}^h \times U_{N,M}^h \simeq W_{N,M}^h$. This is equivalent to the choice $Re \langle u, v \rangle_{\mathbb{C}^{2NM}}$ if u, v are seen as element of

$$\mathbb{C}^{2NM} \simeq U_{N,M}^h \times U_{N,M}^h \simeq W_{N,M}^h$$

One can easily check, that this choice leads to the following adjoint operators:

$$\begin{aligned} \pi_1^T : U_{N,M}^h &\rightarrow U_{N,M}^h \times U_{N,M}^h & \pi_1^*(u) &= (u, 0) \\ \mathcal{F}_c^T : \mathbb{C}^{N \times M} &\rightarrow \mathbb{C}^{N \times M} & \mathcal{F}_c^T u &= \mathcal{F}_c^{-1} u \end{aligned}$$

In conclusion, the adjoint of the transformation K is given by

$$K^T = \pi_1 \circ \mathcal{F}_c^{-1} \circ \mathcal{S}^T$$

7.1 Generation of Test Data and Experimental Setting

The numerical tests, which are shown in the following section are using simulated MRI images. This means that we do not take real world k-space data from an MRI scanner, but instead we chose MRI images, which have already been reconstructed and use them as our ground truth $u_{true} \in U_{M,N}^h$. Afterwards we apply the matrix $K = \mathcal{S} \circ \mathcal{F}_c \circ \pi_1^T$ from (7.1) and add some artificial gaussian noise with zero mean and variance $\sigma^2 = 0.33$. More formally, the test data is generated via

$$f = K u_{true} + \eta \quad \text{where } \eta \sim \mathcal{N}(0, \sigma^2 I_{N \times M}) \quad (7.2)$$

Given the generated test data f and the true variance $\sigma^2 > 0$ we are trying to recover u_{true} . The clean images are chosen from the collection, shown in Figure 7.3. These images represent typical MRI scans, that could occur in the daily practical life of a radiologist. Each image is a grey scale image, whose values are normed between 0 and 1 and which is of size $N \times M = 256 \times 256$ pixels. Although this is still a standard size for MRI, note that due to the high computational demand of our

method, higher resolutions are intractable for the time being. The concrete subsampling operator $\mathcal{S} : U_{N,M}^h \times U_{N,M}^h \rightarrow U_{N_S, M_S}^h \times U_{N_S, M_S}^h$ with $N_S < N, M_S < M$ is defined via:

$$(\mathcal{S} u)_{i,j} := x_{i,\pi(j)} \quad \text{for } u \in \mathbb{C}^{N \times M} \simeq U_{N,M}^h \times U_{N,M}^h \quad (7.3)$$

where $\pi : \{1, \dots, M_S\} \rightarrow \{1, \dots, M\}$ is a strictly monotone increasing function indicating, which Fourier coefficients are kept for our reconstruction. The rows, assigned to indexes, which are not in the set $\{\pi(1), \dots, \pi(M_S)\}$ are thrown away. The subsampling operator, we use in our experiment corresponds to the so called Cartesian subsampling, i.e. sampling along lines, which are parallel to the coordinate axes. Our specific choice is visualized in Figure 7.1. Therefore we defined the mapping $\pi : \{1, \dots, M_S\} \rightarrow \{1, \dots, M\}$ inductively via $\pi(1) = 1$ and

$$\pi(i+1) := \begin{cases} \pi(i) + 3 & \text{for } 1 \leq \pi(i) \leq M/2 - 30 \text{ or } M/2 + 30 \leq \pi(i) \leq M \\ \pi(i) + 1 & \text{otherwise} \end{cases}$$

Note, that due to the strict monotonicity of $\pi(\cdot)$, the spatial ordering of Ku in the Fourier domain is kept. This is essential for the local variance estimator $R(u)$ to work fine. However, to adopt this approach for other sampling patterns is difficult, as this spatial ordering, in for instance radial sampling, see [Ehr15] is not given anymore. Therefore in this regime, it is possible to stack all Fourier coefficients in a one dimensional vector and apply the local variance estimator in one dimension. This has been demonstrated successfully in the recent work [HRWL17] for spatially adaptive TV.

Choice of the model parameters As our approach is quite complex, we have to adjust several parameters manually in advance. These parameters are found via simple gridding by hand. We present our configuration in the following table

variabel name	short description	parameter value
γ	Huber smoothing parameter, see (5.7)	10^{-3}
$\alpha_{0,0}$	Initial parameter for α_0	0.25
$\alpha_{1,0}$	Initial parameter for α_1	0.15
h	discretization parameter	1
δ	smoothing parameter for the max operator, see (5.8)	10^{-7}
(η, μ, μ_K)	Other lower level parameters, see (6.10)	$(0.5, 10^{-2}, 10^{-7})$
tol_g	stopping tolerance for newton algorithm, see algorithm 2	10^{-7}
tol_α	stopping tolerance for projection algorithm, see algorithm 3	10^{-7}
ϵ_α	parameter for the projection, see algorithm 3	10^{-5}
$(\underline{\alpha}_0, \bar{\alpha}_0)$	parameters for the box constraints for α_0 , see (6.7)	$(10^{-2}, 10)$
$(\underline{\alpha}_1, \bar{\alpha}_1)$	parameters for the box constraints for α_1 , see (6.7)	$(10^{-4}, 10)$
(λ_1, λ_2)	upper level regularization parameters, see (\mathbb{P}^h)	$(10^{-11}, 2 \cdot 10^{-7})$
n_W	parameter for the local variance estimator, see (6.5)	7
(τ_0^0, τ_0^1)		$(5 \cdot 10^{-2}, 10^2)$
c	Armijo linesearch parameters, see algorithm 4	10^{-9}
(θ^-, θ^+)		$(0.25, 2)$

Figure 7.2: Table of the model parameters

Following again [HRWL17], the parameters for the tight variance corridor are computed from the rules

$$\underline{\sigma}^2 = \sigma^2 \left(1 - \frac{\sqrt{2}}{n_W}\right) \quad \bar{\sigma}^2 = \sigma^2 \left(1 + \frac{\sqrt{2}}{n_W}\right)$$

Eventually note that this parameter setting is only the product of manual testing and thus probably not optimal. Especially the upper level parameters λ_0, λ_1 seem to have a high impact on the quality of the solution. Our numerical tests suggest, that relatively high values for λ_2 produce good results, i.e. the spatial varying regularization parameter should not oscillate too fast. Additional attention needs to be paid to the initial values $\alpha_{0,0}$ and $\alpha_{1,0}$. Although, the algorithm is able to adapt to the different regions in the image and can possibly switch between the piecewise affine and the piecewise constant regime, initializations with parameters $\alpha_{1,0} \gg \alpha_{0,0}$ lead to reconstructions, which are clearly more piecewise affine.

Figure 7.3: Three MRI images, which are used as a ground truth for our numerical tests.

Conversely, the initialization with $\alpha_{0,0} \gg \alpha_{1,0}$ produces results that are more like typical TV-reconstructions. For the current use case, we found the initialization with larger $\alpha_{1,0}$ slightly more appropriate. We run our algorithm with the parameters, presented in table 7.2. The tests are performed on a laptop with Intel i7 CPU, 4 cores and 16 GB memory. For the implementation we use Matlab R2018b. The linear systems occurring in the discrete Newton step and the adjoint state equation are solved by the BiCGSTAB method [Vor92] up to an accuracy of 10^{-7} . Note that the standard backslash operator in Matlab does not work in our case, since it is not possible to store the whole representation matrix of K in the memory. In contrast to that, the BiCGSTAB method only requires vector matrix multiplications of the form Ku for given $u \in U_{M,N}^h$, which can be in this case efficiently implemented with the discrete fast Fourier transform without storing the whole matrix.

Our method is compared against TGV reconstruction with scalar parameters $\alpha_1 \in \mathbb{R}^2$ and TV reconstruction, also with scalar parameter $\alpha_2 \in \mathbb{R}$ on the dataset, presented in Figure 7.3. The (non smooth) minimization problems, appearing in the TGV and the TV reconstruction methods read

$$\min_{u \in L^2(\Omega)} \frac{1}{2} \|Ku - f\|_{L^2}^2 + TGV_{\alpha_1}^2(u)$$

for the TGV case and

$$\min_{u \in L^2(\Omega)} \frac{1}{2} \|Ku - f\|_{L^2}^2 + \alpha_2 TV(u)$$

for the scalar TV case. We solve these problems with the primal dual proximal point algorithm, introduced by Chambolle and Pock in [CP11], see also [BL19]. We use the implementation suggested

Figure 7.4: Least Squares Reconstruction and illustration of the aliasing artifacts.

in [KBPS11] for TGV and in [BL19] for TV. To quantify the quality of the reconstructions we use the classical metrics PSNR and SSIM. The scalar regularization parameters, $\alpha_1 \in \mathbb{R}^2$ for TGV and $\alpha_2 \in \mathbb{R}$ for the TV reconstruction are found manually - we start with very high values and make 20 gridsearch steps to find those parameters, for which the PSNR and the SSIM are pretty high, while the aliasing artifacts stay mostly suppressed. For an account on the quality measures for image reconstruction used here, we again refer to the recent textbook [BL19] and the original article [WBSS04]. Note again that we compare our method against the original TV and TGV reconstruction methods and not against the (Huber) smoothed version that is used in our procedure.

7.2 Numerical Results

The results of our tests are presented in Figure 7.6 and in Figure 7.7. In the latter figure we cut out some parts of the reconstructed images and enlarged them in order to emphasize the details. Furthermore we present the least squares solution in Figure 7.4. This is done to illustrate the impact of the under sampling and the gaussian noise. The first tests indicate that the proposed method is able to find spatially distributed parameters, which are well adapted to the different image regions. This can be seen in Figure 7.5 where the resulting distributed parameters are depicted. The adaption of the regularization parameters to the different image regions is also reflected in higher PSNR values across all test images. Never the less when considering the SSIM, we see that the scalar TV reconstruction is in the first and the third image the superior method. This is not very surprising since the chosen

Figure 7.5: The discrete weightfunction $\alpha_1(\cdot)$. The origin corresponds to the lower left corner of the images.

clean MRI images are piecewise constant in a very large region of the image and therefore the TV reconstruction delivers often very satisfactory results. The authors personal visual impression is that the proposed method produces similar results as the scalar ROF model in the corresponding piecewise constant regions of the image. However there are also parts in the image where fine structures need to be preserved such as in the region of the neck in image b or at the nose in image a. In these areas, the utilization of spatially varying parameters leads to a slight increase in sharpness and in contrast. The reason for this is that the resulting spatially varying parameters in these parts of the image are pretty small, see Figure 7.5. We also highlight the fact, that our method is able to suppress aliasing effects

Figure 7.6: Results of the numerical tests. Left: Our bilevel TGV method, middle: scalar TGV, right: scalar TV.

nearly totally. This is not always the case for TV and TGV reconstruction, where good PSNR and SSIM results come at the cost of some aliasing artifacts, which are not filtered out properly. This effect can be observed in particular the third row in Figure 7.7. To prevent these artifacts it would be necessary

to increase the scalar parameters, which would in turn directly lead to an over smoothing and worse PSNR and SSIM values.

Short note on the computational demand Even if our method performs pretty well and behaves quite robust with respect to small changes in the parameters, the main drawback is the run time. This is on average 100 times slower than the run time for the scalar TGV method and nearly 300 times slower than the reconstruction time for scalar TV. Additionally for this comparison we have not even used things like Nesterov acceleration or GPU computing, to speed up the first order proximal point method by Chambolle and Pock. This would end up in even higher differences regarding the computational speed.

Figure 7.7: Details of the reconstructions. Left: Our bilevel TGV method, middle: scalar TGV, right: scalar TV.

7.3 Conclusion and Possible Further Investigations

In this work, we investigated an automatic parameter choice strategy for Huberized Total Generalized Variation with spatially varying parameters. As indicated by the first numerical tests in the previous section, the proposed method delivers comparable results to state of the art variational methods in the image reconstruction task of Fourier inpainting. Although the extension from scalar to spatially varying parameters has not a large impact on the quality measures PSNR and SSIM, our approach clearly demonstrated its value in the suppression of the well known aliasing artifacts, see again the third row of Figure 7.7. However, in terms of the SSIM value, the classical ROF model still delivers in most cases the best results, which is clearly due to the special structure of many MRI images (sparsity in the gradient). We would now like to briefly discuss which points in the current model can still be improved and where further research questions could arise. The first point we would like to mention here is the relatively low subsampling rate in our approach. This means that a pretty large number of frequencies must be sampled in order to achieve a sufficiently good result. Otherwise, the local variance estimation leads sometimes to poor outcomes. Consequently, improved variance estimators and in general other upperlevel objectives with more sophisticated loss functions could lead to a significant enhancement of these results.

As we already pointed out, another drawback of the proposed method is the computational demand. In each iteration a Newton method is used to solve the state equation and the (Huber) smoothed TGV problem respectively. This in turn requires in each step the solution of a very large linear system which in our case is anything but sparse. For this task we used the classical BiCGstabl method, whose convergence speed mainly depends on the condition number of the involved system matrix. Vanishing smoothness parameters ($\gamma, \mu, \mu_K, \delta \rightarrow 0$) seem to lead to a major increase in the condition of this matrix and thus to a deterioration of the convergence behavior. However this empirical observation needs to be verified theoretically in future investigations. Once we have properly understood on which quantities the spectrum and thus the condition number of the system matrix depends, the next step could include the analysis and development of suitable preconditioners in each Newton step.

A further aspect is the reconstruction of images with higher resolution. Up to now we can only reconstruct images of size 256×256 on standard notebooks, which is by a far not enough for the multi megapixel cameras of the latest generation. To deal with higher resolution images, a future work could consider for example Schwartz domain decomposition methods, as for instance recently proposed in [VCRS17] for spatially adaptive TV denoising.

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Selbständigkeitserklärung

Ich erkläre, dass ich die vorliegende Arbeit selbstständig verfasst und noch nicht für andere Prüfungen eingereicht habe. Sämtliche Quellen, einschließlich Internetquellen, die unverändert oder abgewandelt wiedergegeben werden, insbesondere Quellen für Texte, Grafiken, Tabellen und Bilder, sind als solche kenntlich gemacht. Mir ist bekannt, dass bei Verstößen gegen diese Grundsätze ein Verfahren wegen Täuschungsversuchs bzw. Täuschung eingeleitet wird.

Berlin, den 29. November 2020

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